

Tabla 3.

Diferencia entre la cota del SRTM y el IGVSb e identificación de zonas de la cuenca.

East	North	SRTM_Elevat	IGVSb_Eleva	BasinLevel	Error
-70,741231	8,739419	3584	3600	High	-16
-70,741674	8,738901	3615	3600	High	15
-70,741634	8,738311	3602	3600	High	2
-70,753273	8,721694	3569	3600	High	-31
-70,753127	8,722248	3582	3600	High	-18
-70,752907	8,722728	3528	3600	High	-72
-70,752724	8,723246	3555	3600	High	-45
-70,752985	8,723613	3591	3600	High	-9
-70,753099	8,724166	3602	3600	High	2
-70,752618	8,724353	3581	3600	High	-19
-70,752175	8,724724	3604	3600	High	4
-70,751842	8,724947	3577	3600	High	-23
-70,751696	8,725427	3571	3600	High	-29
-70,752254	8,725867	3604	3600	High	4
-70,751886	8,726422	3581	3600	High	-19
-70,75148	8,72683	3581	3600	High	-19
-70,750963	8,727201	3619	3600	High	19
-70,75026	8,727536	3605	3600	High	5
-70,749518	8,727576	3565	3600	High	-35
-70,749297	8,727725	3565	3600	High	-35
-70,749598	8,728646	3609	3600	High	9
-70,749674	8,729162	3599	3600	High	-1
-70,749679	8,730158	3613	3600	High	13
-70,749126	8,730788	3610	3600	High	10
-70,748313	8,731382	3613	3600	High	13
-70,748128	8,731567	3613	3600	High	13
-70,74761	8,731827	3609	3600	High	9
-70,74713	8,732125	3630	3600	High	30
-70,746611	8,732312	3626	3600	High	26
-70,746128	8,732056	3607	3600	High	7
-70,745756	8,731725	3607	3600	High	7
-70,74531	8,731543	3610	3600	High	10
-70,744791	8,731545	3610	3600	High	10
-70,744534	8,731989	3568	3600	High	-32
-70,744202	8,73236	3614	3600	High	14
-70,74387	8,732767	3614	3600	High	14
-70,743315	8,733065	3623	3600	High	23
-70,742834	8,733251	3600	3600	High	0
-70,74265	8,733547	3600	3600	High	0
-70,742466	8,733917	3635	3600	High	35
-70,741834	8,733625	3587	3600	High	-13
-70,741354	8,734033	3637	3600	High	37
-70,740798	8,734072	3619	3600	High	19
-70,740352	8,733779	3594	3600	High	-6
-70,73987	8,733855	3594	3600	High	-6

-70,739761	8,734224	3594	3600	High	-6
-70,739949	8,73474	3587	3600	High	-13
-70,740249	8,73555	3570	3600	High	-30
-70,740328	8,736583	3553	3600	High	-47
-70,740701	8,737134	3565	3600	High	-35
-70,741186	8,737796	3565	3600	High	-35
-70,761186	8,717138	3578	3600	High	-22
-70,760816	8,717435	3578	3600	High	-22
-70,760113	8,71777	3558	3600	High	-42
-70,759484	8,718032	3604	3600	High	4
-70,758892	8,718219	3604	3600	High	4
-70,758225	8,718259	3610	3600	High	10
-70,757632	8,718335	3634	3600	High	34
-70,757335	8,718152	3634	3600	High	34
-70,756925	8,717822	3602	3600	High	2
-70,756367	8,717382	3602	3600	High	2
-70,755587	8,717054	3570	3600	High	-30
-70,754621	8,716726	3586	3600	High	-14
-70,753991	8,716618	3607	3600	High	7
-70,753656	8,716362	3634	3600	High	34
-70,753061	8,716069	3625	3600	High	25
-70,752725	8,715554	3639	3600	High	39
-70,752795	8,714706	3647	3600	High	47
-70,753423	8,714223	3649	3600	High	49
-70,754386	8,713997	3620	3600	High	20
-70,755275	8,713846	3609	3600	High	9
-70,756201	8,713657	3624	3600	High	24
-70,75657	8,713139	3612	3600	High	12
-70,756345	8,712771	3582	3600	High	-18
-70,755974	8,712662	3608	3600	High	8
-70,755157	8,71226	3631	3600	High	31
-70,754451	8,712005	3604	3600	High	4
-70,754006	8,711897	3604	3600	High	4
-70,753597	8,71164	3629	3600	High	29
-70,753224	8,71131	3629	3600	High	29
-70,752741	8,711017	3610	3600	High	10
-70,752295	8,710687	3610	3600	High	10
-70,751774	8,710468	3628	3600	High	28
-70,751254	8,710175	3590	3600	High	-10
-70,750771	8,709883	3602	3600	High	2
-70,750472	8,709404	3577	3600	High	-23
-70,750137	8,709185	3587	3600	High	-13
-70,749876	8,708854	3587	3600	High	-13
-70,749543	8,708966	3546	3600	High	-54
-70,749508	8,709335	3546	3600	High	-54
-70,74988	8,709776	3569	3600	High	-31

-70,750254	8,710291	3569	3600	High	-31
-70,750553	8,710806	3598	3600	High	-2
-70,750703	8,711322	3598	3600	High	-2
-70,750854	8,711874	3598	3600	High	-2
-70,751042	8,712464	3581	3600	High	-19
-70,751157	8,713275	3558	3600	High	-42
-70,751346	8,714048	3601	3600	High	1
-70,751535	8,714711	3583	3600	High	-17
-70,751612	8,715412	3583	3600	High	-17
-70,751466	8,715855	3602	3600	High	2
-70,751171	8,716226	3548	3600	High	-52
-70,751136	8,716668	3560	3600	High	-40
-70,751323	8,716926	3609	3600	High	9
-70,752139	8,71707	3640	3600	High	40
-70,753103	8,717065	3634	3600	High	34
-70,753402	8,717543	3591	3600	High	-9
-70,753444	8,71876	3526	3600	High	-74
-70,753338	8,719683	3542	3600	High	-58
-70,75338	8,720863	3555	3600	High	-45
-70,753404	8,718134	3535	3600	High	-65
-70,753341	8,720347	3542	3600	High	-58
-70,753446	8,719129	3526	3600	High	-74
-70,732486	8,740547	3580	3600	High	-20
-70,732781	8,740288	3579	3600	High	-21
-70,733228	8,740655	3607	3600	High	7
-70,7336	8,740985	3607	3600	High	7
-70,734048	8,74161	3617	3600	High	17
-70,734347	8,742014	3617	3600	High	17
-70,734793	8,742381	3641	3600	High	41
-70,735387	8,742489	3641	3600	High	41
-70,736202	8,742375	3627	3600	High	27
-70,736905	8,742003	3575	3600	High	-25
-70,738015	8,741592	3626	3600	High	26
-70,738865	8,740813	3616	3600	High	16
-70,74027	8,740106	3597	3600	High	-3
-70,729653	8,745245	3578	3600	High	-22
-70,730137	8,745723	3628	3600	High	28
-70,730805	8,745867	3611	3600	High	11
-70,731472	8,745827	3619	3600	High	19
-70,732028	8,745714	3619	3600	High	19
-70,732471	8,745417	3625	3600	High	25
-70,732617	8,744826	3584	3600	High	-16
-70,732391	8,744163	3576	3600	High	-24
-70,7325	8,743535	3579	3600	High	-21
-70,732608	8,742871	3575	3600	High	-25
-70,732753	8,74228	3575	3600	High	-25

-70,732751	8,741763	3569	3600	High	-31
-70,732563	8,741285	3569	3600	High	-31
-70,732376	8,740917	3580	3600	High	-20
-70,711032	8,755917	3589	3600	High	-11
-70,711362	8,755178	3616	3600	High	16
-70,711768	8,75477	3616	3600	High	16
-70,711988	8,754216	3579	3600	High	-21
-70,712246	8,753772	3639	3600	High	39
-70,712466	8,753291	3608	3600	High	8
-70,7125	8,752627	3567	3600	High	-33
-70,712684	8,752221	3567	3600	High	-33
-70,712978	8,751777	3611	3600	High	11
-70,713087	8,751149	3594	3600	High	-6
-70,713343	8,750484	3594	3600	High	-6
-70,713899	8,750444	3615	3600	High	15
-70,714383	8,750811	3615	3600	High	15
-70,71516	8,750476	3615	3600	High	15
-70,715604	8,750215	3583	3600	High	-17
-70,715973	8,749771	3583	3600	High	-17
-70,716527	8,749363	3562	3600	High	-38
-70,716859	8,748919	3562	3600	High	-38
-70,7173	8,748105	3568	3600	High	-32
-70,718001	8,747327	3589	3600	High	-11
-70,718665	8,74666	3567	3600	High	-33
-70,719035	8,7464	3602	3600	High	2
-70,719553	8,746177	3557	3600	High	-43
-70,720329	8,745583	3579	3600	High	-21
-70,721069	8,745284	3575	3600	High	-25
-70,721661	8,74506	3599	3600	High	-1
-70,722254	8,74491	3627	3600	High	27
-70,72281	8,744981	3627	3600	High	27
-70,723294	8,745422	3650	3600	High	50
-70,723519	8,745937	3650	3600	High	50
-70,723411	8,746712	3642	3600	High	42
-70,723416	8,747635	3658	3600	High	58
-70,723825	8,748038	3665	3600	High	65
-70,724383	8,748294	3665	3600	High	65
-70,724903	8,748476	3624	3600	High	24
-70,725793	8,748509	3581	3600	High	-19
-70,726423	8,748432	3572	3600	High	-28
-70,727089	8,748208	3617	3600	High	17
-70,727457	8,747579	3567	3600	High	-33
-70,727565	8,746878	3555	3600	High	-45
-70,72771	8,746176	3562	3600	High	-38
-70,727967	8,745548	3629	3600	High	29
-70,728336	8,745177	3598	3600	High	-2

-70,729114	8,745063	3597	3600	High	-3
-70,703144	8,766245	3586	3600	High	-14
-70,703699	8,76591	3586	3600	High	-14
-70,704068	8,76554	3623	3600	High	23
-70,704474	8,765095	3569	3600	High	-31
-70,704917	8,764651	3617	3600	High	17
-70,705359	8,764206	3563	3600	High	-37
-70,705878	8,764019	3619	3600	High	19
-70,706322	8,763796	3673	3600	High	73
-70,706617	8,763462	3605	3600	High	5
-70,706874	8,763019	3605	3600	High	5
-70,707095	8,762501	3609	3600	High	9
-70,70739	8,762205	3609	3600	High	9
-70,707909	8,762239	3609	3600	High	9
-70,708242	8,76198	3589	3600	High	-11
-70,708647	8,761461	3589	3600	High	-11
-70,708941	8,760833	3602	3600	High	2
-70,709308	8,760056	3563	3600	High	-37
-70,709788	8,759464	3602	3600	High	2
-70,710191	8,758429	3588	3600	High	-12
-70,710373	8,757801	3576	3600	High	-24
-70,710592	8,756989	3622	3600	High	22
-70,710849	8,756397	3622	3600	High	22
-70,682093	8,777037	3575	3600	High	-25
-70,682537	8,776851	3575	3600	High	-25
-70,683168	8,776996	3562	3600	High	-38
-70,683946	8,776845	3577	3600	High	-23
-70,684465	8,776658	3577	3600	High	-23
-70,685057	8,776397	3609	3600	High	9
-70,685501	8,776137	3576	3600	High	-24
-70,685909	8,776172	3576	3600	High	-24
-70,686392	8,776391	3628	3600	High	28
-70,686913	8,776757	3628	3600	High	28
-70,687544	8,777013	3593	3600	High	-7
-70,688324	8,777231	3640	3600	High	40
-70,688954	8,777191	3643	3600	High	43
-70,689585	8,777188	3637	3600	High	37
-70,690177	8,777112	3637	3600	High	37
-70,690659	8,777036	3580	3600	High	-20
-70,691252	8,776886	3584	3600	High	-16
-70,691882	8,776735	3584	3600	High	-16
-70,692474	8,776548	3599	3600	High	-1
-70,692955	8,776325	3614	3600	High	14
-70,693511	8,776248	3560	3600	High	-40
-70,694104	8,776172	3578	3600	High	-22
-70,694808	8,776132	3591	3600	High	-9

-70,695364	8,775945	3591	3600	High	-9
-70,695956	8,775758	3630	3600	High	30
-70,696177	8,775277	3556	3600	High	-44
-70,696434	8,774907	3603	3600	High	3
-70,696766	8,774537	3559	3600	High	-41
-70,697173	8,77424	3608	3600	High	8
-70,697616	8,773869	3608	3600	High	8
-70,697948	8,773425	3616	3600	High	16
-70,698205	8,772907	3579	3600	High	-21
-70,698611	8,772463	3579	3600	High	-21
-70,699055	8,772129	3626	3600	High	26
-70,699832	8,771867	3595	3600	High	-5
-70,700498	8,771458	3618	3600	High	18
-70,701015	8,771013	3581	3600	High	-19
-70,700973	8,770017	3582	3600	High	-18
-70,700451	8,769429	3612	3600	High	12
-70,700005	8,769136	3591	3600	High	-9
-70,699486	8,769176	3570	3600	High	-30
-70,699039	8,768624	3575	3600	High	-25
-70,699148	8,768144	3575	3600	High	-25
-70,699628	8,76781	3597	3600	High	-3
-70,700294	8,767401	3597	3600	High	-3
-70,700997	8,767177	3615	3600	High	15
-70,701738	8,766841	3602	3600	High	2
-70,702626	8,766616	3633	3600	High	33
-70,700858	8,777285	3543	3600	High	-57
-70,700377	8,777582	3563	3600	High	-37
-70,69986	8,777917	3535	3600	High	-65
-70,699343	8,778362	3564	3600	High	-36
-70,698713	8,778549	3638	3600	High	38
-70,698456	8,779067	3621	3600	High	21
-70,69805	8,779511	3621	3600	High	21
-70,698015	8,780065	3617	3600	High	17
-70,697982	8,780987	3613	3600	High	13
-70,697986	8,781725	3630	3600	High	30
-70,697988	8,782278	3634	3600	High	34
-70,698102	8,78272	3634	3600	High	34
-70,698327	8,783457	3645	3600	High	45
-70,698479	8,784083	3614	3600	High	14
-70,698221	8,784454	3614	3600	High	14
-70,697777	8,784677	3577	3600	High	-23
-70,697	8,785049	3618	3600	High	18
-70,696519	8,785347	3618	3600	High	18
-70,696187	8,785791	3615	3600	High	15
-70,695929	8,786087	3615	3600	High	15
-70,695783	8,786678	3589	3600	High	-11

-70,695564	8,787306	3557	3600	High	-43
-70,695044	8,787161	3542	3600	High	-58
-70,694523	8,786868	3566	3600	High	-34
-70,693928	8,786354	3566	3600	High	-34
-70,693296	8,786136	3603	3600	High	3
-70,692628	8,786065	3605	3600	High	5
-70,692036	8,786252	3530	3600	High	-70
-70,691555	8,786586	3530	3600	High	-70
-70,691037	8,786736	3569	3600	High	-31
-70,690558	8,787402	3517	3600	High	-83
-70,689858	8,788438	3565	3600	High	-35
-70,689416	8,789141	3601	3600	High	1
-70,68916	8,789917	3605	3600	High	5
-70,688868	8,790841	3600	3600	High	0
-70,688722	8,791468	3592	3600	High	-8
-70,688355	8,792245	3543	3600	High	-57
-70,687873	8,792247	3542	3600	High	-58
-70,68787	8,79162	3556	3600	High	-44
-70,68787	8,79173	3556	3600	High	-44
-70,687831	8,791251	3556	3600	High	-44
-70,687901	8,790255	3528	3600	High	-72
-70,688305	8,789552	3581	3600	High	-19
-70,688673	8,788739	3558	3600	High	-42
-70,688818	8,788185	3594	3600	High	-6
-70,688778	8,78741	3594	3600	High	-6
-70,688812	8,78682	3607	3600	High	7
-70,689218	8,786412	3607	3600	High	7
-70,689994	8,785782	3624	3600	High	24
-70,690103	8,785228	3591	3600	High	-9
-70,689948	8,78379	3584	3600	High	-16
-70,689723	8,783127	3604	3600	High	4
-70,689424	8,782759	3582	3600	High	-18
-70,689015	8,78254	3582	3600	High	-18
-70,688496	8,782431	3559	3600	High	-41
-70,687938	8,782176	3559	3600	High	-41
-70,687492	8,781846	3608	3600	High	8
-70,687084	8,781811	3608	3600	High	8
-70,686825	8,781959	3593	3600	High	-7
-70,68627	8,782331	3535	3600	High	-65
-70,685713	8,782001	3566	3600	High	-34
-70,685339	8,781339	3521	3600	High	-79
-70,684853	8,780566	3568	3600	High	-32
-70,684405	8,779941	3550	3600	High	-50
-70,684292	8,779462	3572	3600	High	-28
-70,683993	8,77891	3572	3600	High	-28
-70,68362	8,778395	3574	3600	High	-26

-70,683026	8,77825	3574	3600	High	-26
-70,682281	8,777664	3581	3600	High	-19
-70,717079	8,764522	3655	3600	High	55
-70,716746	8,764818	3620	3600	High	20
-70,716267	8,765411	3620	3600	High	20
-70,715824	8,765929	3622	3600	High	22
-70,715085	8,766486	3606	3600	High	6
-70,714458	8,76719	3616	3600	High	16
-70,714164	8,767671	3616	3600	High	16
-70,713832	8,768152	3583	3600	High	-17
-70,713463	8,768559	3608	3600	High	8
-70,713018	8,768524	3608	3600	High	8
-70,712647	8,768415	3597	3600	High	-3
-70,71209	8,768233	3597	3600	High	-3
-70,711681	8,768161	3580	3600	High	-20
-70,710977	8,768238	3568	3600	High	-32
-70,710459	8,768351	3568	3600	High	-32
-70,709718	8,768576	3578	3600	High	-22
-70,709238	8,768984	3565	3600	High	-35
-70,708758	8,769429	3565	3600	High	-35
-70,708241	8,769911	3596	3600	High	-4
-70,707761	8,770429	3623	3600	High	23
-70,707393	8,770947	3623	3600	High	23
-70,707172	8,771428	3590	3600	High	-10
-70,707027	8,772166	3641	3600	High	41
-70,706994	8,772904	3641	3600	High	41
-70,706811	8,773495	3618	3600	High	18
-70,706554	8,774087	3627	3600	High	27
-70,706521	8,774899	3636	3600	High	36
-70,706486	8,775489	3629	3600	High	29
-70,706526	8,776153	3629	3600	High	29
-70,706492	8,776817	3612	3600	High	12
-70,706309	8,77726	3600	3600	High	0
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-70,706018	8,778405	3611	3600	High	11
-70,705538	8,77885	3557	3600	High	-43
-70,705092	8,778631	3609	3600	High	9
-70,704868	8,7783	3609	3600	High	9
-70,704643	8,777748	3634	3600	High	34
-70,704381	8,777232	3582	3600	High	-18
-70,703822	8,776792	3608	3600	High	8
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-70,702709	8,776687	3605	3600	High	5
-70,70208	8,776874	3611	3600	High	11
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-70,748558	8,716422	3457	3400	High	57
-70,748225	8,716534	3457	3400	High	57
-70,747669	8,716574	3414	3400	High	14
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-70,746854	8,716762	3345	3400	High	-55
-70,746634	8,717242	3385	3400	High	-15
-70,746784	8,717721	3385	3400	High	-15
-70,747267	8,717867	3441	3400	High	41
-70,747715	8,718418	3378	3400	High	-22
-70,747938	8,718638	3413	3400	High	13
-70,748236	8,718969	3377	3400	High	-23
-70,748571	8,719189	3377	3400	High	-23
-70,748905	8,719335	3408	3400	High	8
-70,74935	8,719296	3408	3400	High	8
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-70,750612	8,719511	3439	3400	High	39
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-70,7511	8,720874	3385	3400	High	-15
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-70,74885	8,723282	3412	3400	High	12
-70,74874	8,723725	3358	3400	High	-42
-70,748669	8,724316	3372	3400	High	-28
-70,74856	8,724796	3403	3400	High	3
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-70,748043	8,725315	3403	3400	High	3
-70,747784	8,725316	3388	3400	High	-12
-70,747414	8,725428	3413	3400	High	13
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-70,747045	8,725836	3322	3400	High	-78
-70,747083	8,726204	3413	3400	High	13
-70,74716	8,72672	3392	3400	High	-8
-70,747162	8,727126	3416	3400	High	16
-70,746978	8,727422	3379	3400	High	-21
-70,746535	8,727793	3379	3400	High	-21
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-70,744128	8,728431	3427	3400	High	27
-70,743756	8,728138	3427	3400	High	27
-70,743495	8,727955	3438	3400	High	38
-70,743124	8,727809	3372	3400	High	-28
-70,742827	8,727773	3380	3400	High	-20
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-70,742682	8,728401	3385	3400	High	-15
-70,742721	8,728991	3388	3400	High	-12
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-70,742023	8,730249	3400	3400	High	0
-70,741431	8,730509	3439	3400	High	39
-70,740839	8,730734	3449	3400	High	49
-70,740096	8,730479	3479	3400	High	79
-70,73965	8,730333	3431	3400	High	31
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-70,74231	8,704287	3404	3400	High	4
-70,741977	8,704362	3390	3400	High	-10
-70,741459	8,704512	3390	3400	High	-10
-70,740792	8,704699	3431	3400	High	31
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-70,736749	8,704238	3412	3400	High	12
-70,736341	8,70413	3412	3400	High	12
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-70,735077	8,703508	3386	3400	High	-14
-70,734558	8,703547	3386	3400	High	-14
-70,734149	8,703328	3386	3400	High	-14
-70,733889	8,703145	3386	3400	High	-14
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-70,733594	8,703515	3361	3400	High	-39
-70,733781	8,70392	3399	3400	High	-1
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-70,733971	8,704731	3398	3400	High	-2
-70,734047	8,705136	3398	3400	High	-2
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-70,733906	8,70676	3403	3400	High	3
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-70,736131	8,706897	3420	3400	High	20
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-70,735522	8,703432	3389	3400	High	-11
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-70,737935	8,704233	3395	3400	High	-5
-70,737243	8,706818	3423	3400	High	23
-70,737576	8,706743	3423	3400	High	23
-70,737946	8,706668	3422	3400	High	22
-70,738279	8,706482	3422	3400	High	22
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-70,739389	8,70596	3445	3400	High	45
-70,739945	8,705884	3431	3400	High	31
-70,740315	8,705698	3431	3400	High	31
-70,740907	8,705584	3413	3400	High	13
-70,7415	8,705545	3400	3400	High	0
-70,74202	8,705616	3400	3400	High	0
-70,742502	8,705725	3393	3400	High	-7
-70,743429	8,70572	3393	3400	High	-7
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-70,744023	8,705939	3407	3400	High	7
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-70,744359	8,706417	3362	3400	High	-38
-70,744694	8,7066	3408	3400	High	8
-70,742984	8,705759	3393	3400	High	-7
-70,745289	8,706966	3408	3400	High	8
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-70,745884	8,70748	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,746108	8,7077	3383	3400	High	-17
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-70,746741	8,708435	3410	3400	High	10
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-70,747041	8,709061	3358	3400	High	-42
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-70,747601	8,709943	3384	3400	High	-16
-70,747566	8,710386	3384	3400	High	-16
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-70,747902	8,710938	3372	3400	High	-28
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-70,748802	8,71311	3418	3400	High	18
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-70,748956	8,714253	3416	3400	High	16
-70,749032	8,714695	3422	3400	High	22
-70,748885	8,714954	3422	3400	High	22
-70,715804	8,745244	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,715727	8,744801	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,716095	8,744209	3361	3400	High	-39
-70,716427	8,743692	3377	3400	High	-23
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-70,71724	8,743134	3411	3400	High	11
-70,717386	8,742728	3385	3400	High	-15
-70,71731	8,742249	3385	3400	High	-15
-70,717197	8,741917	3392	3400	High	-8
-70,717085	8,741697	3392	3400	High	-8
-70,716935	8,741365	3342	3400	High	-58
-70,71686	8,741107	3361	3400	High	-39
-70,716709	8,740481	3361	3400	High	-39
-70,716892	8,739927	3371	3400	High	-29
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-70,71934	8,740174	3424	3400	High	24
-70,71986	8,74043	3461	3400	High	61
-70,720268	8,740391	3414	3400	High	14
-70,720786	8,740278	3407	3400	High	7
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-70,72212	8,739977	3402	3400	High	2
-70,722493	8,740528	3419	3400	High	19
-70,722754	8,740822	3419	3400	High	19
-70,72309	8,741337	3429	3400	High	29
-70,723611	8,741704	3429	3400	High	29
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-70,724542	8,742511	3446	3400	High	46
-70,725099	8,742767	3431	3400	High	31
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-70,726692	8,742464	3407	3400	High	7
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-70,728542	8,741607	3385	3400	High	-15
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-70,731258	8,735693	3443	3400	High	43
-70,731256	8,735176	3422	3400	High	22
-70,731403	8,734991	3422	3400	High	22
-70,731587	8,734585	3422	3400	High	22
-70,731883	8,734473	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,732181	8,734656	3430	3400	High	30
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-70,732777	8,73528	3430	3400	High	30
-70,733223	8,735647	3443	3400	High	43
-70,73378	8,735829	3419	3400	High	19
-70,734895	8,736266	3421	3400	High	21
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-70,735675	8,736632	3406	3400	High	6
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-70,737524	8,735664	3367	3400	High	-33
-70,737374	8,735185	3407	3400	High	7
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-70,737258	8,734116	3401	3400	High	1
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-70,738132	8,730755	3425	3400	High	25
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-70,695593	8,761013	3438	3400	High	38
-70,695891	8,761417	3458	3400	High	58
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-70,702943	8,762898	3377	3400	High	-23
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-70,703756	8,762304	3415	3400	High	15
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-70,705273	8,761486	3392	3400	High	-8
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-70,707807	8,756125	3332	3400	High	-68
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-70,710454	8,75117	3393	3400	High	-7
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-70,710933	8,750504	3393	3400	High	-7
-70,711042	8,749913	3388	3400	High	-12
-70,711002	8,74936	3369	3400	High	-31

-70,711111	8,748769	3369	3400	High	-31
-70,711219	8,748179	3341	3400	High	-59
-70,711477	8,747846	3355	3400	High	-45
-70,711847	8,747623	3355	3400	High	-45
-70,712291	8,747436	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,712736	8,747434	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,713144	8,747543	3370	3400	High	-30
-70,713848	8,747429	3370	3400	High	-30
-70,714552	8,747278	3370	3400	High	-30
-70,715255	8,747017	3343	3400	High	-57
-70,715699	8,74672	3388	3400	High	-12
-70,715808	8,74624	3386	3400	High	-14
-70,715805	8,745576	3386	3400	High	-14
-70,680787	8,779284	3368	3400	High	-32
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-70,680749	8,779026	3368	3400	High	-32
-70,680224	8,777885	3379	3400	High	-21
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-70,680504	8,778216	3406	3400	High	6
-70,679813	8,777149	3379	3400	High	-21
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-70,679399	8,775823	3358	3400	High	-42
-70,679193	8,775399	3399	3400	High	-1
-70,678988	8,775216	3399	3400	High	-1
-70,678524	8,774923	3360	3400	High	-40
-70,677929	8,77463	3360	3400	High	-40
-70,677779	8,774225	3340	3400	High	-60
-70,677757	8,773543	3344	3400	High	-56
-70,677754	8,772916	3347	3400	High	-53
-70,677753	8,772639	3347	3400	High	-53
-70,677733	8,772196	3347	3400	High	-53
-70,677657	8,771828	3375	3400	High	-25
-70,677414	8,771515	3375	3400	High	-25
-70,677173	8,77135	3375	3400	High	-25
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-70,676076	8,770765	3349	3400	High	-51
-70,676186	8,770543	3349	3400	High	-51
-70,676352	8,770266	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,676777	8,770043	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,677165	8,769654	3402	3400	High	2
-70,677349	8,769431	3362	3400	High	-38
-70,677497	8,769191	3362	3400	High	-38
-70,67783	8,769023	3362	3400	High	-38
-70,678461	8,76915	3400	3400	High	0

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-70,679114	8,770143	3394	3400	High	-6
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-70,679451	8,770971	3418	3400	High	18
-70,67962	8,771247	3389	3400	High	-11
-70,679973	8,771412	3422	3400	High	22
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-70,680233	8,771484	3422	3400	High	22
-70,680566	8,771428	3423	3400	High	23
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-70,681476	8,771792	3394	3400	High	-6
-70,681719	8,772105	3436	3400	High	36
-70,681869	8,772473	3436	3400	High	36
-70,682131	8,773007	3404	3400	High	4
-70,682355	8,773338	3404	3400	High	4
-70,682597	8,773706	3404	3400	High	4
-70,683155	8,774127	3419	3400	High	19
-70,683823	8,774106	3420	3400	High	20
-70,684564	8,774066	3420	3400	High	20
-70,684935	8,774083	3413	3400	High	13
-70,685529	8,774191	3413	3400	High	13
-70,686012	8,774484	3413	3400	High	13
-70,686365	8,774482	3407	3400	High	7
-70,68681	8,77448	3407	3400	High	7
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-70,687793	8,774549	3398	3400	High	-2
-70,688256	8,774603	3457	3400	High	57
-70,688905	8,7746	3454	3400	High	54
-70,689517	8,774542	3382	3400	High	-18
-70,690072	8,774392	3390	3400	High	-10
-70,690702	8,774131	3401	3400	High	1
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-70,691959	8,773258	3384	3400	High	-16
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-70,691733	8,772613	3372	3400	High	-28
-70,691583	8,772208	3372	3400	High	-28
-70,691321	8,77173	3393	3400	High	-7
-70,691041	8,771362	3378	3400	High	-22
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-70,690261	8,771071	3397	3400	High	-3
-70,689816	8,770907	3397	3400	High	-3
-70,689722	8,770796	3397	3400	High	-3

-70,689591	8,770447	3397	3400	High	-3
-70,689403	8,769839	3351	3400	High	-49
-70,689345	8,769304	3365	3400	High	-35
-70,689491	8,768787	3365	3400	High	-35
-70,689711	8,768362	3390	3400	High	-10
-70,689672	8,767938	3390	3400	High	-10
-70,68967	8,76744	3395	3400	High	-5
-70,689503	8,767293	3408	3400	High	8
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-70,688985	8,767517	3408	3400	High	8
-70,688764	8,767997	3381	3400	High	-19
-70,6886	8,768496	3419	3400	High	19
-70,688343	8,76905	3404	3400	High	4
-70,688141	8,769586	3375	3400	High	-25
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-70,686844	8,769832	3359	3400	High	-41
-70,686657	8,769482	3413	3400	High	13
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-70,685932	8,768914	3367	3400	High	-33
-70,685597	8,768638	3418	3400	High	18
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-70,684907	8,767941	3358	3400	High	-42
-70,684572	8,76761	3358	3400	High	-42
-70,684385	8,767297	3358	3400	High	-42
-70,684291	8,766947	3366	3400	High	-34
-70,684363	8,766449	3366	3400	High	-34
-70,684674	8,765599	3403	3400	High	3
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-70,68467	8,764732	3385	3400	High	-15
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-70,684146	8,763646	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,683977	8,763131	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,684012	8,762522	3387	3400	High	-13
-70,68425	8,762041	3347	3400	High	-53
-70,684675	8,761633	3393	3400	High	-7
-70,685397	8,761335	3393	3400	High	-7
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-70,686597	8,760223	3372	3400	High	-28
-70,686502	8,759781	3372	3400	High	-28
-70,686203	8,75921	3355	3400	High	-45
-70,686016	8,758769	3355	3400	High	-45

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-70,685862	8,757644	3375	3400	High	-25
-70,685821	8,756704	3379	3400	High	-21
-70,685842	8,757367	3375	3400	High	-25
-70,685819	8,756372	3379	3400	High	-21
-70,685725	8,755985	3404	3400	High	4
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-70,68412	8,753612	3392	3400	High	-8
-70,683989	8,753484	3392	3400	High	-8
-70,68371	8,753208	3346	3400	High	-54
-70,683617	8,75308	3346	3400	High	-54
-70,683504	8,752693	3359	3400	High	-41
-70,683632	8,752416	3359	3400	High	-41
-70,683854	8,752304	3393	3400	High	-7
-70,684373	8,752283	3393	3400	High	-7
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-70,685377	8,752814	3398	3400	High	-2
-70,685619	8,753052	3426	3400	High	26
-70,685898	8,753199	3426	3400	High	26
-70,686158	8,753253	3426	3400	High	26
-70,686565	8,753233	3417	3400	High	17
-70,686936	8,75312	3417	3400	High	17
-70,687213	8,75299	3414	3400	High	14
-70,687491	8,752952	3414	3400	High	14
-70,665211	8,808109	3417	3400	High	17
-70,665544	8,807923	3450	3400	High	50
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-70,666282	8,807127	3456	3400	High	56
-70,666521	8,806775	3392	3400	High	-8
-70,666927	8,806312	3392	3400	High	-8
-70,667315	8,806015	3391	3400	High	-9
-70,667944	8,805607	3418	3400	High	18
-70,668333	8,805476	3418	3400	High	18
-70,66874	8,805382	3349	3400	High	-51
-70,66913	8,805362	3373	3400	High	-27
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-70,670001	8,805339	3382	3400	High	-18
-70,670539	8,805374	3400	3400	High	0
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-70,671577	8,805296	3416	3400	High	16
-70,672059	8,805201	3416	3400	High	16
-70,67254	8,805088	3430	3400	High	30
-70,672892	8,804865	3430	3400	High	30
-70,673132	8,804717	3435	3400	High	35
-70,673539	8,804438	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,67389	8,804105	3393	3400	High	-7
-70,674388	8,803678	3346	3400	High	-54
-70,674832	8,803307	3398	3400	High	-2
-70,675442	8,802936	3428	3400	High	28
-70,67583	8,802639	3376	3400	High	-24
-70,676164	8,802693	3376	3400	High	-24
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-70,677404	8,802189	3423	3400	High	23
-70,67757	8,801875	3374	3400	High	-26
-70,677847	8,801652	3374	3400	High	-26
-70,678253	8,801392	3414	3400	High	14
-70,678642	8,801114	3374	3400	High	-26
-70,678956	8,800873	3407	3400	High	7
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-70,679246	8,799507	3363	3400	High	-37
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-70,679689	8,79897	3405	3400	High	5
-70,679985	8,798784	3405	3400	High	5
-70,680281	8,798672	3367	3400	High	-33
-70,680596	8,798615	3398	3400	High	-2
-70,680687	8,79832	3398	3400	High	-2
-70,680741	8,797914	3378	3400	High	-22
-70,680795	8,797637	3378	3400	High	-22
-70,680701	8,797231	3378	3400	High	-22
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-70,681274	8,796841	3391	3400	High	-9
-70,681478	8,796804	3391	3400	High	-9
-70,681718	8,796729	3391	3400	High	-9
-70,68194	8,796506	3391	3400	High	-9
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-70,683194	8,795062	3382	3400	High	-18

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-70,684098	8,793915	3405	3400	High	5
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-70,684851	8,792417	3394	3400	High	-6
-70,684572	8,792179	3347	3400	High	-53
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-70,684163	8,792033	3367	3400	High	-33
-70,683828	8,791795	3367	3400	High	-33
-70,683716	8,7915	3314	3400	High	-86
-70,6839	8,791149	3368	3400	High	-32
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-70,684546	8,790574	3368	3400	High	-32
-70,685026	8,790185	3384	3400	High	-16
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-70,685001	8,788746	3383	3400	High	-17
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-70,680771	8,779985	3344	3400	High	-56
-70,680996	8,780353	3344	3400	High	-56
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-70,681886	8,780349	3413	3400	High	13
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-70,684609	8,783878	3375	3400	High	-25
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-70,685278	8,784355	3375	3400	High	-25
-70,685687	8,784537	3398	3400	High	-2
-70,686874	8,784532	3400	3400	High	0
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-70,68625	8,786047	3425	3400	High	25
-70,685511	8,786678	3442	3400	High	42
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-70,686243	8,784461	3398	3400	High	-2
-70,684326	8,786904	3366	3400	High	-34
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-70,683475	8,787535	3363	3400	High	-37
-70,683626	8,787941	3316	3400	High	-84
-70,684072	8,788271	3350	3400	High	-50
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-70,657796	8,808603	3349	3400	High	-51
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-70,653143	8,804861	3431	3400	High	31
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-70,650673	8,808007	3325	3400	High	-75
-70,650595	8,807307	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,650444	8,806643	3378	3400	High	-22
-70,650257	8,806349	3326	3400	High	-74
-70,649996	8,805907	3344	3400	High	-56
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-70,648509	8,805139	3373	3400	High	-27
-70,647953	8,805289	3373	3400	High	-27
-70,647471	8,805328	3376	3400	High	-24
-70,647063	8,805367	3355	3400	High	-45
-70,646506	8,805148	3355	3400	High	-45
-70,645949	8,804892	3326	3400	High	-74
-70,645688	8,804598	3326	3400	High	-74
-70,645685	8,804045	3342	3400	High	-58
-70,645571	8,803234	3336	3400	High	-64
-70,645717	8,802827	3336	3400	High	-64
-70,645937	8,80231	3336	3400	High	-64
-70,645825	8,802052	3348	3400	High	-52
-70,645676	8,801831	3348	3400	High	-52
-70,645453	8,801722	3348	3400	High	-52
-70,645156	8,801649	3333	3400	High	-67
-70,644933	8,80154	3333	3400	High	-67
-70,644561	8,801467	3323	3400	High	-77
-70,644486	8,80121	3334	3400	High	-66
-70,644671	8,800987	3355	3400	High	-45
-70,645152	8,800911	3355	3400	High	-45
-70,645561	8,801057	3372	3400	High	-28
-70,645858	8,80113	3372	3400	High	-28
-70,646193	8,801497	3348	3400	High	-52
-70,64664	8,801901	3385	3400	High	-15
-70,647049	8,802157	3405	3400	High	5
-70,647421	8,802414	3426	3400	High	26
-70,647868	8,802707	3426	3400	High	26
-70,648388	8,802889	3379	3400	High	-21
-70,648906	8,802813	3382	3400	High	-18
-70,649313	8,80259	3382	3400	High	-18
-70,64998	8,802403	3429	3400	High	29
-70,65035	8,802254	3429	3400	High	29

-70,651275	8,801733	3379	3400	High	-21
-70,651793	8,801473	3379	3400	High	-21
-70,652014	8,801177	3316	3400	High	-84
-70,652346	8,800659	3348	3400	High	-52
-70,652529	8,800215	3324	3400	High	-76
-70,652973	8,799918	3391	3400	High	-9
-70,65338	8,799732	3391	3400	High	-9
-70,653786	8,799287	3397	3400	High	-3
-70,654303	8,798805	3397	3400	High	-3
-70,654748	8,798656	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,655156	8,798654	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,655453	8,798764	3420	3400	High	20
-70,655824	8,798836	3420	3400	High	20
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-70,656758	8,800307	3417	3400	High	17
-70,6565	8,800677	3395	3400	High	-5
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-70,657062	8,80204	3391	3400	High	-9
-70,657508	8,802259	3409	3400	High	9
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-70,658364	8,802846	3414	3400	High	14
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-70,65889	8,804466	3389	3400	High	-11
-70,659003	8,804945	3394	3400	High	-6
-70,659006	8,805536	3414	3400	High	14
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-70,659085	8,806642	3417	3400	High	17
-70,659346	8,806936	3417	3400	High	17
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-70,661126	8,806891	3388	3400	High	-12
-70,661606	8,80652	3424	3400	High	24
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-70,662458	8,806111	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,66294	8,806219	3357	3400	High	-43
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-70,663685	8,806806	3432	3400	High	32
-70,663798	8,807322	3411	3400	High	11
-70,66406	8,807874	3411	3400	High	11

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-70,664729	8,808203	3417	3400	High	17
-70,667477	8,817229	3365	3400	High	-35
-70,667329	8,81723	3365	3400	High	-35
-70,667107	8,817378	3365	3400	High	-35
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-70,667076	8,818891	3396	3400	High	-4
-70,667153	8,819481	3361	3400	High	-39
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-70,666487	8,819816	3359	3400	High	-41
-70,666118	8,820223	3404	3400	High	4
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-70,665604	8,821369	3346	3400	High	-54
-70,665087	8,821777	3370	3400	High	-30
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-70,664383	8,822076	3390	3400	High	-10
-70,664236	8,822408	3379	3400	High	-21
-70,664164	8,822814	3379	3400	High	-21
-70,664129	8,82322	3370	3400	High	-30
-70,663908	8,823701	3370	3400	High	-30
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-70,663578	8,824514	3385	3400	High	-15
-70,663284	8,825069	3373	3400	High	-27
-70,663175	8,825585	3374	3400	High	-26
-70,662918	8,826177	3374	3400	High	-26
-70,662884	8,826841	3397	3400	High	-3
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-70,661338	8,829393	3364	3400	High	-36
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-70,656155	8,83163	3342	3400	High	-58
-70,656302	8,831297	3374	3400	High	-26
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-70,660153	8,829878	3376	3400	High	-24
-70,660411	8,829397	3344	3400	High	-56
-70,660741	8,828621	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,661146	8,827955	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,661254	8,827291	3373	3400	High	-27
-70,661474	8,826589	3366	3400	High	-34

-70,661359	8,825778	3375	3400	High	-25
-70,660909	8,824673	3337	3400	High	-63
-70,658453	8,831103	3353	3400	High	-47
-70,659081	8,830731	3377	3400	High	-23
-70,659489	8,830545	3377	3400	High	-23
-70,659932	8,830248	3376	3400	High	-24
-70,66087	8,824231	3356	3400	High	-44
-70,660942	8,823714	3332	3400	High	-68
-70,661171	8,825262	3337	3400	High	-63
-70,661126	8,823455	3332	3400	High	-68
-70,661606	8,823084	3391	3400	High	-9
-70,66205	8,822713	3338	3400	High	-62
-70,66253	8,822268	3388	3400	High	-12
-70,662974	8,821971	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,663529	8,82171	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,663638	8,821378	3383	3400	High	-17
-70,663526	8,82101	3357	3400	High	-43
-70,663264	8,820642	3357	3400	High	-43
-70,662892	8,820348	3343	3400	High	-57
-70,662557	8,820018	3343	3400	High	-57
-70,662259	8,819798	3343	3400	High	-57
-70,662036	8,819577	3387	3400	High	-13
-70,661628	8,819727	3325	3400	High	-75
-70,661184	8,819987	3321	3400	High	-79
-70,660554	8,819879	3321	3400	High	-79
-70,660069	8,819402	3335	3400	High	-65
-70,660067	8,818959	3335	3400	High	-65
-70,660139	8,818405	3341	3400	High	-59
-70,660321	8,817741	3350	3400	High	-50
-70,660318	8,816929	3340	3400	High	-60
-70,660576	8,816522	3382	3400	High	-18
-70,660983	8,816299	3382	3400	High	-18
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-70,66142	8,814637	3389	3400	High	-11
-70,661455	8,814083	3365	3400	High	-35
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-70,495499	8,565199	208	200	Low	8
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-70,494645	8,56487	207	200	Low	7
-70,494201	8,565019	205	200	Low	5
-70,493868	8,565316	205	200	Low	5
-70,493275	8,565244	206	200	Low	6
-70,492719	8,56532	209	200	Low	9
-70,491979	8,565544	209	200	Low	9
-70,491535	8,565767	209	200	Low	9

-70,491053	8,565843	218	200	Low	18
-70,490126	8,565736	216	200	Low	16
-70,489645	8,565775	216	200	Low	16
-70,48909	8,566035	214	200	Low	14
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-70,48821	8,568658	209	200	Low	9
-70,488251	8,569617	211	200	Low	11
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-70,487736	8,570541	210	200	Low	10
-70,48733	8,571096	210	200	Low	10
-70,487036	8,571651	209	200	Low	9
-70,486705	8,572427	208	200	Low	8
-70,48656	8,573165	210	200	Low	10
-70,486303	8,573867	211	200	Low	11
-70,486082	8,574237	210	200	Low	10
-70,485417	8,574867	209	200	Low	9
-70,484789	8,575422	211	200	Low	11
-70,484495	8,575977	215	200	Low	15
-70,484052	8,576495	213	200	Low	13
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-70,483278	8,577679	218	200	Low	18
-70,482837	8,578492	219	200	Low	19
-70,482431	8,57901	218	200	Low	18
-70,482359	8,579601	219	200	Low	19
-70,482361	8,58008	219	200	Low	19
-70,482215	8,580561	218	200	Low	18
-70,481994	8,580967	220	200	Low	20
-70,4817	8,581596	221	200	Low	21
-70,481442	8,58215	222	200	Low	22
-70,481482	8,582703	222	200	Low	22
-70,48141	8,583404	221	200	Low	21
-70,481523	8,583884	216	200	Low	16
-70,481562	8,584363	216	200	Low	16
-70,481787	8,584916	216	200	Low	16
-70,481677	8,585211	216	200	Low	16
-70,481382	8,585544	219	200	Low	19
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-70,4812	8,586467	219	200	Low	19
-70,481164	8,586837	219	200	Low	19
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-70,481537	8,587352	214	200	Low	14
-70,481908	8,587461	214	200	Low	14
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-70,482793	8,586424	222	200	Low	22
-70,482828	8,585834	215	200	Low	15
-70,48305	8,585649	217	200	Low	17
-70,483384	8,585758	217	200	Low	17
-70,483978	8,58594	214	200	Low	14
-70,484496	8,585828	214	200	Low	14
-70,484606	8,585348	226	200	Low	26
-70,484418	8,584869	219	200	Low	19
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-70,483598	8,583581	219	200	Low	19
-70,483041	8,583251	219	200	Low	19
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-70,482888	8,582255	217	200	Low	17
-70,483295	8,581811	217	200	Low	17
-70,484033	8,581144	216	200	Low	16
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-70,484395	8,578744	211	200	Low	11
-70,4848	8,578226	212	200	Low	12
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-70,485758	8,576747	213	200	Low	13
-70,486128	8,576377	213	200	Low	13
-70,486646	8,576153	215	200	Low	15
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-70,48805	8,575004	215	200	Low	15
-70,488344	8,57456	212	200	Low	12
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-70,489693	8,568763	205	200	Low	5
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-70,491281	8,567133	209	200	Low	9
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-70,493394	8,567346	205	200	Low	5
-70,493876	8,567197	206	200	Low	6

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-70,49658	8,566855	213	200	Low	13
-70,496949	8,566374	213	200	Low	13
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-70,498022	8,56589	235	200	Low	35
-70,498278	8,565077	232	200	Low	32
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-70,498532	8,563674	226	200	Low	26
-70,498567	8,563084	226	200	Low	26
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-70,498854	8,560685	237	200	Low	37
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-70,49773	8,557516	229	200	Low	29
-70,497282	8,556891	226	200	Low	26
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-70,497486	8,551983	223	200	Low	23
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-70,490569	8,546217	202	200	Low	2
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-70,491192	8,54437	199	200	Low	-1
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-70,493302	8,543698	198	200	Low	-2
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-70,498441	8,549803	211	200	Low	11
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-70,501362	8,548057	211	200	Low	11
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-70,500547	8,548097	205	200	Low	5
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-70,495812	8,541069	198	200	Low	-2
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-70,496026	8,538781	194	200	Low	-6
-70,496135	8,538227	197	200	Low	-3
-70,496578	8,537856	194	200	Low	-6
-70,496687	8,537376	194	200	Low	-6
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-70,497018	8,536674	193	200	Low	-7
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-70,49853	8,534787	196	200	Low	-4
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-70,497852	8,532022	224	200	Low	24
-70,497332	8,531655	224	200	Low	24
-70,496849	8,531436	210	200	Low	10
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-70,495847	8,530997	221	200	Low	21
-70,495291	8,530962	217	200	Low	17
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-70,493177	8,530491	204	200	Low	4
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-70,489226	8,534417	197	200	Low	-3
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-70,480695	8,523123	214	200	Low	14
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-70,479363	8,523608	208	200	Low	8
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-70,477512	8,524205	199	200	Low	-1
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-70,469718	8,531023	204	200	Low	4
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-70,481563	8,53677	201	200	Low	1
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-70,494678	8,535318	196	200	Low	-4
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-70,508758	8,543786	363	400	Low	-37
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-70,518357	8,571935	217	200	Low	17
-70,518616	8,571638	217	200	Low	17

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-70,525296	8,573697	223	200	Low	23
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-70,520805	8,586147	246	200	Low	46
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-70,521782	8,580222	247	200	Low	47
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-70,520966	8,58017	236	200	Low	36
-70,520577	8,580208	236	200	Low	36
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-70,514346	8,56518	217	200	Low	17
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-70,515841	8,568274	222	200	Low	22
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-70,516299	8,571555	216	200	Low	16
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-70,516489	8,572698	227	200	Low	27
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-70,538255	8,652752	587	600	Low	-13
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-70,536801	8,650876	592	600	Low	-8
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-70,537282	8,650505	585	600	Low	-15
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-70,536314	8,649698	582	600	Low	-18
-70,536388	8,649439	587	600	Low	-13
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-70,539286	8,642049	574	600	Low	-26
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-70,537632	8,64556	603	600	Low	3
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-70,533804	8,652401	586	600	Low	-14
-70,533509	8,652623	577	600	Low	-23
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-70,53314	8,653178	580	600	Low	-20
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-70,53451	8,65273	586	600	Low	-14
-70,534769	8,652471	583	600	Low	-17
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-70,53655	8,652906	606	600	Low	6
-70,536588	8,653091	593	600	Low	-7
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-70,537893	8,654967	581	600	Low	-19
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-70,538193	8,655925	598	600	Low	-2
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-70,542385	8,656461	602	600	Low	2
-70,542866	8,656349	602	600	Low	2
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-70,544683	8,656378	567	600	Low	-33
-70,545461	8,656154	598	600	Low	-2
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-70,551452	8,652551	587	600	Low	-13
-70,551635	8,652108	587	600	Low	-13
-70,551781	8,65148	590	600	Low	-10
-70,551816	8,650926	596	600	Low	-4
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-70,553828	8,644278	564	600	Low	-36
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-70,555007	8,642502	575	600	Low	-25
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-70,618338	8,619717	813	800	Medium	13
-70,618225	8,619201	808	800	Medium	8
-70,618331	8,618057	803	800	Medium	3
-70,618403	8,617504	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,618587	8,617097	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,618259	8,618574	803	800	Medium	3
-70,618992	8,616468	764	800	Medium	-36
-70,61925	8,616209	750	800	Medium	-50
-70,619877	8,615432	778	800	Medium	-22
-70,620356	8,614655	779	800	Medium	-21
-70,620539	8,614138	816	800	Medium	16
-70,62061	8,61351	839	800	Medium	39
-70,620571	8,613068	839	800	Medium	39

-70,620458	8,612515	845	800	Medium	45
-70,620122	8,61211	815	800	Medium	15
-70,619861	8,611595	796	800	Medium	-4
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-70,620115	8,610487	794	800	Medium	-6
-70,620152	8,610339	778	800	Medium	-22
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-70,620667	8,609452	738	800	Medium	-62
-70,621037	8,609303	738	800	Medium	-62
-70,621407	8,609154	762	800	Medium	-38
-70,621777	8,608968	762	800	Medium	-38
-70,622071	8,608376	759	800	Medium	-41
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-70,622548	8,607267	776	800	Medium	-24
-70,622843	8,606787	763	800	Medium	-37
-70,623323	8,606416	771	800	Medium	-29
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-70,62417	8,605047	798	800	Medium	-2
-70,624204	8,604457	818	800	Medium	18
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-70,623977	8,603277	829	800	Medium	29
-70,623901	8,602872	809	800	Medium	9
-70,623973	8,602355	809	800	Medium	9
-70,624045	8,601986	788	800	Medium	-12
-70,624228	8,601358	788	800	Medium	-12
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-70,626844	8,632372	782	800	Medium	-18
-70,626953	8,631818	789	800	Medium	-11
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-70,627207	8,6306	812	800	Medium	12
-70,627613	8,630192	825	800	Medium	25
-70,628056	8,629821	843	800	Medium	43
-70,628018	8,62949	856	800	Medium	56
-70,627831	8,629048	846	800	Medium	46
-70,627422	8,628865	846	800	Medium	46
-70,627013	8,628645	848	800	Medium	48
-70,62679	8,628425	848	800	Medium	48
-70,626345	8,628427	848	800	Medium	48
-70,626273	8,628759	831	800	Medium	31
-70,626052	8,629166	842	800	Medium	42
-70,625868	8,629609	835	800	Medium	35
-70,625352	8,630128	853	800	Medium	53
-70,624723	8,630426	832	800	Medium	32

-70,62428	8,630834	845	800	Medium	45
-70,623577	8,631132	851	800	Medium	51
-70,623243	8,631096	851	800	Medium	51
-70,622724	8,631025	843	800	Medium	43
-70,62239	8,631063	843	800	Medium	43
-70,621871	8,630991	809	800	Medium	9
-70,621463	8,630956	809	800	Medium	9
-70,621165	8,630736	770	800	Medium	-30
-70,620756	8,630332	794	800	Medium	-6
-70,621125	8,629851	794	800	Medium	-6
-70,62142	8,629481	866	800	Medium	66
-70,621825	8,628999	866	800	Medium	66
-70,62175	8,628668	896	800	Medium	96
-70,621452	8,628484	896	800	Medium	96
-70,621118	8,628375	885	800	Medium	85
-70,620599	8,628377	885	800	Medium	85
-70,620191	8,628268	846	800	Medium	46
-70,619931	8,628085	846	800	Medium	46
-70,619669	8,627607	836	800	Medium	36
-70,619296	8,627092	807	800	Medium	7
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-70,618145	8,626543	780	800	Medium	-20
-70,617663	8,626508	800	800	Medium	0
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-70,61762	8,625033	717	800	Medium	-83
-70,61814	8,625473	743	800	Medium	-57
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-70,621363	8,624833	743	800	Medium	-57
-70,621769	8,624425	738	800	Medium	-62
-70,62236	8,623943	747	800	Medium	-53
-70,62273	8,623757	747	800	Medium	-53
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-70,623583	8,623901	771	800	Medium	-29
-70,623881	8,624195	794	800	Medium	-6
-70,624214	8,624083	794	800	Medium	-6
-70,624694	8,623675	819	800	Medium	19

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-70,625098	8,622898	841	800	Medium	41
-70,625393	8,622528	841	800	Medium	41
-70,625466	8,622233	855	800	Medium	55
-70,625317	8,621975	877	800	Medium	77
-70,624982	8,621792	877	800	Medium	77
-70,624723	8,62172	877	800	Medium	77
-70,624463	8,621573	845	800	Medium	45
-70,62435	8,621242	870	800	Medium	70
-70,624128	8,621242	870	800	Medium	70
-70,623831	8,621207	870	800	Medium	70
-70,623533	8,62095	850	800	Medium	50
-70,62342	8,620471	850	800	Medium	50
-70,623233	8,620176	886	800	Medium	86
-70,622973	8,620067	886	800	Medium	86
-70,622862	8,620067	890	800	Medium	90
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-70,622085	8,620292	890	800	Medium	90
-70,621567	8,620479	855	800	Medium	55
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-70,621084	8,62037	890	800	Medium	90
-70,620677	8,620409	890	800	Medium	90
-70,62027	8,620595	850	800	Medium	50
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-70,634597	8,650868	816	800	Medium	16
-70,633758	8,649718	812	800	Medium	12
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-70,632183	8,647548	810	800	Medium	10

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-70,630953	8,646179	810	800	Medium	10
-70,630655	8,645793	810	800	Medium	10
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-70,629982	8,644459	792	800	Medium	-8
-70,629656	8,644138	792	800	Medium	-8
-70,629561	8,643585	782	800	Medium	-18
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-70,629417	8,642312	802	800	Medium	2
-70,62923	8,64199	829	800	Medium	29
-70,628802	8,641522	829	800	Medium	29
-70,628495	8,64121	787	800	Medium	-13
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-70,627833	8,640475	763	800	Medium	-37
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-70,624761	8,637168	774	800	Medium	-26
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-70,523744	8,733845	784	800	Medium	-16
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-70,529309	8,716409	756	800	Medium	-44
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-70,535381	8,723247	764	800	Medium	-36
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-70,523762	8,738235	838	800	Medium	38
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-70,508147	8,771907	814	800	Medium	14
-70,508123	8,770689	834	800	Medium	34
-70,507823	8,769695	783	800	Medium	-17
-70,5073	8,768756	798	800	Medium	-2
-70,507113	8,768332	782	800	Medium	-18
-70,507129	8,76789	742	800	Medium	-58
-70,507871	8,767887	742	800	Medium	-58
-70,508224	8,768162	777	800	Medium	-23
-70,508782	8,768418	789	800	Medium	-11
-70,509337	8,768121	789	800	Medium	-11
-70,509947	8,767675	796	800	Medium	-4
-70,510259	8,766992	776	800	Medium	-24
-70,510423	8,766106	830	800	Medium	30
-70,510938	8,765218	830	800	Medium	30
-70,510714	8,76485	830	800	Medium	30
-70,510192	8,764114	789	800	Medium	-11

-70,509893	8,763415	783	800	Medium	-17
-70,510187	8,762749	756	800	Medium	-44
-70,511149	8,762413	754	800	Medium	-46
-70,512443	8,761449	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,513813	8,760927	769	800	Medium	-31
-70,515036	8,760627	779	800	Medium	-21
-70,515851	8,760513	786	800	Medium	-14
-70,516555	8,760326	748	800	Medium	-52
-70,517483	8,760359	753	800	Medium	-47
-70,517928	8,760578	759	800	Medium	-41
-70,51782	8,761206	783	800	Medium	-17
-70,517332	8,76202	775	800	Medium	-25
-70,517316	8,76285	770	800	Medium	-30
-70,517303	8,764012	760	800	Medium	-40
-70,517175	8,764474	760	800	Medium	-40
-70,51677	8,765324	775	800	Medium	-25
-70,516383	8,765916	757	800	Medium	-43
-70,515866	8,766508	781	800	Medium	-19
-70,515312	8,766898	796	800	Medium	-4
-70,514943	8,767342	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,514981	8,767618	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,515629	8,767487	780	800	Medium	-20
-70,516019	8,767448	780	800	Medium	-20
-70,516316	8,767595	758	800	Medium	-42
-70,51654	8,768055	775	800	Medium	-25
-70,516932	8,768736	775	800	Medium	-25
-70,517751	8,76947	770	800	Medium	-30
-70,518161	8,769856	773	800	Medium	-27
-70,51822	8,770649	773	800	Medium	-27
-70,518148	8,771184	773	800	Medium	-27
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-70,518451	8,772769	783	800	Medium	-17
-70,519322	8,772674	783	800	Medium	-17
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-70,520893	8,771487	770	800	Medium	-30
-70,521413	8,771724	753	800	Medium	-47
-70,521823	8,772258	763	800	Medium	-37
-70,521789	8,772811	763	800	Medium	-37
-70,521346	8,773496	756	800	Medium	-44
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-70,520889	8,774973	771	800	Medium	-29
-70,520705	8,775343	771	800	Medium	-29
-70,520299	8,775806	773	800	Medium	-27

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-70,520046	8,777375	787	800	Medium	-13
-70,520825	8,777501	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,521806	8,777183	794	800	Medium	-6
-70,522454	8,77683	780	800	Medium	-20
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-70,523229	8,775923	766	800	Medium	-34
-70,523768	8,776161	725	800	Medium	-75
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-70,524357	8,779718	769	800	Medium	-31
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-70,524604	8,781064	746	800	Medium	-54
-70,524679	8,78134	758	800	Medium	-42
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-70,523719	8,782303	792	800	Medium	-8
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-70,524805	8,785047	771	800	Medium	-29
-70,524492	8,785455	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,524513	8,785989	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,524755	8,786339	781	800	Medium	-19
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-70,524482	8,78765	794	800	Medium	-6
-70,524558	8,788055	804	800	Medium	4
-70,524892	8,788201	813	800	Medium	13
-70,5253	8,787978	813	800	Medium	13
-70,52565	8,78746	815	800	Medium	15
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-70,526294	8,786406	804	800	Medium	4
-70,526998	8,786238	778	800	Medium	-22
-70,527981	8,786307	795	800	Medium	-5
-70,528594	8,786434	795	800	Medium	-5
-70,529671	8,786854	780	800	Medium	-20
-70,530507	8,787256	795	800	Medium	-5
-70,531214	8,787678	795	800	Medium	-5
-70,532067	8,787711	791	800	Medium	-9
-70,532662	8,788262	823	800	Medium	23
-70,533425	8,788757	844	800	Medium	44
-70,534556	8,788808	836	800	Medium	36

-70,536207	8,78893	830	800	Medium	30
-70,537099	8,789517	820	800	Medium	20
-70,537862	8,790178	837	800	Medium	37
-70,538198	8,790564	846	800	Medium	46
-70,53883	8,790912	846	800	Medium	46
-70,539292	8,79067	846	800	Medium	46
-70,539476	8,79019	855	800	Medium	55
-70,539177	8,789748	855	800	Medium	55
-70,53836	8,789364	848	800	Medium	48
-70,537727	8,788776	820	800	Medium	20
-70,537261	8,788206	835	800	Medium	35
-70,536592	8,787877	855	800	Medium	55
-70,535626	8,787438	830	800	Medium	30
-70,534642	8,78711	817	800	Medium	17
-70,497168	8,794732	786	800	Medium	-14
-70,497875	8,795098	786	800	Medium	-14
-70,498506	8,795428	812	800	Medium	12
-70,499433	8,795313	769	800	Medium	-31
-70,499992	8,796049	823	800	Medium	23
-70,500475	8,796047	855	800	Medium	55
-70,501028	8,795454	855	800	Medium	55
-70,501321	8,794531	819	800	Medium	19
-70,501504	8,793903	819	800	Medium	19
-70,502579	8,793641	784	800	Medium	-16
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-70,50332	8,793564	795	800	Medium	-5
-70,504099	8,793487	799	800	Medium	-1
-70,50562	8,793702	756	800	Medium	-44
-70,506104	8,794143	781	800	Medium	-19
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-70,514439	8,672216	370	400	Low	-30
-70,514591	8,673174	400	400	Low	0
-70,514743	8,673985	392	400	Low	-8
-70,514894	8,67487	396	400	Low	-4
-70,515083	8,675792	395	400	Low	-5
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-70,51644	8,681173	392	400	Low	-8
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-70,515523	8,683611	407	400	Low	7
-70,515451	8,684276	406	400	Low	6
-70,515082	8,684757	426	400	Low	26
-70,514789	8,685496	424	400	Low	24
-70,514418	8,685424	458	400	Low	58
-70,514194	8,685166	465	400	Low	65
-70,514154	8,684502	476	400	Low	76
-70,514301	8,684022	476	400	Low	76
-70,514632	8,68332	432	400	Low	32
-70,514815	8,682692	442	400	Low	42
-70,51507	8,681769	454	400	Low	54
-70,515252	8,680772	451	400	Low	51
-70,515323	8,67996	440	400	Low	40
-70,515022	8,679039	424	400	Low	24
-70,514351	8,677971	421	400	Low	21
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-70,513193	8,675947	422	400	Low	22
-70,513002	8,674398	397	400	Low	-3
-70,512776	8,673587	405	400	Low	5
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-70,512402	8,672703	386	400	Low	-14
-70,51188	8,672152	406	400	Low	6
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-70,510541	8,670977	403	400	Low	3
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-70,510391	8,670609	419	400	Low	19
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-70,51519	8,665425	433	400	Low	33
-70,515446	8,664464	404	400	Low	4
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-70,517143	8,662428	364	400	Low	-36
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-70,517096	8,659994	391	400	Low	-9
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-70,513286	8,662112	418	400	Low	18
-70,512619	8,662114	405	400	Low	5
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-70,511285	8,662415	401	400	Low	1
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-70,511659	8,663151	403	400	Low	3
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-70,531091	8,676881	399	400	Low	-1
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-70,530881	8,671016	380	400	Low	-20
-70,530063	8,670318	376	400	Low	-24
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-70,52127	8,668693	366	400	Low	-34
-70,520528	8,668622	380	400	Low	-20
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-70,518223	8,667008	343	400	Low	-57
-70,517706	8,6676	350	400	Low	-50
-70,517302	8,668414	361	400	Low	-39
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-70,522746	8,657822	413	400	Low	13
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-70,522972	8,658781	422	400	Low	22
-70,523344	8,659037	422	400	Low	22
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-70,527201	8,650168	422	400	Low	22
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-70,527242	8,651016	433	400	Low	33
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-70,526637	8,652679	406	400	Low	6
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-70,528801	8,647136	420	400	Low	20
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-70,528209	8,64736	412	400	Low	12
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-70,526132	8,647184	407	400	Low	7
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-70,531686	8,636241	377	400	Low	-23
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-70,499182	8,671049	359	400	Low	-41
-70,499887	8,67112	373	400	Low	-27
-70,50048	8,671044	386	400	Low	-14
-70,500998	8,670747	386	400	Low	-14
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-70,501551	8,669896	396	400	Low	-4
-70,501586	8,669417	423	400	Low	23
-70,501177	8,66916	416	400	Low	16
-70,500805	8,668903	416	400	Low	16
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-70,499986	8,667984	411	400	Low	11
-70,499764	8,668169	411	400	Low	11
-70,499393	8,668208	400	400	Low	0
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-70,499242	8,667507	415	400	Low	15
-70,499056	8,667324	415	400	Low	15
-70,49861	8,66703	427	400	Low	27
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-70,497733	8,665595	405	400	Low	5
-70,498009	8,664911	433	400	Low	33
-70,497729	8,664525	432	400	Low	32
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-70,497825	8,665299	414	400	Low	14
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-70,495451	8,66494	402	400	Low	2
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-70,495632	8,664035	392	400	Low	-8
-70,496697	8,661412	406	400	Low	6
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-70,498054	8,67644	400	400	Low	0
-70,49809	8,676108	408	400	Low	8
-70,498125	8,675591	408	400	Low	8
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-70,49797	8,673858	398	400	Low	-2
-70,498191	8,673488	383	400	Low	-17
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-70,498815	8,671936	384	400	Low	-16
-70,501848	8,707379	411	400	Low	11
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-70,500627	8,7079	428	400	Low	28
-70,500407	8,708639	422	400	Low	22
-70,500037	8,708935	397	400	Low	-3
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-70,498226	8,710197	401	400	Low	1
-70,497712	8,711711	416	400	Low	16
-70,497492	8,712192	405	400	Low	5
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-70,497497	8,71352	397	400	Low	-3
-70,497277	8,714074	391	400	Low	-9
-70,496872	8,714924	406	400	Low	6
-70,496655	8,71618	385	400	Low	-15
-70,496361	8,716845	370	400	Low	-30
-70,496476	8,71773	363	400	Low	-37
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-70,497373	8,71946	369	400	Low	-31
-70,496893	8,720052	387	400	Low	-13
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-70,497167	8,714517	391	400	Low	-9
-70,496764	8,715515	385	400	Low	-15
-70,497223	8,719055	369	400	Low	-31

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-70,504272	8,692317	375	400	Low	-25
-70,504163	8,69276	375	400	Low	-25
-70,504202	8,69335	383	400	Low	-17
-70,504539	8,69416	383	400	Low	-17
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-70,507024	8,694335	433	400	Low	33
-70,508063	8,694626	412	400	Low	12
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-70,509055	8,701447	389	400	Low	-11
-70,509574	8,701593	389	400	Low	-11
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-70,510475	8,704172	430	400	Low	30
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-70,514349	8,708805	372	400	Low	-28
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-70,514693	8,711312	397	400	Low	-3
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-70,513134	8,710875	375	400	Low	-25
-70,512802	8,711283	378	400	Low	-22
-70,512433	8,711801	378	400	Low	-22
-70,511806	8,71243	367	400	Low	-33
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-70,512221	8,714384	427	400	Low	27
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-70,512781	8,715267	414	400	Low	14
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-70,51275	8,716854	377	400	Low	-23
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-70,512106	8,722575	428	400	Low	28
-70,511848	8,723018	410	400	Low	10
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-70,511185	8,714831	391	400	Low	-9
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-70,509809	8,713951	370	400	Low	-30
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-70,508996	8,714655	390	400	Low	-10
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-70,509187	8,706722	374	400	Low	-26
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-70,503326	8,67808	411	400	Low	11
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-70,503154	8,681585	382	400	Low	-18
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-70,505657	8,686187	394	400	Low	-6
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-70,501738	8,717008	405	400	Low	5
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-70,602718	8,619682	597	600	Low	-3
-70,602495	8,619369	614	600	Low	14
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-70,600992	8,619043	597	600	Low	-3
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-70,587103	8,644113	570	600	Low	-30
-70,587068	8,644612	594	600	Low	-6
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-70,58758	8,647247	574	600	Low	-26
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-70,588455	8,648221	584	600	Low	-16
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-70,589992	8,647809	589	600	Low	-11
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-70,589988	8,646776	567	600	Low	-33
-70,590209	8,64648	567	600	Low	-33
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-70,592776	8,644348	545	600	Low	-55
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-70,593648	8,644474	544	600	Low	-56
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-70,59454	8,644931	558	600	Low	-42
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-70,597259	8,643721	637	600	Low	37
-70,597072	8,643389	626	600	Low	26

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-70,596627	8,643188	626	600	Low	26
-70,596406	8,643503	626	600	Low	26
-70,596073	8,64367	632	600	Low	32
-70,595683	8,64358	632	600	Low	32
-70,595274	8,64336	614	600	Low	14
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-70,591498	8,640056	638	600	Low	38
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-70,583576	8,655989	599	600	Low	-1

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-70,583387	8,655252	598	600	Low	-2
-70,583422	8,654606	598	600	Low	-2
-70,58355	8,654273	598	600	Low	-2
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-70,584008	8,653073	611	600	Low	11
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-70,578744	8,652984	616	600	Low	16
-70,578131	8,652802	660	600	Low	60
-70,577519	8,65262	641	600	Low	41
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-70,576199	8,651648	593	600	Low	-7
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-70,577838	8,649224	577	600	Low	-23
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-70,582198	8,645591	609	600	Low	9
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-70,583416	8,644332	582	600	Low	-18
-70,583748	8,644054	582	600	Low	-18
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-70,594434	8,659541	582	600	Low	-18

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-70,575282	8,658587	558	600	Low	-42
-70,575503	8,658309	547	600	Low	-53
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-70,5763	8,658269	533	600	Low	-67
-70,576561	8,658655	533	600	Low	-67
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-70,579437	8,663569	637	600	Low	37
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-70,582012	8,663374	575	600	Low	-25
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-70,570252	8,692659	621	600	Low	21
-70,569586	8,692957	592	600	Low	-8
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-70,568145	8,694291	606	600	Low	6
-70,567701	8,694293	606	600	Low	6
-70,56707	8,694148	612	600	Low	12
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-70,565961	8,695075	615	600	Low	15
-70,565331	8,69504	612	600	Low	12
-70,564736	8,694563	624	600	Low	24
-70,564436	8,69379	583	600	Low	-17
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-70,563693	8,693387	598	600	Low	-2
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-70,56349	8,693738	598	600	Low	-2
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-70,562323	8,693946	583	600	Low	-17
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-70,561386	8,691515	583	600	Low	-17

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-70,56126	8,687974	574	600	Low	-26
-70,56111	8,687495	567	600	Low	-33
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-70,560659	8,686132	627	600	Low	27
-70,559954	8,685913	627	600	Low	27
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-70,549637	8,683483	633	600	Low	33
-70,548895	8,683486	625	600	Low	25
-70,548339	8,683378	612	600	Low	12
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-70,551999	8,680965	562	600	Low	-38
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-70,554581	8,677561	631	600	Low	31
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-70,572692	8,682024	584	600	Low	-16
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-70,573293	8,683903	585	600	Low	-15
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-70,574134	8,68117	549	600	Low	-51
-70,574798	8,680245	561	600	Low	-39
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-70,575086	8,678251	617	600	Low	17
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-70,584004	8,674082	633	600	Low	33
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-70,575471	8,672826	639	600	Low	39
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-70,571016	8,671222	653	600	Low	53
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-70,566857	8,669689	559	600	Low	-41
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-70,557013	8,714443	590	600	Low	-10
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-70,555692	8,717805	569	600	Low	-31
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-70,498181	8,698963	421	400	Low	21
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-70,50526	8,698382	419	400	Low	19
-70,505039	8,698751	414	400	Low	14
-70,504559	8,699122	428	400	Low	28
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-70,503493	8,701451	395	400	Low	-5
-70,503236	8,702153	388	400	Low	-12
-70,502869	8,70315	406	400	Low	6
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-70,480325	8,705351	420	400	Low	20
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-70,480732	8,705073	440	400	Low	40
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-70,479058	8,703732	431	400	Low	31
-70,478593	8,703476	429	400	Low	29
-70,477999	8,703183	429	400	Low	29
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-70,477347	8,702503	411	400	Low	11
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-70,478849	8,702368	413	400	Low	13
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-70,48026	8,702916	432	400	Low	32
-70,480798	8,703062	440	400	Low	40
-70,481	8,702692	460	400	Low	60
-70,480664	8,702103	460	400	Low	60
-70,479939	8,70146	463	400	Low	63
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-70,47845	8,699935	461	400	Low	61
-70,47804	8,699494	485	400	Low	85
-70,477445	8,698998	457	400	Low	57
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-70,476085	8,69738	419	400	Low	19
-70,475582	8,696607	431	400	Low	31
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-70,475204	8,694764	416	400	Low	16
-70,475034	8,694008	418	400	Low	18
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-70,475176	8,687607	393	400	Low	-7
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-70,475956	8,687991	399	400	Low	-1
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-70,479261	8,684695	387	400	Low	-13
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-70,480745	8,684855	378	400	Low	-22
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-70,483232	8,685638	385	400	Low	-15
-70,483567	8,685951	385	400	Low	-15
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-70,487864	8,689531	417	400	Low	17
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-70,487874	8,687391	427	400	Low	27
-70,487632	8,687097	427	400	Low	27
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-70,486406	8,68653	443	400	Low	43
-70,486312	8,686198	456	400	Low	56
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-70,48545	8,684025	423	400	Low	23
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-70,486146	8,681864	439	400	Low	39
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-70,48771	8,67874	363	400	Low	-37
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-70,48873	8,678866	404	400	Low	4
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-70,491236	8,679612	396	400	Low	-4
-70,491607	8,679869	377	400	Low	-23
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-70,492443	8,680327	350	400	Low	-50
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-70,491954	8,683133	428	400	Low	28
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-70,493326	8,687923	417	400	Low	17
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-70,49579	8,687508	386	400	Low	-14
-70,496162	8,687801	386	400	Low	-14

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-70,49571	8,690773	383	400	Low	-17
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-70,468999	8,696393	422	400	Low	22
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-70,469289	8,694584	394	400	Low	-6
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-70,472936	8,697909	398	400	Low	-2
-70,472826	8,698333	442	400	Low	42
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-70,47501	8,702125	412	400	Low	12
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-70,435117	8,722809	406	400	Low	6
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-70,452423	8,71518	406	400	Low	6
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-70,453228	8,726651	408	400	Low	8
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-70,454743	8,734872	422	400	Low	22
-70,455022	8,735148	422	400	Low	22
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-70,460035	8,708289	428	400	Low	28
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-70,420582	8,688681	436	400	Low	36
-70,421065	8,688956	418	400	Low	18
-70,4214	8,689305	416	400	Low	16
-70,421697	8,689396	416	400	Low	16
-70,422328	8,689431	419	400	Low	19
-70,422754	8,689282	419	400	Low	19
-70,423123	8,688911	411	400	Low	11
-70,423531	8,688891	411	400	Low	11
-70,423753	8,688725	405	400	Low	5
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-70,424634	8,686489	390	400	Low	-10
-70,424503	8,686102	410	400	Low	10
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-70,424611	8,685198	402	400	Low	2
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-70,426057	8,685322	388	400	Low	-12
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-70,42743	8,685593	398	400	Low	-2
-70,427839	8,685942	398	400	Low	-2
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-70,432125	8,672183	398	400	Low	-2
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-70,429658	8,67162	394	400	Low	-6
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-70,423754	8,684039	404	400	Low	4
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-70,410897	8,701372	383	400	Low	-17
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-70,516117	8,740239	565	600	Low	-35
-70,516692	8,740311	553	600	Low	-47
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-70,517602	8,740768	588	600	Low	-12
-70,518066	8,740767	614	600	Low	14
-70,51851	8,740543	614	600	Low	14
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-70,519487	8,73923	609	600	Low	9
-70,519857	8,738841	630	600	Low	30
-70,519559	8,738584	654	600	Low	54
-70,518854	8,738495	654	600	Low	54
-70,518223	8,738442	629	600	Low	29
-70,51746	8,737725	623	600	Low	23
-70,517346	8,736988	631	600	Low	31
-70,517418	8,736397	631	600	Low	31
-70,51799	8,735768	643	600	Low	43
-70,518021	8,734274	606	600	Low	6
-70,519	8,733347	619	600	Low	19
-70,519144	8,732351	608	600	Low	8
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-70,519882	8,731296	631	600	Low	31
-70,520139	8,730779	589	600	Low	-11
-70,520544	8,730076	547	600	Low	-53
-70,521025	8,729816	547	600	Low	-53
-70,52136	8,729981	542	600	Low	-58
-70,521733	8,730662	596	600	Low	-4

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-70,523179	8,730508	595	600	Low	-5
-70,523975	8,730339	545	600	Low	-55
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-70,528685	8,730486	598	600	Low	-2
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-70,529425	8,730096	644	600	Low	44
-70,529015	8,729655	644	600	Low	44
-70,528142	8,729142	669	600	Low	69
-70,527547	8,728757	648	600	Low	48
-70,526933	8,728317	651	600	Low	51
-70,526226	8,727692	615	600	Low	15
-70,525947	8,727343	615	600	Low	15
-70,526184	8,726346	615	600	Low	15
-70,525849	8,726034	660	600	Low	60
-70,525292	8,725962	648	600	Low	48
-70,524494	8,725633	631	600	Low	31
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-70,516892	8,725535	579	600	Low	-21
-70,516834	8,725074	608	600	Low	8
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-70,516292	8,723895	628	600	Low	28
-70,516231	8,722567	579	600	Low	-21
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-70,51721	8,72177	574	600	Low	-26
-70,517691	8,721492	574	600	Low	-26
-70,518228	8,721121	583	600	Low	-17
-70,518745	8,720657	583	600	Low	-17
-70,519171	8,72049	588	600	Low	-12
-70,519615	8,720303	558	600	Low	-42

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-70,52115	8,719449	646	600	Low	46
-70,52087	8,718989	646	600	Low	46
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-70,519152	8,715823	575	600	Low	-25
-70,519298	8,715287	537	600	Low	-63
-70,519723	8,715046	547	600	Low	-53
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-70,520818	8,715281	519	600	Low	-81
-70,52132	8,715648	539	600	Low	-61
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-70,522212	8,716198	516	600	Low	-84
-70,522733	8,716639	572	600	Low	-28
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-70,524292	8,716909	550	600	Low	-50
-70,525551	8,716517	580	600	Low	-20
-70,52681	8,716106	620	600	Low	20
-70,52703	8,71568	620	600	Low	20
-70,526844	8,715386	631	600	Low	31
-70,52649	8,715019	631	600	Low	31
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-70,526097	8,714153	621	600	Low	21
-70,52541	8,713879	599	600	Low	-1
-70,525279	8,713474	608	600	Low	8
-70,52529	8,711777	615	600	Low	15
-70,525158	8,711021	632	600	Low	32
-70,524896	8,710524	632	600	Low	32
-70,524226	8,709881	613	600	Low	13
-70,524167	8,709125	600	600	Low	0
-70,52385	8,708591	578	600	Low	-22
-70,523533	8,708039	571	600	Low	-29
-70,523679	8,707559	536	600	Low	-64
-70,52403	8,707189	554	600	Low	-46
-70,524752	8,707112	574	600	Low	-26
-70,525103	8,70665	551	600	Low	-49
-70,525509	8,706187	529	600	Low	-71
-70,526047	8,706295	553	600	Low	-47
-70,526568	8,706754	544	600	Low	-56
-70,526939	8,706864	544	600	Low	-56
-70,527364	8,706585	538	600	Low	-62
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-70,529333	8,707573	552	600	Low	-48
-70,529818	8,708199	555	600	Low	-45
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-70,529583	8,709767	562	600	Low	-38
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-70,53016	8,710189	562	600	Low	-38
-70,530678	8,71004	545	600	Low	-55
-70,531254	8,710277	536	600	Low	-64
-70,531643	8,710294	536	600	Low	-64
-70,532254	8,710052	543	600	Low	-57
-70,532996	8,709975	548	600	Low	-52
-70,533663	8,710101	548	600	Low	-52
-70,534351	8,710523	555	600	Low	-45
-70,534761	8,711038	547	600	Low	-53
-70,535373	8,711017	547	600	Low	-53
-70,536058	8,710774	553	600	Low	-47
-70,536542	8,711252	571	600	Low	-29
-70,536842	8,712155	577	600	Low	-23
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-70,537182	8,713776	608	600	Low	8
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-70,536872	8,715032	601	600	Low	1
-70,536857	8,715899	598	600	Low	-2
-70,53697	8,71636	605	600	Low	5
-70,537286	8,716395	613	600	Low	13
-70,53773	8,716154	611	600	Low	11
-70,537931	8,715581	671	600	Low	71
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-70,538081	8,711356	593	600	Low	-7
-70,538228	8,71095	581	600	Low	-19
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-70,538704	8,709657	595	600	Low	-5
-70,538332	8,709197	612	600	Low	12
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-70,535301	8,70707	615	600	Low	15
-70,534613	8,70663	615	600	Low	15

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-70,533255	8,705381	583	600	Low	-17
-70,532417	8,70437	594	600	Low	-6
-70,531932	8,7038	579	600	Low	-21
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-70,528289	8,701527	572	600	Low	-28
-70,527954	8,701178	565	600	Low	-35
-70,527321	8,70048	569	600	Low	-31
-70,527245	8,700129	540	600	Low	-60
-70,527616	8,700091	540	600	Low	-60
-70,528266	8,700402	546	600	Low	-54
-70,528972	8,70075	534	600	Low	-66
-70,529788	8,700839	535	600	Low	-65
-70,53077	8,700724	554	600	Low	-46
-70,531362	8,700463	573	600	Low	-27
-70,532047	8,700055	536	600	Low	-64
-70,533268	8,699589	554	600	Low	-46
-70,534195	8,699437	549	600	Low	-51
-70,535196	8,699433	541	600	Low	-59
-70,535846	8,6998	538	600	Low	-62
-70,536553	8,700442	563	600	Low	-37
-70,537111	8,700754	574	600	Low	-26
-70,537592	8,70053	574	600	Low	-26
-70,538258	8,700214	577	600	Low	-23
-70,538906	8,699972	582	600	Low	-18
-70,539647	8,699932	588	600	Low	-12
-70,540277	8,699874	588	600	Low	-12
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-70,540535	8,69932	621	600	Low	21
-70,540292	8,698859	590	600	Low	-10
-70,540104	8,698344	591	600	Low	-9
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-70,54028	8,696056	568	600	Low	-32
-70,540446	8,695723	582	600	Low	-18
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-70,54152	8,695405	544	600	Low	-56
-70,54189	8,695274	544	600	Low	-56
-70,542481	8,6947	567	600	Low	-33
-70,54298	8,694292	565	600	Low	-35
-70,543553	8,694087	565	600	Low	-35
-70,543962	8,694307	547	600	Low	-53
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-70,543449	8,695803	588	600	Low	-12
-70,543229	8,696302	577	600	Low	-23
-70,543195	8,697114	569	600	Low	-31
-70,543216	8,697796	569	600	Low	-31
-70,542997	8,698443	566	600	Low	-34
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-70,50586	8,743933	605	600	Low	5
-70,505265	8,743566	635	600	Low	35
-70,504782	8,743347	635	600	Low	35
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-70,503037	8,742616	629	600	Low	29
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-70,5017	8,742142	615	600	Low	15
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-70,500881	8,741407	626	600	Low	26
-70,500176	8,741373	614	600	Low	14
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-70,499102	8,741672	599	600	Low	-1
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-70,501531	8,736977	634	600	Low	34
-70,501268	8,73613	628	600	Low	28
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-70,501928	8,734393	618	600	Low	18
-70,501889	8,733914	618	600	Low	18
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-70,501662	8,732808	607	600	Low	7
-70,501846	8,732291	607	600	Low	7

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-70,501803	8,730852	610	600	Low	10
-70,502135	8,730592	587	600	Low	-13
-70,502692	8,730738	587	600	Low	-13
-70,503252	8,731695	578	600	Low	-22
-70,503591	8,7328	582	600	Low	-18
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-70,504525	8,734604	565	600	Low	-35
-70,505044	8,734565	551	600	Low	-49
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-70,506599	8,734043	564	600	Low	-36
-70,507194	8,734557	551	600	Low	-49
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-70,511844	8,72893	576	600	Low	-24
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-70,512074	8,730737	607	600	Low	7
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-70,500859	8,754559	628	600	Low	28
-70,501151	8,753378	594	600	Low	-6
-70,501446	8,752971	629	600	Low	29
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-70,502928	8,752485	583	600	Low	-17
-70,504708	8,752589	549	600	Low	-51
-70,505691	8,752529	547	600	Low	-53
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-70,506913	8,752266	555	600	Low	-45
-70,50747	8,752449	553	600	Low	-47
-70,508529	8,752998	571	600	Low	-29
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-70,509774	8,753546	550	600	Low	-50
-70,510221	8,753932	580	600	Low	-20
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-70,512043	8,755197	573	600	Low	-27
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-70,51842	8,754932	582	600	Low	-18
-70,519183	8,755556	586	600	Low	-14
-70,519908	8,756088	582	600	Low	-18
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-70,520859	8,757394	595	600	Low	-5
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-70,521669	8,75597	604	600	Low	4
-70,521723	8,755675	604	600	Low	4

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-70,523281	8,755706	624	600	Low	24
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-70,518091	8,751594	625	600	Low	25
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-70,521774	8,754365	631	600	Low	31
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-70,490082	8,776756	591	600	Low	-9
-70,490673	8,776164	597	600	Low	-3
-70,491081	8,776162	597	600	Low	-3
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-70,490676	8,776828	612	600	Low	12
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-70,490135	8,778352	615	600	Low	15
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-70,490865	8,777823	612	600	Low	12
-70,491491	8,777779	635	600	Low	35
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-70,493289	8,771874	565	600	Low	-35
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-70,497227	8,773518	583	600	Low	-17
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-70,498435	8,778826	577	600	Low	-23

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-70,499794	8,78476	582	600	Low	-18
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-70,500122	8,783394	576	600	Low	-24
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-70,501056	8,785051	584	600	Low	-16
-70,501986	8,785711	594	600	Low	-6
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-70,498506	8,768828	623	600	Low	23

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-70,496765	8,769314	586	600	Low	-14
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-70,496205	8,768247	609	600	Low	9
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-70,485553	8,753319	606	600	Low	6
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-70,487475	8,751771	623	600	Low	23
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-70,488014	8,766102	542	600	Low	-58
-70,488684	8,766708	563	600	Low	-37
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-70,48871	8,768461	603	600	Low	3
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-70,488585	8,769697	564	600	Low	-36

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-70,479776	8,738871	570	600	Low	-30
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-70,478784	8,731985	575	600	Low	-25
-70,478655	8,732206	574	600	Low	-26
-70,478676	8,732631	574	600	Low	-26
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-70,477822	8,73256	598	600	Low	-2
-70,477245	8,731972	616	600	Low	16
-70,476723	8,731199	627	600	Low	27
-70,476111	8,731073	615	600	Low	15
-70,476021	8,731903	590	600	Low	-10
-70,476006	8,73277	594	600	Low	-6
-70,475451	8,733086	581	600	Low	-19
-70,474581	8,733449	600	600	Low	0
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-70,473768	8,734042	599	600	Low	-1
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-70,473734	8,73491	603	600	Low	3
-70,474457	8,734944	587	600	Low	-13

-70,4747	8,735404	575	600	Low	-25
-70,474721	8,735994	588	600	Low	-12
-70,475222	8,736177	588	600	Low	-12
-70,475909	8,736229	583	600	Low	-17
-70,476243	8,736523	601	600	Low	1
-70,476486	8,736817	586	600	Low	-14
-70,477301	8,73674	582	600	Low	-18
-70,477969	8,736848	576	600	Low	-24
-70,4791	8,736807	566	600	Low	-34
-70,480751	8,736911	562	600	Low	-38
-70,481696	8,736797	558	600	Low	-42
-70,48242	8,736997	537	600	Low	-63
-70,48257	8,737568	565	600	Low	-35
-70,48209	8,737994	573	600	Low	-27
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-70,480774	8,738166	581	600	Low	-19
-70,479884	8,738261	582	600	Low	-18
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-70,465774	8,719196	586	600	Low	-14
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-70,467071	8,718896	608	600	Low	8
-70,467254	8,718379	645	600	Low	45
-70,466919	8,717864	624	600	Low	24
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-70,466133	8,716059	608	600	Low	8
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-70,464867	8,714846	622	600	Low	22
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-70,463383	8,714557	589	600	Low	-11
-70,463233	8,714041	589	600	Low	-11
-70,463749	8,713338	564	600	Low	-36
-70,464488	8,712634	574	600	Low	-26
-70,464967	8,711968	605	600	Low	5
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-70,46544	8,709679	635	600	Low	35
-70,465325	8,708646	595	600	Low	-5

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-70,463485	8,702714	598	600	Low	-2
-70,463856	8,702601	600	600	Low	0
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-70,465564	8,703333	608	600	Low	8
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-70,468589	8,708929	610	600	Low	10
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-70,470746	8,710507	609	600	Low	9
-70,471157	8,711169	609	600	Low	9
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-70,473085	8,71131	598	600	Low	-2
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-70,478279	8,711917	614	600	Low	14
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-70,479877	8,71287	588	600	Low	-12
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-70,480511	8,713863	614	600	Low	14
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-70,482986	8,711492	609	600	Low	9
-70,483612	8,71042	592	600	Low	-8
-70,484018	8,709902	600	600	Low	0
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-70,485023	8,710783	624	600	Low	24
-70,485171	8,710598	624	600	Low	24
-70,485277	8,709381	594	600	Low	-6
-70,485497	8,708863	612	600	Low	12
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-70,486974	8,707087	599	600	Low	-1
-70,486822	8,706312	605	600	Low	5
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-70,480441	8,695896	623	600	Low	23
-70,479883	8,695456	617	600	Low	17
-70,479583	8,694756	608	600	Low	8
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-70,480432	8,693794	577	600	Low	-23
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-70,481437	8,694675	585	600	Low	-15
-70,481845	8,694784	585	600	Low	-15
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-70,483036	8,695849	572	600	Low	-28
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-70,485153	8,696727	573	600	Low	-27
-70,486043	8,696908	571	600	Low	-29
-70,486377	8,696833	584	600	Low	-16
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-70,487598	8,696237	562	600	Low	-38

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-70,486124	8,69842	603	600	Low	3
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-70,488783	8,705272	579	600	Low	-21
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-70,490089	8,707296	590	600	Low	-10
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-70,488426	8,708593	584	600	Low	-16
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-70,462865	8,733891	605	600	Low	5
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-70,465	8,729788	612	600	Low	12
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-70,465661	8,728125	613	600	Low	13
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-70,463501	8,72592	621	600	Low	21
-70,463169	8,726142	621	600	Low	21
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-70,552585	8,807835	1183	1200	Medium	-17
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-70,550892	8,806551	1196	1200	Medium	-4
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-70,549656	8,785822	1237	1200	Medium	37
-70,549956	8,78643	1230	1200	Medium	30
-70,549661	8,78704	1230	1200	Medium	30
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-70,549755	8,791761	1227	1200	Medium	27
-70,549703	8,792518	1226	1200	Medium	26
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-70,559483	8,763481	1225	1200	Medium	25
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-70,557999	8,763228	1177	1200	Medium	-23
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-70,551417	8,767793	1214	1200	Medium	14
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-70,54869	8,771863	1177	1200	Medium	-23
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-70,546962	8,775448	1233	1200	Medium	33
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-70,573858	8,760064	1103	1200	Medium	-97
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-70,572782	8,760031	1097	1200	Medium	-103
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-70,577808	8,747025	1098	1200	Medium	-102
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-70,605132	8,737281	1209	1200	Medium	9
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-70,604385	8,736067	1164	1200	Medium	-36
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-70,620882	8,743873	1252	1200	Medium	52
-70,620733	8,743707	1222	1200	Medium	22
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-70,62021	8,742769	1218	1200	Medium	18
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-70,59575	8,728485	1235	1200	Medium	35
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-70,589735	8,706827	1221	1200	Medium	21
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-70,590197	8,710939	1213	1200	Medium	13
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-70,589509	8,714723	1152	1200	Medium	-48
-70,589141	8,71537	1152	1200	Medium	-48
-70,588772	8,715833	1185	1200	Medium	-15
-70,588515	8,716295	1170	1200	Medium	-30
-70,587942	8,716851	1170	1200	Medium	-30
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-70,590823	8,700994	1113	1200	Medium	-87
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-70,590082	8,701089	1140	1200	Medium	-60
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-70,599302	8,693912	1167	1200	Medium	-33
-70,599529	8,695073	1175	1200	Medium	-25
-70,599642	8,695479	1215	1200	Medium	15
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-70,595999	8,701802	1117	1200	Medium	-83
-70,595814	8,702061	1117	1200	Medium	-83
-70,595594	8,70256	1167	1200	Medium	-33
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-70,600508	8,685385	1117	1200	Medium	-83
-70,599674	8,685573	1104	1200	Medium	-96
-70,598711	8,685688	1104	1200	Medium	-96
-70,598155	8,685764	1104	1200	Medium	-96
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-70,622433	8,682037	1304	1200	Medium	104
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-70,624118	8,681716	1352	1200	Medium	152
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-70,635257	8,664164	1113	1200	Medium	-87
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-70,634137	8,662361	1133	1200	Medium	-67
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-70,632238	8,660377	1101	1200	Medium	-99
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-70,63175	8,65894	1136	1200	Medium	-64
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-70,630103	8,655258	1055	1200	Medium	-145
-70,629583	8,655187	1055	1200	Medium	-145
-70,628806	8,655559	1126	1200	Medium	-74
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-70,621379	8,661235	1279	1200	Medium	79
-70,621122	8,661642	1225	1200	Medium	25
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-70,61957	8,662829	1101	1200	Medium	-99
-70,619052	8,663089	1140	1200	Medium	-60
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-70,618053	8,663647	1123	1200	Medium	-77
-70,617945	8,664422	1174	1200	Medium	-26
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-70,61685	8,668411	1157	1200	Medium	-43
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-70,661365	8,683179	1236	1200	Medium	36
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-70,661555	8,684174	1227	1200	Medium	27
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-70,663169	8,688705	1206	1200	Medium	6

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-70,66797	8,692705	1281	1200	Medium	81
-70,668342	8,693035	1241	1200	Medium	41
-70,669158	8,693216	1259	1200	Medium	59
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-70,670463	8,694796	1256	1200	Medium	56
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-70,666677	8,693891	1236	1200	Medium	36
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-70,665753	8,694485	1229	1200	Medium	29
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-70,651728	8,6837	1171	1200	Medium	-29
-70,651132	8,683039	1169	1200	Medium	-31
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-70,650995	8,651498	1267	1200	Medium	67
-70,651255	8,651681	1279	1200	Medium	79
-70,651515	8,651717	1279	1200	Medium	79
-70,651774	8,651716	1279	1200	Medium	79
-70,65207	8,651678	1279	1200	Medium	79
-70,652442	8,651824	1297	1200	Medium	97
-70,652814	8,652154	1251	1200	Medium	51
-70,653037	8,652301	1276	1200	Medium	76
-70,653334	8,652373	1276	1200	Medium	76
-70,653742	8,652335	1276	1200	Medium	76
-70,65415	8,652444	1300	1200	Medium	100
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-70,654413	8,653365	1259	1200	Medium	59
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-70,65049	8,663342	1219	1200	Medium	19
-70,650492	8,663748	1219	1200	Medium	19
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-70,64976	8,648995	1237	1200	Medium	37
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-70,661014	8,668498	1474	1400	Medium	74
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-70,607743	8,701414	1659	1600	Medium	59
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-70,597486	8,709738	1565	1600	Medium	-35
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-70,599239	8,714666	1633	1600	Medium	33
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-70,621136	8,699481	1491	1600	Medium	-109
-70,620526	8,699805	1546	1600	Medium	-54
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-70,619221	8,700537	1498	1600	Medium	-102
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-70,617667	8,700358	1443	1600	Medium	-157
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-70,628753	8,677698	1687	1600	Medium	87
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-70,687818	8,718389	1628	1600	Medium	28
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-70,685778	8,717975	1644	1600	Medium	44
-70,684569	8,71717	1649	1600	Medium	49

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-70,666872	8,70241	1654	1600	Medium	54
-70,666768	8,701785	1618	1600	Medium	18
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-70,649562	8,690199	1484	1600	Medium	-116
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-70,670033	8,683485	1641	1600	Medium	41
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-70,670646	8,683989	1643	1600	Medium	43
-70,671053	8,683819	1643	1600	Medium	43
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-70,671497	8,684425	1689	1600	Medium	89
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-70,671608	8,686452	1612	1600	Medium	12
-70,671917	8,687026	1612	1600	Medium	12
-70,672258	8,687396	1623	1600	Medium	23
-70,672733	8,687292	1623	1600	Medium	23
-70,673139	8,686919	1662	1600	Medium	62
-70,673884	8,686341	1621	1600	Medium	21
-70,674493	8,685899	1652	1600	Medium	52
-70,675036	8,685795	1650	1600	Medium	50
-70,675274	8,685794	1650	1600	Medium	50
-70,675615	8,685995	1686	1600	Medium	86
-70,675956	8,6864	1638	1600	Medium	38
-70,676331	8,68677	1657	1600	Medium	57
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-70,678026	8,68585	1693	1600	Medium	93
-70,678467	8,685814	1693	1600	Medium	93
-70,678909	8,685981	1689	1600	Medium	89
-70,679318	8,686114	1689	1600	Medium	89
-70,67976	8,686214	1698	1600	Medium	98
-70,680302	8,685975	1698	1600	Medium	98
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-70,681721	8,684211	1726	1600	Medium	126
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-70,682367	8,684445	1716	1600	Medium	116
-70,682505	8,684748	1676	1600	Medium	76
-70,682541	8,685221	1676	1600	Medium	76
-70,682373	8,685695	1640	1600	Medium	40
-70,68224	8,68627	1658	1600	Medium	58
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-70,682653	8,687654	1640	1600	Medium	40
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-70,681813	8,689551	1594	1600	Medium	-6
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-70,67668	8,696469	1547	1600	Medium	-53
-70,677091	8,697244	1599	1600	Medium	-1
-70,677567	8,697242	1599	1600	Medium	-1
-70,678179	8,697307	1631	1600	Medium	31
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-70,68043	8,699393	1644	1600	Medium	44
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-70,682601	8,698741	1674	1600	Medium	74
-70,682972	8,698131	1627	1600	Medium	27
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-70,683715	8,697249	1660	1600	Medium	60
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-70,684565	8,697414	1620	1600	Medium	20
-70,684617	8,697549	1632	1600	Medium	32
-70,685061	8,698088	1616	1600	Medium	16
-70,685199	8,69856	1616	1600	Medium	16
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-70,690173	8,701851	1649	1600	Medium	49
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-70,691976	8,702485	1641	1600	Medium	41
-70,692656	8,702583	1654	1600	Medium	54
-70,693607	8,702647	1656	1600	Medium	56
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-70,69486	8,701728	1650	1600	Medium	50
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-70,696792	8,700706	1674	1600	Medium	74
-70,697168	8,701211	1688	1600	Medium	88
-70,697543	8,701615	1654	1600	Medium	54
-70,697647	8,702054	1654	1600	Medium	54
-70,697273	8,701988	1654	1600	Medium	54

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-70,696526	8,702059	1623	1600	Medium	23
-70,69612	8,702331	1602	1600	Medium	2
-70,695816	8,702839	1602	1600	Medium	2
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-70,69538	8,703991	1608	1600	Medium	8
-70,695109	8,704262	1608	1600	Medium	8
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-70,694297	8,70484	1622	1600	Medium	22
-70,694025	8,704909	1622	1600	Medium	22
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-70,693516	8,70508	1602	1600	Medium	2
-70,693143	8,705184	1602	1600	Medium	2
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-70,692329	8,70539	1581	1600	Medium	-19
-70,691582	8,705393	1569	1600	Medium	-31
-70,691072	8,705463	1624	1600	Medium	24
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-70,68968	8,705605	1622	1600	Medium	22
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-70,688558	8,705407	1612	1600	Medium	12
-70,688115	8,705104	1612	1600	Medium	12
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-70,686079	8,705519	1623	1600	Medium	23
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-70,685332	8,70559	1629	1600	Medium	29
-70,684789	8,705694	1629	1600	Medium	29
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-70,683089	8,713002	1619	1600	Medium	19
-70,683329	8,713508	1619	1600	Medium	19
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-70,671476	8,65458	1644	1600	Medium	44
-70,671491	8,654141	1644	1600	Medium	44
-70,671251	8,653736	1645	1600	Medium	45
-70,671064	8,653517	1678	1600	Medium	78
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-70,668241	8,652769	1557	1600	Medium	-43
-70,668038	8,652973	1603	1600	Medium	3
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-70,667361	8,65333	1565	1600	Medium	-35
-70,667141	8,653568	1565	1600	Medium	-35
-70,666837	8,653992	1543	1600	Medium	-57
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-70,665956	8,654367	1517	1600	Medium	-83
-70,665565	8,654285	1517	1600	Medium	-83
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-70,663999	8,653615	1485	1600	Medium	-115
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-70,662519	8,652878	1471	1600	Medium	-129
-70,662194	8,652356	1471	1600	Medium	-129
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-70,660335	8,650725	1523	1600	Medium	-77
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-70,659854	8,653228	1623	1600	Medium	23
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-70,659884	8,658061	1602	1600	Medium	2
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-70,660636	8,659359	1678	1600	Medium	78
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-70,661724	8,659608	1671	1600	Medium	71
-70,662369	8,65947	1697	1600	Medium	97
-70,662879	8,659485	1697	1600	Medium	97
-70,663304	8,659584	1661	1600	Medium	61
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-70,663158	8,661275	1649	1600	Medium	49
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-70,664181	8,662031	1689	1600	Medium	89
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-70,664961	8,661858	1683	1600	Medium	83
-70,665317	8,661688	1683	1600	Medium	83
-70,665756	8,661179	1693	1600	Medium	93
-70,666247	8,660737	1693	1600	Medium	93
-70,666756	8,660651	1696	1600	Medium	96
-70,667046	8,660937	1696	1600	Medium	96
-70,667184	8,66146	1715	1600	Medium	115
-70,667102	8,662001	1715	1600	Medium	115
-70,667138	8,662542	1701	1600	Medium	101
-70,667326	8,662845	1701	1600	Medium	101
-70,6677	8,662945	1679	1600	Medium	79
-70,66782	8,66313	1679	1600	Medium	79
-70,667873	8,663705	1679	1600	Medium	79
-70,66774	8,664212	1645	1600	Medium	45
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-70,667145	8,664232	1645	1600	Medium	45

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-70,66584	8,664711	1624	1600	Medium	24
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-70,666578	8,66655	1677	1600	Medium	77
-70,666599	8,667344	1654	1600	Medium	54
-70,66667	8,668138	1624	1600	Medium	24
-70,666893	8,668678	1624	1600	Medium	24
-70,667338	8,669335	1660	1600	Medium	60
-70,667578	8,669807	1632	1600	Medium	32
-70,667581	8,670517	1625	1600	Medium	25
-70,667585	8,671429	1614	1600	Medium	14
-70,667536	8,672004	1614	1600	Medium	14
-70,667198	8,672394	1638	1600	Medium	38
-70,666674	8,672836	1579	1600	Medium	-21
-70,666659	8,673427	1613	1600	Medium	13
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-70,667477	8,673965	1673	1600	Medium	73
-70,66802	8,673743	1705	1600	Medium	105
-70,668325	8,673707	1705	1600	Medium	105
-70,668564	8,674011	1673	1600	Medium	73
-70,668905	8,674229	1689	1600	Medium	89
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-70,669753	8,674022	1687	1600	Medium	87
-70,669873	8,674275	1687	1600	Medium	87
-70,669859	8,674918	1657	1600	Medium	57
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-70,672133	8,66388	1840	1800	Medium	40
-70,672741	8,663269	1822	1800	Medium	22
-70,673113	8,662761	1869	1800	Medium	69

-70,673008	8,662187	1869	1800	Medium	69
-70,672904	8,66168	1820	1800	Medium	20
-70,673005	8,661409	1858	1800	Medium	58
-70,673444	8,6609	1879	1800	Medium	79
-70,67351	8,660528	1879	1800	Medium	79
-70,673407	8,660225	1916	1800	Medium	116
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-70,672828	8,659754	1905	1800	Medium	105
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-70,671978	8,659724	1881	1800	Medium	81
-70,671535	8,659388	1872	1800	Medium	72
-70,67116	8,659085	1873	1800	Medium	73
-70,670277	8,65892	1882	1800	Medium	82
-70,669664	8,658754	1882	1800	Medium	82
-70,66929	8,658519	1873	1800	Medium	73
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-70,669215	8,657032	1779	1800	Medium	-21
-70,66942	8,6572	1823	1800	Medium	23
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-70,670236	8,657501	1794	1800	Medium	-6
-70,67078	8,657532	1759	1800	Medium	-41
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-70,673634	8,657824	1713	1800	Medium	-87
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-70,672224	8,67696	1808	1800	Medium	8
-70,672867	8,676417	1808	1800	Medium	8
-70,673511	8,676042	1822	1800	Medium	22
-70,673951	8,675601	1872	1800	Medium	72
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-70,673539	8,674724	1818	1800	Medium	18
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-70,674038	8,672254	1816	1800	Medium	16
-70,674443	8,671746	1815	1800	Medium	15
-70,674643	8,670866	1838	1800	Medium	38
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-70,675792	8,669543	1918	1800	Medium	118
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-70,675382	8,668902	1843	1800	Medium	43
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-70,675071	8,667822	1949	1800	Medium	149
-70,674833	8,667756	1949	1800	Medium	149
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-70,673037	8,668777	1875	1800	Medium	75
-70,672461	8,669118	1891	1800	Medium	91
-70,67175	8,669459	1907	1800	Medium	107
-70,671275	8,669596	1878	1800	Medium	78
-70,670597	8,669971	1886	1800	Medium	86
-70,670055	8,670278	1863	1800	Medium	63
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-70,669471	8,668759	1795	1800	Medium	-5
-70,669908	8,667811	1771	1800	Medium	-29
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-70,681874	8,692939	1796	1800	Medium	-4
-70,682652	8,692124	1781	1800	Medium	-19
-70,683159	8,691548	1784	1800	Medium	-16
-70,683734	8,690903	1748	1800	Medium	-52
-70,684477	8,690021	1792	1800	Medium	-8
-70,684781	8,689546	1839	1800	Medium	39
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-70,684707	8,68833	1855	1800	Medium	55
-70,684433	8,687858	1758	1800	Medium	-42
-70,684431	8,687418	1758	1800	Medium	-42
-70,684598	8,686809	1874	1800	Medium	74
-70,684901	8,686132	1822	1800	Medium	22
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-70,685066	8,685016	1804	1800	Medium	4
-70,685267	8,68444	1787	1800	Medium	-13
-70,685571	8,683898	1855	1800	Medium	55
-70,685909	8,683525	1828	1800	Medium	28
-70,685735	8,682613	1855	1800	Medium	55
-70,686003	8,681936	1890	1800	Medium	90

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-70,68539	8,681398	1885	1800	Medium	85
-70,685321	8,681331	1885	1800	Medium	85
-70,685252	8,680925	1902	1800	Medium	102
-70,685114	8,680588	1902	1800	Medium	102
-70,684876	8,680488	1902	1800	Medium	102
-70,684572	8,680861	1904	1800	Medium	104
-70,68437	8,6812	1904	1800	Medium	104
-70,684168	8,681674	1890	1800	Medium	90
-70,683794	8,681675	1890	1800	Medium	90
-70,683692	8,681473	1879	1800	Medium	79
-70,683487	8,681237	1896	1800	Medium	96
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-70,683414	8,680257	1916	1800	Medium	116
-70,68331	8,679649	1916	1800	Medium	116
-70,683139	8,679414	1929	1800	Medium	129
-70,682731	8,679382	1924	1800	Medium	124
-70,682494	8,679619	1917	1800	Medium	117
-70,682291	8,679789	1917	1800	Medium	117
-70,681986	8,679824	1912	1800	Medium	112
-70,681613	8,679927	1912	1800	Medium	112
-70,68107	8,680099	1907	1800	Medium	107
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-70,680767	8,680742	1904	1800	Medium	104
-70,680531	8,681115	1904	1800	Medium	104
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-70,67785	8,681702	1863	1800	Medium	63
-70,677513	8,682176	1855	1800	Medium	55
-70,677242	8,68238	1855	1800	Medium	55
-70,676767	8,682484	1846	1800	Medium	46
-70,67629	8,682317	1846	1800	Medium	46
-70,675881	8,681981	1888	1800	Medium	88
-70,675405	8,681814	1908	1800	Medium	108
-70,674964	8,681985	1908	1800	Medium	108
-70,674387	8,682122	1861	1800	Medium	61
-70,673776	8,682159	1861	1800	Medium	61
-70,673232	8,68206	1901	1800	Medium	101
-70,672756	8,681825	1830	1800	Medium	30
-70,672448	8,681421	1830	1800	Medium	30
-70,672242	8,680983	1841	1800	Medium	41
-70,672206	8,680408	1877	1800	Medium	77
-70,672271	8,679833	1877	1800	Medium	77
-70,671963	8,679294	1804	1800	Medium	4
-70,695052	8,707448	1835	1800	Medium	35

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-70,697824	8,704461	1768	1800	Medium	-32
-70,698807	8,704187	1806	1800	Medium	6
-70,699555	8,704251	1806	1800	Medium	6
-70,700199	8,703944	1846	1800	Medium	46
-70,700842	8,703434	1803	1800	Medium	3
-70,701421	8,703702	1779	1800	Medium	-21
-70,701932	8,704105	1835	1800	Medium	35
-70,702375	8,704272	1811	1800	Medium	11
-70,703224	8,704234	1779	1800	Medium	-21
-70,704073	8,704197	1793	1800	Medium	-7
-70,704615	8,703958	1819	1800	Medium	19
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-70,70536	8,703414	1798	1800	Medium	-2
-70,705361	8,703752	1819	1800	Medium	19
-70,70489	8,704666	1810	1800	Medium	10
-70,704791	8,705377	1810	1800	Medium	10
-70,704895	8,705815	1837	1800	Medium	37
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-70,705813	8,70598	1840	1800	Medium	40
-70,705811	8,705406	1835	1800	Medium	35
-70,705977	8,704594	1835	1800	Medium	35
-70,706382	8,703984	1858	1800	Medium	58
-70,706821	8,703407	1839	1800	Medium	39
-70,70675	8,702731	1866	1800	Medium	66
-70,70651	8,702293	1866	1800	Medium	66
-70,705897	8,702059	1904	1800	Medium	104
-70,704912	8,702064	1882	1800	Medium	82
-70,704097	8,702034	1851	1800	Medium	51
-70,703517	8,701563	1830	1800	Medium	30
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-70,702428	8,701162	1817	1800	Medium	17
-70,702189	8,700792	1817	1800	Medium	17
-70,702424	8,700283	1782	1800	Medium	-18
-70,703102	8,699909	1831	1800	Medium	31
-70,704323	8,69943	1812	1800	Medium	12
-70,705476	8,699019	1847	1800	Medium	47
-70,705849	8,698916	1847	1800	Medium	47
-70,706389	8,69817	1886	1800	Medium	86
-70,706658	8,697459	1876	1800	Medium	76
-70,706622	8,69702	1866	1800	Medium	66
-70,70618	8,697022	1892	1800	Medium	92
-70,705434	8,697329	1853	1800	Medium	53
-70,705062	8,697568	1883	1800	Medium	83
-70,704623	8,69811	1846	1800	Medium	46

-70,704386	8,698281	1867	1800	Medium	67
-70,70364	8,698554	1877	1800	Medium	77
-70,702654	8,698457	1874	1800	Medium	74
-70,702145	8,698527	1874	1800	Medium	74
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-70,70089	8,698938	1772	1800	Medium	-28
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-70,699494	8,698336	1879	1800	Medium	79
-70,698746	8,698035	1830	1800	Medium	30
-70,697997	8,697667	1906	1800	Medium	106
-70,697623	8,697635	1876	1800	Medium	76
-70,697116	8,698144	1818	1800	Medium	18
-70,696608	8,698619	1838	1800	Medium	38
-70,696066	8,698825	1822	1800	Medium	22
-70,695353	8,698862	1855	1800	Medium	55
-70,695082	8,699032	1855	1800	Medium	55
-70,694709	8,699236	1855	1800	Medium	55
-70,694064	8,699307	1883	1800	Medium	83
-70,693895	8,69951	1883	1800	Medium	83
-70,69332	8,700189	1837	1800	Medium	37
-70,693048	8,700156	1837	1800	Medium	37
-70,692607	8,700091	1816	1800	Medium	16
-70,692436	8,699889	1816	1800	Medium	16
-70,691788	8,699249	1834	1800	Medium	34
-70,691209	8,699083	1818	1800	Medium	18
-70,690428	8,69912	1818	1800	Medium	18
-70,690055	8,699291	1834	1800	Medium	34
-70,689615	8,699529	1834	1800	Medium	34
-70,689206	8,699227	1832	1800	Medium	32
-70,688763	8,698891	1832	1800	Medium	32
-70,688253	8,698826	1797	1800	Medium	-3
-70,688083	8,698759	1797	1800	Medium	-3
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-70,687227	8,697242	1838	1800	Medium	38
-70,68685	8,696601	1794	1800	Medium	-6
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-70,687215	8,694572	1848	1800	Medium	48
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-70,686872	8,693965	1857	1800	Medium	57
-70,686091	8,693968	1834	1800	Medium	34
-70,685309	8,69387	1812	1800	Medium	12
-70,684629	8,693535	1931	1800	Medium	131

-70,683982	8,693268	1883	1800	Medium	83
-70,683472	8,693236	1862	1800	Medium	62
-70,683031	8,693407	1862	1800	Medium	62
-70,682456	8,693917	1853	1800	Medium	53
-70,682016	8,69429	1836	1800	Medium	36
-70,681781	8,694798	1859	1800	Medium	59
-70,681715	8,695272	1859	1800	Medium	59
-70,68182	8,69588	1844	1800	Medium	44
-70,681651	8,696219	1844	1800	Medium	44
-70,681415	8,696558	1826	1800	Medium	26
-70,681178	8,696694	1829	1800	Medium	29
-70,680872	8,69656	1829	1800	Medium	29
-70,680769	8,696391	1829	1800	Medium	29
-70,680767	8,695986	1858	1800	Medium	58
-70,680426	8,695649	1858	1800	Medium	58
-70,680288	8,695312	1804	1800	Medium	4
-70,68032	8,694872	1804	1800	Medium	4
-70,680488	8,694365	1794	1800	Medium	-6
-70,680962	8,693889	1794	1800	Medium	-6
-70,685179	8,720805	1838	1800	Medium	38
-70,685912	8,721291	1841	1800	Medium	41
-70,686541	8,721373	1824	1800	Medium	24
-70,6871	8,721151	1779	1800	Medium	-21
-70,688084	8,720842	1809	1800	Medium	9
-70,689153	8,7205	1838	1800	Medium	38
-70,690051	8,720022	1816	1800	Medium	16
-70,691186	8,719494	1783	1800	Medium	-17
-70,69239	8,718964	1843	1800	Medium	43
-70,693392	8,718825	1835	1800	Medium	35
-70,693612	8,718773	1835	1800	Medium	35
-70,694052	8,718315	1765	1800	Medium	-35
-70,694408	8,718195	1765	1800	Medium	-35
-70,694834	8,718615	1801	1800	Medium	1
-70,695346	8,719154	1845	1800	Medium	45
-70,696012	8,719911	1819	1800	Medium	19
-70,696455	8,720231	1819	1800	Medium	19
-70,696828	8,719975	1819	1800	Medium	19
-70,696876	8,719333	1823	1800	Medium	23
-70,69655	8,718658	1870	1800	Medium	70
-70,695936	8,718002	1820	1800	Medium	20
-70,695865	8,717394	1807	1800	Medium	7
-70,695776	8,716482	1805	1800	Medium	5
-70,695519	8,716111	1888	1800	Medium	88
-70,695162	8,715944	1835	1800	Medium	35
-70,694467	8,716167	1815	1800	Medium	15
-70,693957	8,716253	1763	1800	Medium	-37

-70,693515	8,715985	1802	1800	Medium	2
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-70,69263	8,715668	1764	1800	Medium	-36
-70,691865	8,715637	1805	1800	Medium	5
-70,690575	8,715812	1868	1800	Medium	68
-70,689339	8,716544	1823	1800	Medium	23
-70,688762	8,716783	1823	1800	Medium	23
-70,688014	8,716635	1817	1800	Medium	17
-70,687383	8,715962	1825	1800	Medium	25
-70,686819	8,715271	1777	1800	Medium	-23
-70,686289	8,714412	1854	1800	Medium	54
-70,68569	8,71335	1829	1800	Medium	29
-70,685568	8,712792	1877	1800	Medium	77
-70,685224	8,711746	1806	1800	Medium	6
-70,685016	8,710953	1819	1800	Medium	19
-70,685097	8,709905	1822	1800	Medium	22
-70,685209	8,708552	1784	1800	Medium	-16
-70,685649	8,70806	1818	1800	Medium	18
-70,686345	8,708108	1813	1800	Medium	13
-70,687196	8,708476	1818	1800	Medium	18
-70,688029	8,708489	1803	1800	Medium	3
-70,689421	8,708449	1789	1800	Medium	-11
-70,690049	8,708294	1799	1800	Medium	-1
-70,690711	8,708122	1800	1800	Medium	0
-70,691796	8,707813	1761	1800	Medium	-39
-70,69239	8,707642	1772	1800	Medium	-28
-70,692849	8,707656	1772	1800	Medium	-28
-70,693461	8,707806	1788	1800	Medium	-12
-70,694305	8,707663	1799	1800	Medium	-1
-70,650964	8,696197	1757	1800	Medium	-43
-70,651171	8,696736	1796	1800	Medium	-4
-70,651717	8,697309	1797	1800	Medium	-3
-70,652365	8,697914	1761	1800	Medium	-39
-70,653147	8,698249	1789	1800	Medium	-11
-70,6541	8,698549	1769	1800	Medium	-31
-70,654847	8,698512	1760	1800	Medium	-40
-70,655189	8,698984	1815	1800	Medium	15
-70,654953	8,699492	1815	1800	Medium	15
-70,65441	8,699595	1792	1800	Medium	-8
-70,653152	8,699297	1830	1800	Medium	30
-70,652404	8,699165	1830	1800	Medium	30
-70,651827	8,699336	1847	1800	Medium	47
-70,651456	8,699777	1786	1800	Medium	-14
-70,651491	8,700081	1786	1800	Medium	-14
-70,651867	8,700553	1790	1800	Medium	-10
-70,652345	8,701193	1745	1800	Medium	-55

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-70,653166	8,702508	1787	1800	Medium	-13
-70,653472	8,702574	1787	1800	Medium	-13
-70,654084	8,702639	1754	1800	Medium	-46
-70,654629	8,703076	1793	1800	Medium	-7
-70,655343	8,703039	1793	1800	Medium	-7
-70,655683	8,703105	1761	1800	Medium	-39
-70,655756	8,704288	1777	1800	Medium	-23
-70,655521	8,705032	1785	1800	Medium	-15
-70,655422	8,705675	1810	1800	Medium	10
-70,655797	8,705876	1810	1800	Medium	10
-70,656852	8,706345	1837	1800	Medium	37
-70,657871	8,706475	1821	1800	Medium	21
-70,658517	8,706473	1809	1800	Medium	9
-70,658824	8,706877	1794	1800	Medium	-6
-70,658725	8,707553	1802	1800	Medium	2
-70,658898	8,708127	1749	1800	Medium	-51
-70,659648	8,7088	1845	1800	Medium	45
-70,660055	8,708731	1753	1800	Medium	-47
-70,660768	8,708491	1775	1800	Medium	-25
-70,662024	8,70835	1791	1800	Medium	-9
-70,662634	8,707908	1727	1800	Medium	-73
-70,663175	8,707466	1762	1800	Medium	-38
-70,663922	8,707294	1818	1800	Medium	18
-70,664632	8,706581	1798	1800	Medium	-2
-70,665141	8,70641	1798	1800	Medium	-2
-70,665486	8,707727	1822	1800	Medium	22
-70,66573	8,709044	1867	1800	Medium	67
-70,666519	8,710832	1838	1800	Medium	38
-70,666967	8,712317	1843	1800	Medium	43
-70,667681	8,712449	1819	1800	Medium	19
-70,66846	8,711871	1769	1800	Medium	-31
-70,669238	8,71109	1735	1800	Medium	-65
-70,670119	8,710579	1796	1800	Medium	-4
-70,671201	8,70956	1779	1800	Medium	-21
-70,672046	8,708543	1786	1800	Medium	-14
-70,673062	8,70793	1852	1800	Medium	52
-70,673707	8,707826	1784	1800	Medium	-16
-70,674388	8,708127	1853	1800	Medium	53
-70,67436	8,709378	1904	1800	Medium	104
-70,6745	8,71029	1940	1800	Medium	140
-70,676906	8,716667	1915	1800	Medium	115
-70,674607	8,711607	1913	1800	Medium	113
-70,67512	8,712315	1971	1800	Medium	171
-70,675633	8,712989	1929	1800	Medium	129
-70,676316	8,71383	1859	1800	Medium	59

-70,676422	8,714743	1884	1800	Medium	84
-70,676153	8,715487	1992	1800	Medium	192
-70,676056	8,716468	1994	1800	Medium	194
-70,676433	8,717345	1929	1800	Medium	129
-70,677354	8,718118	1862	1800	Medium	62
-70,678035	8,71842	1831	1800	Medium	31
-70,67868	8,718315	1831	1800	Medium	31
-70,679191	8,718617	1793	1800	Medium	-7
-70,679871	8,718716	1771	1800	Medium	-29
-70,680482	8,718645	1778	1800	Medium	-22
-70,681263	8,718608	1790	1800	Medium	-10
-70,68208	8,718943	1874	1800	Medium	74
-70,683101	8,719411	1804	1800	Medium	4
-70,683613	8,720051	1853	1800	Medium	53
-70,683955	8,720388	1795	1800	Medium	-5
-70,684532	8,720453	1863	1800	Medium	63
-70,607405	8,7097	1771	1800	Medium	-29
-70,604828	8,710894	1729	1800	Medium	-71
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-70,607303	8,709633	1771	1800	Medium	-29
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-70,607534	8,708044	1734	1800	Medium	-66
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-70,609124	8,706617	1751	1800	Medium	-49
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-70,610278	8,706207	1784	1800	Medium	-16
-70,610273	8,705125	1793	1800	Medium	-7
-70,610371	8,70428	1771	1800	Medium	-29
-70,610298	8,703029	1764	1800	Medium	-36
-70,610363	8,702387	1775	1800	Medium	-25
-70,61053	8,701609	1790	1800	Medium	-10
-70,610695	8,700594	1775	1800	Medium	-25
-70,610964	8,699816	1759	1800	Medium	-41
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-70,611951	8,700352	1738	1800	Medium	-62
-70,612261	8,70123	1704	1800	Medium	-96
-70,612296	8,7015	1736	1800	Medium	-64
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-70,613658	8,702407	1686	1800	Medium	-114
-70,61417	8,702912	1634	1800	Medium	-166
-70,61485	8,702943	1666	1800	Medium	-134
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-70,617675	8,704215	1634	1800	Medium	-166

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-70,621744	8,702474	1761	1800	Medium	-39
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-70,623269	8,701724	1712	1800	Medium	-88
-70,623879	8,701316	1615	1800	Medium	-185
-70,624383	8,700164	1550	1800	Medium	-250
-70,625836	8,698299	1603	1800	Medium	-197
-70,626579	8,697316	1673	1800	Medium	-127
-70,627153	8,696569	1689	1800	Medium	-111
-70,62715	8,695894	1670	1800	Medium	-130
-70,627043	8,694542	1663	1800	Medium	-137
-70,627211	8,694068	1689	1800	Medium	-111
-70,627887	8,693389	1657	1800	Medium	-143
-70,6288	8,692405	1670	1800	Medium	-130
-70,630189	8,691588	1644	1800	Medium	-156
-70,631036	8,691145	1664	1800	Medium	-136
-70,631272	8,690671	1715	1800	Medium	-85
-70,631304	8,690197	1718	1800	Medium	-82
-70,631573	8,689486	1702	1800	Medium	-98
-70,632011	8,688606	1682	1800	Medium	-118
-70,632652	8,687724	1684	1800	Medium	-116
-70,6337	8,686604	1696	1800	Medium	-104
-70,634411	8,685891	1721	1800	Medium	-79
-70,634916	8,685044	1752	1800	Medium	-48
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-70,635043	8,682914	1718	1800	Medium	-82
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-70,634901	8,681529	1688	1800	Medium	-112
-70,635001	8,681089	1647	1800	Medium	-153
-70,63534	8,680817	1647	1800	Medium	-153
-70,63585	8,680917	1603	1800	Medium	-197
-70,636361	8,681421	1618	1800	Medium	-182
-70,636908	8,682095	1680	1800	Medium	-120
-70,63759	8,682836	1657	1800	Medium	-143
-70,638444	8,683778	1708	1800	Medium	-92
-70,639092	8,684485	1665	1800	Medium	-135
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-70,639777	8,685699	1577	1800	Medium	-223
-70,640151	8,685934	1577	1800	Medium	-223
-70,640761	8,685594	1552	1800	Medium	-248
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-70,643729	8,68842	1502	1800	Medium	-298
-70,644785	8,689159	1419	1800	Medium	-381
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-70,645948	8,691013	1468	1800	Medium	-332
-70,645679	8,691487	1507	1800	Medium	-293
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-70,646292	8,692026	1533	1800	Medium	-267
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-70,64827	8,693775	1745	1800	Medium	-55
-70,648782	8,694212	1749	1800	Medium	-51
-70,64919	8,694379	1749	1800	Medium	-51
-70,650588	8,695488	1757	1800	Medium	-43
-70,650144	8,695085	1763	1800	Medium	-37
-70,625127	8,699282	1503	1800	Medium	-297
-70,630848	8,722157	1749	1800	Medium	-51
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-70,639645	8,721697	1768	1800	Medium	-32
-70,639155	8,722274	1749	1800	Medium	-51
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-70,636563	8,723941	1744	1800	Medium	-56
-70,636174	8,72423	1782	1800	Medium	-18
-70,635411	8,724571	1804	1800	Medium	4
-70,634613	8,72471	1739	1800	Medium	-61
-70,633797	8,724578	1789	1800	Medium	-11
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-70,632655	8,723687	1726	1800	Medium	-74
-70,632177	8,723098	1726	1800	Medium	-74
-70,631851	8,722373	1733	1800	Medium	-67
-70,63146	8,722239	1733	1800	Medium	-67
-70,630577	8,722344	1749	1800	Medium	-51
-70,630325	8,722971	1785	1800	Medium	-15
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-70,627142	8,725384	1747	1800	Medium	-53
-70,626753	8,725724	1738	1800	Medium	-62
-70,626246	8,726318	1726	1800	Medium	-74

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-70,624841	8,727524	1705	1800	Medium	-95
-70,624451	8,72766	1720	1800	Medium	-80
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-70,623753	8,727342	1720	1800	Medium	-80
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-70,623679	8,725855	1719	1800	Medium	-81
-70,623167	8,725351	1733	1800	Medium	-67
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-70,623316	8,724471	1704	1800	Medium	-96
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-70,624351	8,724112	1744	1800	Medium	-56
-70,624791	8,723772	1782	1800	Medium	-18
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-70,625245	8,72279	1736	1800	Medium	-64
-70,625192	8,7223	1736	1800	Medium	-64
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-70,624209	8,722625	1752	1800	Medium	-48
-70,62353	8,722831	1743	1800	Medium	-57
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-70,622507	8,721838	1734	1800	Medium	-66
-70,622352	8,721433	1734	1800	Medium	-66
-70,622063	8,721333	1729	1800	Medium	-71
-70,621656	8,721453	1729	1800	Medium	-71
-70,621334	8,721624	1729	1800	Medium	-71
-70,621044	8,721422	1722	1800	Medium	-78
-70,62043	8,720934	1787	1800	Medium	-13
-70,619698	8,720532	1756	1800	Medium	-44
-70,61895	8,720349	1781	1800	Medium	-19
-70,618338	8,720132	1747	1800	Medium	-53
-70,61793	8,720151	1747	1800	Medium	-53
-70,617591	8,720304	1723	1800	Medium	-77
-70,617185	8,720644	1685	1800	Medium	-115
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-70,616014	8,720936	1695	1800	Medium	-105
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-70,615162	8,720332	1727	1800	Medium	-73
-70,614755	8,720435	1690	1800	Medium	-110
-70,614093	8,720674	1676	1800	Medium	-124
-70,613227	8,720678	1634	1800	Medium	-166
-70,612325	8,720175	1623	1800	Medium	-177
-70,611661	8,719907	1620	1800	Medium	-180
-70,610776	8,719573	1667	1800	Medium	-133
-70,609434	8,719545	1690	1800	Medium	-110

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-70,605532	8,720508	1693	1800	Medium	-107
-70,604885	8,720206	1741	1800	Medium	-59
-70,604201	8,719195	1784	1800	Medium	-16
-70,603638	8,718606	1819	1800	Medium	19
-70,602564	8,717563	1818	1800	Medium	18
-70,602222	8,717125	1818	1800	Medium	18
-70,602236	8,716449	1849	1800	Medium	49
-70,602216	8,715688	1854	1800	Medium	54
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-70,601988	8,713948	1798	1800	Medium	-2
-70,60173	8,713341	1793	1800	Medium	-7
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-70,60164	8,711973	1683	1800	Medium	-117
-70,60225	8,711649	1674	1800	Medium	-126
-70,602845	8,711748	1674	1800	Medium	-126
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-70,642125	8,74903	1838	1800	Medium	38
-70,641805	8,749437	1879	1800	Medium	79
-70,640873	8,750067	1850	1800	Medium	50
-70,640518	8,750423	1802	1800	Medium	2
-70,639976	8,750916	1834	1800	Medium	34
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-70,638703	8,751175	1880	1800	Medium	80
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-70,63691	8,75272	1770	1800	Medium	-30
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-70,636676	8,749916	1773	1800	Medium	-27
-70,636352	8,749495	1805	1800	Medium	5
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-70,636245	8,748329	1777	1800	Medium	-23
-70,636209	8,747958	1777	1800	Medium	-23
-70,635596	8,747504	1817	1800	Medium	17
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-70,634757	8,746071	1803	1800	Medium	3
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-70,634291	8,744315	1773	1800	Medium	-27
-70,634119	8,743758	1773	1800	Medium	-27
-70,633692	8,743304	1786	1800	Medium	-14
-70,63313	8,742901	1837	1800	Medium	37
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-70,6347	8,736945	1820	1800	Medium	20
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-70,63454	8,735121	1757	1800	Medium	-43
-70,634673	8,734512	1769	1800	Medium	-31
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-70,638655	8,728444	1747	1800	Medium	-53
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-70,639293	8,726633	1753	1800	Medium	-47
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-70,641465	8,726218	1765	1800	Medium	-35
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-70,642347	8,725809	1843	1800	Medium	43
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-70,641408	8,724917	1773	1800	Medium	-27
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-70,641756	8,72282	1762	1800	Medium	-38
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-70,642275	8,721212	1779	1800	Medium	-21
-70,642461	8,72084	1779	1800	Medium	-21
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-70,642186	8,720283	1827	1800	Medium	27
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-70,640202	8,720968	1818	1800	Medium	18
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-70,642485	8,757479	1768	1800	Medium	-32
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-70,643046	8,753674	1757	1800	Medium	-43
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-70,644318	8,753263	1774	1800	Medium	-26
-70,644793	8,753092	1788	1800	Medium	-12
-70,645472	8,752937	1819	1800	Medium	19
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-70,647	8,752693	1784	1800	Medium	-16
-70,647389	8,752438	1791	1800	Medium	-9
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-70,648662	8,752044	1765	1800	Medium	-35
-70,649239	8,751923	1781	1800	Medium	-19
-70,649681	8,751938	1807	1800	Medium	7
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-70,651004	8,751662	1832	1800	Medium	32
-70,650646	8,751207	1856	1800	Medium	56
-70,650423	8,750904	1856	1800	Medium	56
-70,649897	8,750839	1832	1800	Medium	32
-70,64954	8,750975	1836	1800	Medium	36
-70,648997	8,751012	1836	1800	Medium	36
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-70,648045	8,75083	1843	1800	Medium	43
-70,647433	8,750714	1829	1800	Medium	29
-70,646515	8,750651	1820	1800	Medium	20

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-70,64464	8,749053	1797	1800	Medium	-3
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-70,644806	8,748258	1846	1800	Medium	46
-70,644518	8,748378	1862	1800	Medium	62
-70,644179	8,748633	1862	1800	Medium	62
-70,643517	8,748703	1863	1800	Medium	63
-70,642905	8,748689	1859	1800	Medium	59
-70,642413	8,748776	1838	1800	Medium	38
-70,647765	8,764402	1809	1800	Medium	9
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-70,647135	8,764067	1809	1800	Medium	9
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-70,641489	8,770395	1831	1800	Medium	31
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-70,642772	8,772519	1827	1800	Medium	27
-70,643336	8,773209	1854	1800	Medium	54
-70,643951	8,773967	1854	1800	Medium	54
-70,644531	8,774607	1885	1800	Medium	85
-70,645077	8,775027	1826	1800	Medium	26
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-70,645795	8,776156	1844	1800	Medium	44
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-70,637314	8,763619	1754	1800	Medium	-46

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-70,638529	8,765659	1836	1800	Medium	36
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-70,640033	8,767748	1801	1800	Medium	1
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-70,618365	8,757955	1766	1800	Medium	-34
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-70,625212	8,758179	1858	1800	Medium	58
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-70,626099	8,75902	1866	1800	Medium	66
-70,626407	8,759441	1808	1800	Medium	8
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-70,626601	8,76108	1903	1800	Medium	103
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-70,627308	8,763493	1808	1800	Medium	8
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-70,628125	8,767749	1776	1800	Medium	-24
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-70,596351	8,750443	1812	1800	Medium	12
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-70,597758	8,749795	1768	1800	Medium	-32
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-70,599902	8,746575	1736	1800	Medium	-64
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-70,602831	8,752258	1806	1800	Medium	6
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-70,608906	8,758603	1813	1800	Medium	13
-70,609011	8,75933	1824	1800	Medium	24
-70,609165	8,759718	1832	1800	Medium	32
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-70,609987	8,761083	1782	1800	Medium	-18
-70,610244	8,761691	1795	1800	Medium	-5
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-70,610066	8,763652	1797	1800	Medium	-3
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-70,609687	8,766442	1889	1800	Medium	89
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-70,610795	8,767333	1836	1800	Medium	36
-70,611216	8,766503	1828	1800	Medium	28
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-70,617499	8,761862	1806	1800	Medium	6
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-70,589873	8,765055	1835	1800	Medium	35
-70,590242	8,764074	1830	1800	Medium	30

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-70,591153	8,762583	1914	1800	Medium	114
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-70,59094	8,760353	1920	1800	Medium	120
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-70,590731	8,759103	1899	1800	Medium	99
-70,590523	8,758191	1869	1800	Medium	69
-70,590383	8,757279	1819	1800	Medium	19
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-70,590409	8,755352	1819	1800	Medium	19
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-70,590536	8,753324	1850	1800	Medium	50
-70,591042	8,752375	1808	1800	Medium	8
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-70,579495	8,785616	1753	1800	Medium	-47
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-70,579252	8,784536	1852	1800	Medium	52
-70,578675	8,784504	1854	1800	Medium	54
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-70,576806	8,784546	1845	1800	Medium	45
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-70,57531	8,784451	1816	1800	Medium	16
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-70,572917	8,780979	1804	1800	Medium	4
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-70,586703	8,770646	1760	1800	Medium	-40
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-70,588322	8,76807	1751	1800	Medium	-49
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-70,589726	8,788565	1816	1800	Medium	16
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-70,586883	8,787191	1769	1800	Medium	-31
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-70,592292	8,804457	1789	1800	Medium	-11
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-70,59382	8,804146	1783	1800	Medium	-17
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-70,594942	8,804378	1765	1800	Medium	-35
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-70,595929	8,804847	1790	1800	Medium	-10
-70,596439	8,804777	1758	1800	Medium	-42
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-70,597322	8,804706	1740	1800	Medium	-60
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-70,598749	8,804768	1746	1800	Medium	-54
-70,599599	8,80473	1781	1800	Medium	-19
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-70,60163	8,810907	1811	1800	Medium	11
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-70,612298	8,802682	1756	1800	Medium	-44
-70,612398	8,802276	1756	1800	Medium	-44
-70,61277	8,801868	1729	1800	Medium	-71
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-70,613309	8,800717	1768	1800	Medium	-32
-70,613511	8,800209	1780	1800	Medium	-20
-70,613271	8,799703	1780	1800	Medium	-20
-70,612896	8,799536	1820	1800	Medium	20
-70,612419	8,799166	1820	1800	Medium	20
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-70,611738	8,798966	1811	1800	Medium	11
-70,6114	8,79917	1811	1800	Medium	11
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-70,609838	8,799414	1769	1800	Medium	-31
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-70,609383	8,796542	1742	1800	Medium	-58
-70,609109	8,795868	1766	1800	Medium	-34
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-70,608826	8,793401	1783	1800	Medium	-17
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-70,608169	8,790633	1789	1800	Medium	-11
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-70,601301	8,797692	1823	1800	Medium	23
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-70,565495	8,813382	1763	1800	Medium	-37
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-70,567661	8,81289	1728	1800	Medium	-72
-70,56826	8,813032	1804	1800	Medium	4
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-70,575071	8,812585	1774	1800	Medium	-26
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-70,581717	8,811688	1775	1800	Medium	-25
-70,581165	8,811127	1749	1800	Medium	-51
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-70,581044	8,809422	1738	1800	Medium	-62
-70,581347	8,808294	1782	1800	Medium	-18
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-70,583378	8,806482	1784	1800	Medium	-16
-70,584025	8,806351	1784	1800	Medium	-16
-70,584752	8,80601	1758	1800	Medium	-42

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-70,585909	8,804315	1727	1800	Medium	-73
-70,586231	8,803782	1727	1800	Medium	-73
-70,58686	8,803474	1720	1800	Medium	-80
-70,587313	8,803456	1756	1800	Medium	-44
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-70,699208	8,719226	2020	2000	Medium	20
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-70,699051	8,72045	2022	2000	Medium	22
-70,698893	8,721223	2022	2000	Medium	22
-70,698604	8,721707	1977	2000	Medium	-23
-70,698153	8,722128	2027	2000	Medium	27
-70,697508	8,722678	1976	2000	Medium	-24
-70,697316	8,723129	2029	2000	Medium	29
-70,697254	8,723612	2029	2000	Medium	29
-70,69716	8,724353	2065	2000	Medium	65
-70,697033	8,724804	1983	2000	Medium	-17
-70,696907	8,725513	2008	2000	Medium	8
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-70,696748	8,726222	2008	2000	Medium	8
-70,696621	8,726673	2017	2000	Medium	17
-70,696269	8,727544	2025	2000	Medium	25
-70,696174	8,728124	1966	2000	Medium	-34
-70,696273	8,728478	2031	2000	Medium	31
-70,696275	8,728993	2041	2000	Medium	41
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-70,69534	8,729737	2011	2000	Medium	11
-70,694922	8,730351	2011	2000	Medium	11
-70,694537	8,730932	2016	2000	Medium	16
-70,694116	8,730934	2016	2000	Medium	16
-70,693856	8,730677	2016	2000	Medium	16
-70,693692	8,730163	2002	2000	Medium	2
-70,69356	8,729552	2064	2000	Medium	64
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-70,705645	8,711987	2064	2000	Medium	64
-70,705607	8,710731	2046	2000	Medium	46
-70,705669	8,710055	2023	2000	Medium	23

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-70,70492	8,7089	2025	2000	Medium	25
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-70,703228	8,706879	1996	2000	Medium	-4
-70,702773	8,706431	2037	2000	Medium	37
-70,70219	8,706208	1966	2000	Medium	-34
-70,701317	8,706308	2064	2000	Medium	64
-70,700863	8,70615	1995	2000	Medium	-5
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-70,699988	8,705832	1987	2000	Medium	-13
-70,699537	8,706188	1956	2000	Medium	-44
-70,699021	8,706576	1999	2000	Medium	-1
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-70,697281	8,708129	2064	2000	Medium	64
-70,696734	8,708679	1999	2000	Medium	-1
-70,695734	8,709391	2027	2000	Medium	27
-70,695153	8,709684	2097	2000	Medium	97
-70,694344	8,709655	2060	2000	Medium	60
-70,693502	8,709595	2068	2000	Medium	68
-70,692434	8,709503	1943	2000	Medium	-57
-70,691658	8,709442	1944	2000	Medium	-56
-70,691237	8,709508	1944	2000	Medium	-56
-70,69043	8,709801	2104	2000	Medium	104
-70,689784	8,709997	2070	2000	Medium	70
-70,688879	8,710195	2038	2000	Medium	38
-70,6882	8,710423	2063	2000	Medium	63
-70,687458	8,710812	2027	2000	Medium	27
-70,68704	8,711426	1982	2000	Medium	-18
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-70,687209	8,713067	2058	2000	Medium	58
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-70,688221	8,714962	2000	2000	Medium	0
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-70,689803	8,714279	2075	2000	Medium	75
-70,690611	8,714178	2047	2000	Medium	47
-70,691615	8,71427	2076	2000	Medium	76
-70,692101	8,714429	2158	2000	Medium	158
-70,692878	8,714555	2158	2000	Medium	158
-70,693558	8,714648	1997	2000	Medium	-3
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-70,695857	8,715121	2071	2000	Medium	71
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-70,709372	8,706176	2057	2000	Medium	57
-70,708658	8,705761	1990	2000	Medium	-10
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-70,711252	8,707069	2119	2000	Medium	119
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-70,71339	8,707735	2087	2000	Medium	87
-70,713975	8,708215	2063	2000	Medium	63
-70,714073	8,708504	2063	2000	Medium	63
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-70,708208	8,713391	2039	2000	Medium	39
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-70,708279	8,714807	2009	2000	Medium	9
-70,7088	8,715545	2053	2000	Medium	53
-70,709288	8,716251	2006	2000	Medium	6
-70,709679	8,716926	2074	2000	Medium	74
-70,709908	8,717472	2024	2000	Medium	24
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-70,706335	8,714269	2041	2000	Medium	41
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-70,709054	8,693237	2043	2000	Medium	43
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-70,709349	8,694137	2017	2000	Medium	17
-70,709708	8,694779	2060	2000	Medium	60
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-70,709584	8,695874	2068	2000	Medium	68
-70,709295	8,696326	2049	2000	Medium	49
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-70,708427	8,697682	2003	2000	Medium	3
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-70,707725	8,699842	2020	2000	Medium	20
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-70,686355	8,673928	2082	2000	Medium	82
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-70,687585	8,674115	2085	2000	Medium	85
-70,688072	8,674467	2096	2000	Medium	96
-70,688269	8,675175	2069	2000	Medium	69
-70,688627	8,67572	2054	2000	Medium	54
-70,689112	8,675686	2075	2000	Medium	75
-70,689405	8,676039	2075	2000	Medium	75
-70,689342	8,67649	2057	2000	Medium	57
-70,689021	8,676942	2057	2000	Medium	57
-70,688669	8,67778	2020	2000	Medium	20
-70,688156	8,678845	2067	2000	Medium	67
-70,688191	8,679488	2067	2000	Medium	67
-70,688031	8,679908	2075	2000	Medium	75

-70,68784	8,680584	1999	2000	Medium	-1
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-70,687685	8,682098	2026	2000	Medium	26
-70,68772	8,682742	2026	2000	Medium	26
-70,687787	8,683192	2036	2000	Medium	36
-70,68779	8,6839	2033	2000	Medium	33
-70,687502	8,684578	2033	2000	Medium	33
-70,687116	8,685094	2054	2000	Medium	54
-70,686926	8,685996	1992	2000	Medium	-8
-70,686897	8,686737	2031	2000	Medium	31
-70,68677	8,687188	2053	2000	Medium	53
-70,68674	8,687736	2053	2000	Medium	53
-70,686968	8,688089	2027	2000	Medium	27
-70,687099	8,688539	2096	2000	Medium	96
-70,687038	8,689215	1985	2000	Medium	-15
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-70,686624	8,690665	2042	2000	Medium	42
-70,686723	8,691116	2042	2000	Medium	42
-70,68721	8,691564	2083	2000	Medium	83
-70,687857	8,691626	2083	2000	Medium	83
-70,688375	8,691752	2118	2000	Medium	118
-70,688831	8,692265	2061	2000	Medium	61
-70,689189	8,692778	2061	2000	Medium	61
-70,68945	8,693357	1996	2000	Medium	-4
-70,689193	8,693809	1995	2000	Medium	-5
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-70,689139	8,695998	2015	2000	Medium	15
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-70,690695	8,696763	2056	2000	Medium	56
-70,691375	8,696921	2064	2000	Medium	64
-70,692379	8,697239	2010	2000	Medium	10
-70,693287	8,697653	2027	2000	Medium	27
-70,693934	8,697618	2013	2000	Medium	13
-70,694838	8,697163	1981	2000	Medium	-19
-70,695548	8,696806	2003	2000	Medium	3
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-70,69651	8,694903	2165	2000	Medium	165
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-70,698062	8,694864	2096	2000	Medium	96
-70,698712	8,695408	2096	2000	Medium	96
-70,699233	8,696242	2022	2000	Medium	22
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-70,700208	8,697204	1974	2000	Medium	-26
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-70,703338	8,695355	2107	2000	Medium	107
-70,704466	8,694416	2131	2000	Medium	131
-70,704949	8,693931	2080	2000	Medium	80
-70,705496	8,693253	2078	2000	Medium	78
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-70,70917	8,690179	2092	2000	Medium	92
-70,70927	8,69079	2033	2000	Medium	33
-70,708916	8,691371	2059	2000	Medium	59
-70,708919	8,691982	2059	2000	Medium	59
-70,708922	8,692562	2073	2000	Medium	73
-70,676505	8,67777	2061	2000	Medium	61
-70,677376	8,677154	2050	2000	Medium	50
-70,678021	8,676668	2094	2000	Medium	94
-70,678634	8,67644	2094	2000	Medium	94
-70,679573	8,676501	2072	2000	Medium	72
-70,679993	8,676338	2049	2000	Medium	49
-70,680896	8,675851	2103	2000	Medium	103
-70,681705	8,675751	2061	2000	Medium	61
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-70,676158	8,665217	2040	2000	Medium	40
-70,676645	8,66544	2075	2000	Medium	75
-70,67726	8,665534	2097	2000	Medium	97
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-70,677943	8,6664	2109	2000	Medium	109
-70,678333	8,666753	2109	2000	Medium	109
-70,678722	8,667041	2109	2000	Medium	109
-70,679178	8,667618	2121	2000	Medium	121
-70,67931	8,668229	2068	2000	Medium	68
-70,679603	8,668711	2108	2000	Medium	108
-70,679799	8,669128	2093	2000	Medium	93
-70,679639	8,669515	2093	2000	Medium	93
-70,67922	8,669903	2036	2000	Medium	36
-70,678736	8,670099	1987	2000	Medium	-13
-70,678155	8,67052	1998	2000	Medium	-2
-70,67751	8,670941	1977	2000	Medium	-23
-70,677253	8,671393	2025	2000	Medium	25
-70,677095	8,672134	2062	2000	Medium	62
-70,677001	8,672778	1990	2000	Medium	-10
-70,677004	8,673486	2007	2000	Medium	7

-70,676844	8,673873	2033	2000	Medium	33
-70,67636	8,674294	2033	2000	Medium	33
-70,675943	8,674972	1987	2000	Medium	-13
-70,675946	8,675583	2000	2000	Medium	0
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-70,675952	8,677096	1999	2000	Medium	-1
-70,675663	8,677612	1999	2000	Medium	-1
-70,674987	8,678356	1971	2000	Medium	-29
-70,674568	8,678647	1941	2000	Medium	-59
-70,674343	8,679035	1996	2000	Medium	-4
-70,674635	8,679162	2031	2000	Medium	31
-70,675184	8,678902	2031	2000	Medium	31
-70,675893	8,67832	2029	2000	Medium	29
-70,679304	8,65957	1702	2000	Medium	-298
-70,678689	8,659637	1784	2000	Medium	-216
-70,678042	8,659608	1784	2000	Medium	-216
-70,677395	8,659482	1795	2000	Medium	-205
-70,676877	8,659484	1830	2000	Medium	-170
-70,676393	8,659679	1850	2000	Medium	-150
-70,676039	8,660131	1881	2000	Medium	-119
-70,676202	8,660517	1932	2000	Medium	-68
-70,676366	8,66087	1907	2000	Medium	-93
-70,676368	8,661353	1959	2000	Medium	-41
-70,676242	8,662062	1990	2000	Medium	-10
-70,676115	8,662739	2035	2000	Medium	35
-70,675922	8,662965	2052	2000	Medium	52
-70,675632	8,663288	2052	2000	Medium	52
-70,67544	8,663643	2052	2000	Medium	52
-70,675442	8,66419	2040	2000	Medium	40
-70,69271	8,720366	1995	2000	Medium	-5
-70,693002	8,720686	2009	2000	Medium	9
-70,69307	8,721265	2042	2000	Medium	42
-70,693106	8,722102	2043	2000	Medium	43
-70,69285	8,722779	2131	2000	Medium	131
-70,692627	8,723649	2140	2000	Medium	140
-70,692501	8,72439	2111	2000	Medium	111
-70,692439	8,724905	2129	2000	Medium	129
-70,69244	8,725195	2129	2000	Medium	129
-70,692704	8,726321	2164	2000	Medium	164
-70,692934	8,727124	2085	2000	Medium	85
-70,693393	8,728346	2083	2000	Medium	83
-70,67428	8,715812	2110	2000	Medium	110
-70,674154	8,716392	2133	2000	Medium	133
-70,674092	8,717165	2089	2000	Medium	89
-70,674255	8,717454	2089	2000	Medium	89

-70,674483	8,71771	2089	2000	Medium	89
-70,674744	8,71816	2044	2000	Medium	44
-70,674681	8,718643	2044	2000	Medium	44
-70,674812	8,718868	2043	2000	Medium	43
-70,675138	8,719381	2043	2000	Medium	43
-70,675011	8,719961	2065	2000	Medium	65
-70,674789	8,721024	2078	2000	Medium	78
-70,674919	8,721249	2078	2000	Medium	78
-70,675309	8,721537	2030	2000	Medium	30
-70,675763	8,721793	2009	2000	Medium	9
-70,67583	8,722372	2023	2000	Medium	23
-70,675542	8,72292	1974	2000	Medium	-26
-70,675189	8,723662	2059	2000	Medium	59
-70,674869	8,724468	2057	2000	Medium	57
-70,67458	8,725049	2146	2000	Medium	146
-70,674423	8,725919	2090	2000	Medium	90
-70,67462	8,726594	1986	2000	Medium	-14
-70,674848	8,726979	1986	2000	Medium	-14
-70,675203	8,726913	1986	2000	Medium	-14
-70,67572	8,726654	1988	2000	Medium	-12
-70,676205	8,726619	1988	2000	Medium	-12
-70,676592	8,726328	2050	2000	Medium	50
-70,677299	8,725295	1999	2000	Medium	-1
-70,677973	8,724101	2004	2000	Medium	4
-70,679004	8,723098	2019	2000	Medium	19
-70,679937	8,721871	1996	2000	Medium	-4
-70,680646	8,721192	2002	2000	Medium	2
-70,681227	8,72106	2002	2000	Medium	2
-70,681746	8,721251	2066	2000	Medium	66
-70,682234	8,721764	2035	2000	Medium	35
-70,682591	8,722084	2090	2000	Medium	90
-70,683141	8,722146	2079	2000	Medium	79
-70,683692	8,722401	2079	2000	Medium	79
-70,684082	8,722786	2049	2000	Medium	49
-70,684635	8,723395	2110	2000	Medium	110
-70,685154	8,723618	2110	2000	Medium	110
-70,685736	8,72368	2048	2000	Medium	48
-70,686221	8,723452	2048	2000	Medium	48
-70,686963	8,722966	2072	2000	Medium	72
-70,687673	8,722673	1927	2000	Medium	-73
-70,688482	8,722605	1972	2000	Medium	-28
-70,689451	8,722376	2030	2000	Medium	30
-70,690032	8,722116	2077	2000	Medium	77
-70,690773	8,721436	2020	2000	Medium	20
-70,69158	8,720918	2003	2000	Medium	3
-70,692193	8,720625	2048	2000	Medium	48

-70,650605	8,702782	1961	2000	Medium	-39
-70,650608	8,703458	1991	2000	Medium	-9
-70,650741	8,704165	2018	2000	Medium	18
-70,651001	8,704454	2018	2000	Medium	18
-70,651486	8,704291	1987	2000	Medium	-13
-70,651841	8,704193	1987	2000	Medium	-13
-70,652391	8,704255	1945	2000	Medium	-55
-70,652653	8,70493	2002	2000	Medium	2
-70,652626	8,706056	2016	2000	Medium	16
-70,652822	8,706603	2012	2000	Medium	12
-70,652986	8,707182	1937	2000	Medium	-63
-70,65273	8,707827	2004	2000	Medium	4
-70,652377	8,708343	1990	2000	Medium	-10
-70,651959	8,709021	1999	2000	Medium	-1
-70,651799	8,709344	1999	2000	Medium	-1
-70,652221	8,709631	2031	2000	Medium	31
-70,652932	8,709467	1984	2000	Medium	-16
-70,653416	8,709176	1984	2000	Medium	-16
-70,654093	8,708786	1998	2000	Medium	-2
-70,654644	8,708816	1973	2000	Medium	-27
-70,65526	8,7092	1973	2000	Medium	-27
-70,655747	8,709552	1924	2000	Medium	-76
-70,656331	8,710032	1841	2000	Medium	-159
-70,656851	8,710448	1883	2000	Medium	-117
-70,657694	8,710799	1891	2000	Medium	-109
-70,658147	8,710861	1863	2000	Medium	-137
-70,658828	8,711244	1897	2000	Medium	-103
-70,659477	8,71166	1929	2000	Medium	-71
-70,660122	8,711303	1989	2000	Medium	-11
-70,661057	8,710526	2033	2000	Medium	33
-70,661863	8,709976	1971	2000	Medium	-29
-70,662671	8,70965	1981	2000	Medium	-19
-70,663737	8,709259	1932	2000	Medium	-68
-70,664352	8,709353	1941	2000	Medium	-59
-70,66471	8,70977	1929	2000	Medium	-71
-70,664974	8,710992	1951	2000	Medium	-49
-70,665042	8,711829	1969	2000	Medium	-31
-70,665175	8,712504	2014	2000	Medium	14
-70,665404	8,713179	2054	2000	Medium	54
-70,665862	8,714336	1940	2000	Medium	-60
-70,666157	8,715236	2006	2000	Medium	6
-70,666773	8,715555	2064	2000	Medium	64
-70,667162	8,715554	2038	2000	Medium	38
-70,667808	8,715325	1971	2000	Medium	-29
-70,668679	8,714935	1990	2000	Medium	-10
-70,669388	8,714288	1984	2000	Medium	-16

-70,67013	8,713673	1969	2000	Medium	-31
-70,67129	8,712638	2007	2000	Medium	7
-70,671902	8,712056	1968	2000	Medium	-32
-70,672287	8,711411	2011	2000	Medium	11
-70,672771	8,711022	1978	2000	Medium	-22
-70,673323	8,711535	2039	2000	Medium	39
-70,673423	8,712146	2075	2000	Medium	75
-70,673685	8,712885	2075	2000	Medium	75
-70,674207	8,713945	2080	2000	Medium	80
-70,674696	8,714619	2036	2000	Medium	36
-70,674666	8,715199	2036	2000	Medium	36
-70,636466	8,689347	1790	2000	Medium	-210
-70,637272	8,688764	1719	2000	Medium	-281
-70,638082	8,689018	1729	2000	Medium	-271
-70,638666	8,689434	1729	2000	Medium	-271
-70,638957	8,689336	1733	2000	Medium	-267
-70,639571	8,689237	1733	2000	Medium	-267
-70,640186	8,689267	1718	2000	Medium	-282
-70,640804	8,690198	1702	2000	Medium	-298
-70,641423	8,691064	1673	2000	Medium	-327
-70,642753	8,691863	1662	2000	Medium	-338
-70,642072	8,691576	1705	2000	Medium	-295
-70,643402	8,692472	1653	2000	Medium	-347
-70,644085	8,693113	1646	2000	Medium	-354
-70,644734	8,693561	1631	2000	Medium	-369
-70,645804	8,694296	1692	2000	Medium	-308
-70,646552	8,695001	1772	2000	Medium	-228
-70,647233	8,695449	1833	2000	Medium	-167
-70,647817	8,695865	1833	2000	Medium	-167
-70,648304	8,69612	1860	2000	Medium	-140
-70,649081	8,696407	1876	2000	Medium	-124
-70,649374	8,696856	1876	2000	Medium	-124
-70,649474	8,697499	1913	2000	Medium	-87
-70,64938	8,698144	1938	2000	Medium	-62
-70,649222	8,699046	1916	2000	Medium	-84
-70,648903	8,699948	1930	2000	Medium	-70
-70,64881	8,700915	1966	2000	Medium	-34
-70,649006	8,701332	1979	2000	Medium	-21
-70,649395	8,701652	1979	2000	Medium	-21
-70,650142	8,702229	2006	2000	Medium	6
-70,634972	8,703067	1985	2600	High	-615
-70,635488	8,702582	2019	2600	High	-581
-70,636003	8,702032	2007	2600	High	-593
-70,636714	8,701739	2061	2600	High	-539
-70,637521	8,70135	2185	2600	High	-415
-70,638296	8,701057	2147	2600	High	-453

-70,639072	8,700989	2102	2600	High	-498
-70,639621	8,700793	2065	2600	High	-535
-70,640397	8,700532	2065	2600	High	-535
-70,641432	8,700625	2027	2600	High	-573
-70,641823	8,701234	2027	2600	High	-573
-70,642118	8,702135	2166	2600	High	-434
-70,642089	8,702843	2166	2600	High	-434
-70,642092	8,703648	2221	2600	High	-379
-70,642128	8,704452	2278	2600	High	-322
-70,642227	8,704935	2347	2600	High	-253
-70,64278	8,705447	2432	2600	High	-168
-70,643202	8,705832	2451	2600	High	-149
-70,643819	8,706376	2491	2600	High	-109
-70,644306	8,706857	2491	2600	High	-109
-70,644762	8,707467	2484	2600	High	-116
-70,644765	8,708143	2501	2600	High	-99
-70,644251	8,709046	2567	2600	High	-33
-70,64338	8,709565	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,642507	8,709794	2533	2600	High	-67
-70,64183	8,710216	2568	2600	High	-32
-70,641508	8,710475	2515	2600	High	-85
-70,64083	8,710864	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,640378	8,711059	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,639762	8,710933	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,63892	8,710743	2565	2600	High	-35
-70,638403	8,710745	2569	2600	High	-31
-70,637562	8,710846	2545	2600	High	-55
-70,636948	8,710945	2519	2600	High	-81
-70,636204	8,711045	2502	2600	High	-98
-70,635557	8,710983	2502	2600	High	-98
-70,634812	8,710793	2455	2600	High	-145
-70,634389	8,710376	2348	2600	High	-252
-70,634095	8,709605	2348	2600	High	-252
-70,633705	8,709253	2250	2600	High	-350
-70,633186	8,708804	2250	2600	High	-350
-70,632536	8,708356	2154	2600	High	-446
-70,631889	8,708295	2131	2600	High	-469
-70,631274	8,708297	2131	2600	High	-469
-70,630788	8,707945	2111	2600	High	-489
-70,630624	8,707528	2033	2600	High	-567
-70,631075	8,707139	2033	2600	High	-567
-70,631688	8,706654	2015	2600	High	-585
-70,632493	8,705781	2033	2600	High	-567
-70,63346	8,704876	2036	2600	High	-564
-70,634522	8,703745	1927	2600	High	-673
-70,635295	8,702904	1957	2600	High	-643

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-70,63845	8,706625	2373	2800	High	-427
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-70,639034	8,707202	2472	2800	High	-328
-70,638874	8,707524	2472	2800	High	-328
-70,638486	8,707623	2426	2800	High	-374
-70,637904	8,707593	2365	2800	High	-435
-70,637482	8,707402	2365	2800	High	-435
-70,637416	8,706951	2301	2800	High	-499
-70,632316	8,702273	1862	2400	High	-538
-70,632798	8,701563	1804	2400	High	-596
-70,633346	8,70111	1830	2400	High	-570
-70,633862	8,700593	1895	2400	High	-505
-70,634151	8,700076	1890	2400	High	-510
-70,634698	8,699591	1952	2400	High	-448
-70,635213	8,698849	1953	2400	High	-447
-70,635695	8,698235	2045	2400	High	-355
-70,636596	8,696943	2130	2400	High	-270
-70,637112	8,696619	2139	2400	High	-261
-70,637985	8,696455	2114	2400	High	-286
-70,638827	8,696676	2087	2400	High	-313
-70,639411	8,696996	2087	2400	High	-313
-70,639993	8,697025	2052	2400	High	-348
-70,640609	8,69728	2005	2400	High	-395
-70,640998	8,697568	2005	2400	High	-395
-70,64155	8,697984	1917	2400	High	-483
-70,642037	8,698272	1917	2400	High	-483
-70,642717	8,69843	1890	2400	High	-510
-70,643074	8,698654	1886	2400	High	-514
-70,643624	8,698748	1886	2400	High	-514
-70,644144	8,699196	1920	2400	High	-480
-70,644341	8,699968	1972	2400	High	-428
-70,644473	8,700579	2037	2400	High	-363
-70,644282	8,701159	2037	2400	High	-363
-70,644058	8,70174	2099	2400	High	-301
-70,644061	8,702609	2185	2400	High	-215
-70,644033	8,703414	2264	2400	High	-136
-70,644165	8,704186	2341	2400	High	-59
-70,644458	8,704507	2341	2400	High	-59
-70,645107	8,705051	2365	2400	High	-35
-70,645529	8,705403	2298	2400	High	-102
-70,645952	8,705852	2359	2400	High	-41
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-70,646863	8,70691	2348	2400	High	-52
-70,647189	8,707617	2335	2400	High	-65
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-70,647295	8,709613	2307	2400	High	-93
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-70,646202	8,711259	2391	2400	High	-9
-70,645331	8,711907	2411	2400	High	11
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-70,643004	8,712432	2350	2400	High	-50
-70,64226	8,712499	2361	2400	High	-39
-70,64129	8,712632	2403	2400	High	3
-70,64029	8,713152	2359	2400	High	-41
-70,639837	8,713218	2359	2400	High	-41
-70,639029	8,713286	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,638512	8,713546	2403	2400	High	3
-70,637899	8,713838	2357	2400	High	-43
-70,637122	8,713777	2357	2400	High	-43
-70,636086	8,713749	2369	2400	High	-31
-70,635341	8,713527	2348	2400	High	-52
-70,634564	8,713402	2341	2400	High	-59
-70,633592	8,713116	2341	2400	High	-59
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-70,62954	8,711202	2215	2400	High	-185
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-70,628824	8,710143	2158	2400	High	-242
-70,628531	8,70979	2127	2400	High	-273
-70,627753	8,709471	2048	2400	High	-352
-70,627362	8,708797	2048	2400	High	-352
-70,626972	8,708412	1966	2400	High	-434
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-70,625674	8,707549	1889	2400	High	-511
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-70,626834	8,706514	1795	2400	High	-605
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-70,632042	8,706331	2015	2400	High	-385
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-70,643813	8,712299	2362	2400	High	-38

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-70,625139	8,703495	1607	2000	Medium	-393
-70,626106	8,702718	1595	2000	Medium	-405
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-70,627583	8,700105	1590	2000	Medium	-410
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-70,628836	8,697942	1686	2000	Medium	-314
-70,62948	8,697232	1732	2000	Medium	-268
-70,630189	8,696681	1769	2000	Medium	-231
-70,630446	8,69639	1781	2000	Medium	-219
-70,63054	8,695585	1834	2000	Medium	-166
-70,630764	8,695101	1837	2000	Medium	-163
-70,630924	8,694521	1801	2000	Medium	-199
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-70,631856	8,693101	1808	2000	Medium	-192
-70,633082	8,692452	1895	2000	Medium	-105
-70,633566	8,692192	1895	2000	Medium	-105
-70,633629	8,691613	1857	2000	Medium	-143
-70,633755	8,690968	1864	2000	Medium	-136
-70,634238	8,690419	1864	2000	Medium	-136
-70,635079	8,690287	1855	2000	Medium	-145
-70,635726	8,690316	1835	2000	Medium	-165
-70,63608	8,689896	1835	2000	Medium	-165
-70,621833	8,716997	1981	2000	Medium	-19
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-70,619243	8,716686	1959	2000	Medium	-41
-70,618982	8,716205	1984	2000	Medium	-16
-70,618882	8,715529	1984	2000	Medium	-16
-70,618976	8,714853	1980	2000	Medium	-20
-70,619103	8,714176	1941	2000	Medium	-59
-70,619166	8,713789	1941	2000	Medium	-59
-70,618615	8,713534	1922	2000	Medium	-78
-70,617903	8,713634	1891	2000	Medium	-109
-70,617416	8,713282	1891	2000	Medium	-109
-70,617028	8,713155	1871	2000	Medium	-129
-70,616543	8,71335	1871	2000	Medium	-129
-70,616286	8,713705	1871	2000	Medium	-129
-70,616029	8,714157	1839	2000	Medium	-161
-70,615966	8,714576	1839	2000	Medium	-161

-70,615742	8,715156	1844	2000	Medium	-156
-70,615452	8,715511	1843	2000	Medium	-157
-70,614872	8,716029	1803	2000	Medium	-197
-70,614	8,716258	1786	2000	Medium	-214
-70,613579	8,716292	1758	2000	Medium	-242
-70,612674	8,71636	1760	2000	Medium	-240
-70,611929	8,716363	1767	2000	Medium	-233
-70,611346	8,716108	1806	2000	Medium	-194
-70,610827	8,715789	1813	2000	Medium	-187
-70,610471	8,715694	1813	2000	Medium	-187
-70,609338	8,715731	1862	2000	Medium	-138
-70,608659	8,715669	1860	2000	Medium	-140
-70,608045	8,7158	1860	2000	Medium	-140
-70,607753	8,715705	1853	2000	Medium	-147
-70,609889	8,715857	1835	2000	Medium	-165
-70,607461	8,715449	1853	2000	Medium	-147
-70,607555	8,714837	1900	2000	Medium	-100
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-70,608131	8,713353	1926	2000	Medium	-74
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-70,610838	8,710702	1997	2000	Medium	-3
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-70,614223	8,70792	1986	2000	Medium	-14
-70,614414	8,707275	1945	2000	Medium	-55
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-70,615578	8,707012	1835	2000	Medium	-165
-70,616064	8,707171	1893	2000	Medium	-107
-70,616421	8,707621	1859	2000	Medium	-141
-70,616715	8,708199	1905	2000	Medium	-95
-70,617103	8,708197	1929	2000	Medium	-71
-70,617586	8,70768	1891	2000	Medium	-109
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-70,619779	8,7059	1864	2000	Medium	-136
-70,620231	8,705802	1864	2000	Medium	-136
-70,62091	8,705702	1817	2000	Medium	-183
-70,621234	8,705669	1817	2000	Medium	-183
-70,62175	8,705409	1779	2000	Medium	-221
-70,622718	8,704857	1728	2000	Medium	-272
-70,623267	8,704437	1665	2000	Medium	-335

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-70,639818	8,730987	2031	2000	Medium	31
-70,639847	8,730279	1894	2000	Medium	-106
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-70,640391	8,728892	1863	2000	Medium	-137
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-70,641104	8,729115	1930	2000	Medium	-70
-70,641462	8,729596	2067	2000	Medium	67
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-70,642716	8,727949	2016	2000	Medium	16
-70,642939	8,727143	2058	2000	Medium	58
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-70,64508	8,720953	1944	2000	Medium	-56
-70,645628	8,720468	1994	2000	Medium	-6
-70,64608	8,720305	1944	2000	Medium	-56
-70,646176	8,720047	1944	2000	Medium	-56
-70,646044	8,719533	1910	2000	Medium	-90
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-70,646525	8,718533	1956	2000	Medium	-44
-70,646879	8,717984	1956	2000	Medium	-44
-70,647135	8,717307	1993	2000	Medium	-7
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-70,64587	8,716572	2011	2000	Medium	11
-70,645514	8,716734	2011	2000	Medium	11
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-70,644384	8,71719	2005	2000	Medium	5
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-70,640669	8,718461	1987	2000	Medium	-13
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-70,639633	8,718401	1972	2000	Medium	-28
-70,639374	8,718403	2006	2000	Medium	6
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-70,63747	8,719473	1990	2000	Medium	-10
-70,637082	8,719507	2023	2000	Medium	23
-70,636518	8,719912	1967	2000	Medium	-33
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-70,634957	8,72193	1952	2000	Medium	-48
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-70,63439	8,721595	1908	2000	Medium	-92
-70,633886	8,721002	1933	2000	Medium	-67
-70,633592	8,720391	1937	2000	Medium	-63
-70,633153	8,720055	1937	2000	Medium	-63
-70,632602	8,719768	1926	2000	Medium	-74
-70,632117	8,719818	1926	2000	Medium	-74
-70,63176	8,719546	1967	2000	Medium	-33
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-70,630208	8,719665	1903	2000	Medium	-97
-70,629786	8,719458	1945	2000	Medium	-55
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-70,628358	8,718482	1883	2000	Medium	-117
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-70,624359	8,717598	1904	2000	Medium	-96
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-70,623019	8,718183	1872	2000	Medium	-128
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-70,622013	8,717544	1945	2000	Medium	-55
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-70,647883	8,747852	1948	2000	Medium	-52
-70,647754	8,747756	1948	2000	Medium	-52
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-70,644827	8,744389	2043	2000	Medium	43
-70,645024	8,745193	2027	2000	Medium	27
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-70,623943	8,763536	2125	2000	Medium	125
-70,624108	8,764179	2124	2000	Medium	124
-70,62453	8,764628	2111	2000	Medium	111
-70,625017	8,765077	2047	2000	Medium	47
-70,625408	8,765622	2059	2000	Medium	59
-70,625702	8,766329	2024	2000	Medium	24
-70,625706	8,767102	2018	2000	Medium	18
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-70,627405	8,770796	1860	2000	Medium	-140
-70,627666	8,771342	1896	2000	Medium	-104
-70,628121	8,771759	1939	2000	Medium	-61
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-70,629153	8,771014	1955	2000	Medium	-45
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-70,630604	8,769817	2000	2000	Medium	0
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-70,632087	8,768716	1981	2000	Medium	-19
-70,632894	8,768101	1981	2000	Medium	-19
-70,633605	8,767872	1951	2000	Medium	-49
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-70,63428	8,766936	1953	2000	Medium	-47
-70,634601	8,766419	2009	2000	Medium	9

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-70,635771	8,767573	2063	2000	Medium	63
-70,635806	8,768152	2066	2000	Medium	66
-70,636002	8,768538	2066	2000	Medium	66
-70,636651	8,768921	2024	2000	Medium	24
-70,637169	8,769016	2005	2000	Medium	5
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-70,590021	8,768702	1904	2000	Medium	-96
-70,590471	8,768056	1976	2000	Medium	-24
-70,591243	8,766926	1845	2000	Medium	-155
-70,591628	8,766152	1901	2000	Medium	-99
-70,591754	8,765379	1945	2000	Medium	-55
-70,592075	8,76467	1945	2000	Medium	-55
-70,592525	8,763927	2097	2000	Medium	97
-70,593007	8,763056	2144	2000	Medium	144
-70,593133	8,762444	2131	2000	Medium	131
-70,593033	8,761575	2136	2000	Medium	136
-70,59277	8,760611	2061	2000	Medium	61
-70,592636	8,759581	2055	2000	Medium	55
-70,592794	8,758711	2040	2000	Medium	40
-70,592951	8,757713	2131	2000	Medium	131
-70,592884	8,757005	2085	2000	Medium	85
-70,592814	8,755814	2042	2000	Medium	42
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-70,59352	8,754427	2064	2000	Medium	64
-70,594875	8,753455	1982	2000	Medium	-18
-70,596005	8,752968	1976	2000	Medium	-24
-70,596781	8,752739	1925	2000	Medium	-75
-70,597298	8,752511	1908	2000	Medium	-92
-70,597946	8,752766	1881	2000	Medium	-119
-70,598207	8,75328	1887	2000	Medium	-113
-70,598338	8,75373	1887	2000	Medium	-113
-70,598566	8,753955	1912	2000	Medium	-88
-70,598924	8,754468	1843	2000	Medium	-157
-70,59941	8,754724	1899	2000	Medium	-101
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-70,600835	8,754943	1958	2000	Medium	-42
-70,601449	8,754876	1959	2000	Medium	-41
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-70,602325	8,755259	1950	2000	Medium	-50
-70,602392	8,755902	1998	2000	Medium	-2
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-70,602235	8,756933	2036	2000	Medium	36
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-70,602242	8,758639	2008	2000	Medium	8
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-70,602896	8,760149	2051	2000	Medium	51
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-70,604708	8,760303	1933	2000	Medium	-67
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-70,605967	8,759621	1973	2000	Medium	-27
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-70,607051	8,763383	2055	2000	Medium	55
-70,606924	8,763931	2075	2000	Medium	75
-70,606604	8,76464	2066	2000	Medium	66
-70,606509	8,765091	2066	2000	Medium	66
-70,606254	8,766155	2024	2000	Medium	24
-70,606354	8,766766	2027	2000	Medium	27
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-70,607624	8,76866	2065	2000	Medium	65
-70,608306	8,769108	2030	2000	Medium	30
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-70,609645	8,771935	1958	2000	Medium	-42
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-70,612874	8,770504	1970	2000	Medium	-30
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-70,613904	8,76918	1973	2000	Medium	-27
-70,61439	8,769339	1973	2000	Medium	-27
-70,61494	8,769208	1981	2000	Medium	-19
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-70,616091	8,766177	1949	2000	Medium	-51
-70,616573	8,765402	1945	2000	Medium	-55
-70,617637	8,764497	1934	2000	Medium	-66
-70,618284	8,764268	1964	2000	Medium	-36
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-70,619797	8,762685	1977	2000	Medium	-23
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-70,622305	8,75894	2025	2000	Medium	25
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-70,623344	8,759676	2072	2000	Medium	72
-70,623541	8,760319	2072	2000	Medium	72
-70,623773	8,761605	2100	2000	Medium	100
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-70,594165	8,753941	2044	2000	Medium	44
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-70,593441	8,789	1958	2000	Medium	-42
-70,592921	8,788552	2005	2000	Medium	5
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-70,590875	8,786919	1989	2000	Medium	-11
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-70,589804	8,786118	2003	2000	Medium	3
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-70,586648	8,782108	2034	2000	Medium	34
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-70,586393	8,782882	2034	2000	Medium	34
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-70,585714	8,783238	2046	2000	Medium	46
-70,585652	8,783657	2046	2000	Medium	46
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-70,583971	8,784115	2017	2000	Medium	17
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-70,581966	8,784606	1962	2000	Medium	-38
-70,58161	8,784479	1968	2000	Medium	-32
-70,581479	8,784125	1968	2000	Medium	-32
-70,581575	8,783803	1968	2000	Medium	-32
-70,581799	8,783352	1939	2000	Medium	-61
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-70,581729	8,782032	2048	2000	Medium	48
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-70,577783	8,782403	1981	2000	Medium	-19
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-70,577039	8,782631	1953	2000	Medium	-47
-70,576618	8,782504	1953	2000	Medium	-47
-70,576551	8,782021	1941	2000	Medium	-59
-70,576874	8,781859	1941	2000	Medium	-59
-70,577488	8,781599	1951	2000	Medium	-49
-70,577844	8,781501	1951	2000	Medium	-49
-70,578653	8,781498	1965	2000	Medium	-35
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-70,579621	8,780978	1949	2000	Medium	-51
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-70,589515	8,771441	1941	2000	Medium	-59
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-70,608422	8,810633	1983	2000	Medium	-17
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-70,609685	8,81095	1983	2000	Medium	-17
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-70,616893	8,816391	2058	2000	Medium	58
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-70,622956	8,818844	2013	2000	Medium	13
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-70,621079	8,80398	1985	2000	Medium	-15
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-70,615457	8,798693	2011	2000	Medium	11
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-70,614192	8,798022	1953	2000	Medium	-47
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-70,611113	8,789505	1982	2000	Medium	-18
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-70,606367	8,784406	2067	2000	Medium	67
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-70,604882	8,785218	2078	2000	Medium	78
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-70,602363	8,786548	2204	2000	Medium	204
-70,602237	8,78716	2165	2000	Medium	165
-70,602077	8,787676	2261	2000	Medium	261
-70,602144	8,788287	2126	2000	Medium	126
-70,602049	8,788771	2157	2000	Medium	157
-70,601792	8,78919	2157	2000	Medium	157
-70,601765	8,790349	2129	2000	Medium	129
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-70,601675	8,791927	2103	2000	Medium	103
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-70,599454	8,794769	1949	2000	Medium	-51
-70,598836	8,79416	2017	2000	Medium	17
-70,598447	8,793872	2002	2000	Medium	2
-70,597929	8,793842	2002	2000	Medium	2
-70,597249	8,793845	1948	2000	Medium	-52
-70,59699	8,793653	1908	2000	Medium	-92
-70,596825	8,792945	1908	2000	Medium	-92
-70,596595	8,79227	1971	2000	Medium	-29
-70,595977	8,791533	1926	2000	Medium	-74
-70,595457	8,790955	2020	2000	Medium	20
-70,594742	8,790315	2062	2000	Medium	62
-70,593996	8,789738	1969	2000	Medium	-31
-70,612317	8,813417	2001	2000	Medium	1
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-70,611956	8,812196	2014	2000	Medium	14
-70,589749	8,808902	2013	2000	Medium	13
-70,59001	8,809352	2013	2000	Medium	13
-70,590464	8,809478	1968	2000	Medium	-32
-70,590949	8,809412	1968	2000	Medium	-32
-70,591304	8,809282	1954	2000	Medium	-46
-70,591788	8,808829	1954	2000	Medium	-46
-70,592401	8,808344	1930	2000	Medium	-70
-70,593207	8,807793	1952	2000	Medium	-48
-70,593788	8,807404	1980	2000	Medium	-20
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-70,595309	8,807462	1968	2000	Medium	-32
-70,595988	8,807137	1957	2000	Medium	-43
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-70,597703	8,807162	1985	2000	Medium	-15
-70,598674	8,807126	1985	2000	Medium	-15
-70,599224	8,807124	1986	2000	Medium	-14
-70,599808	8,807507	1972	2000	Medium	-28
-70,599939	8,807861	1972	2000	Medium	-28
-70,599586	8,808571	2009	2000	Medium	9
-70,599135	8,809152	2063	2000	Medium	63
-70,599105	8,809603	2057	2000	Medium	57
-70,598913	8,810119	2057	2000	Medium	57
-70,598494	8,810539	2037	2000	Medium	37
-70,598108	8,810959	2037	2000	Medium	37
-70,597722	8,811508	2020	2000	Medium	20
-70,597433	8,812217	1988	2000	Medium	-12
-70,597208	8,812605	1988	2000	Medium	-12
-70,596919	8,812992	1976	2000	Medium	-24
-70,596436	8,813477	1976	2000	Medium	-24
-70,595791	8,814091	2056	2000	Medium	56
-70,595858	8,814542	2056	2000	Medium	56
-70,596085	8,814831	2043	2000	Medium	43
-70,596927	8,814891	2011	2000	Medium	11
-70,597671	8,814727	1978	2000	Medium	-22
-70,598414	8,814434	1980	2000	Medium	-20
-70,599385	8,81443	1958	2000	Medium	-42
-70,59987	8,814493	1954	2000	Medium	-46
-70,60026	8,814716	2027	2000	Medium	27
-70,600682	8,815165	1994	2000	Medium	-6
-70,600944	8,815904	2011	2000	Medium	11
-70,601142	8,816708	2075	2000	Medium	75
-70,601273	8,816997	2080	2000	Medium	80
-70,60163	8,817189	2132	2000	Medium	132
-70,602114	8,817026	2095	2000	Medium	95
-70,602371	8,816574	2095	2000	Medium	95
-70,602592	8,815189	1998	2000	Medium	-2
-70,602879	8,814254	1881	2000	Medium	-119
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-70,604319	8,812405	1956	2000	Medium	-44
-70,604845	8,812298	1990	2000	Medium	-10
-70,605169	8,812466	1990	2000	Medium	-10
-70,60526	8,81294	2032	2000	Medium	32
-70,6056	8,813011	2012	2000	Medium	12
-70,605817	8,812729	1975	2000	Medium	-25
-70,605978	8,812358	1975	2000	Medium	-25
-70,583533	8,815882	1965	2000	Medium	-35
-70,584114	8,815525	1980	2000	Medium	-20
-70,584727	8,815072	1955	2000	Medium	-45
-70,58495	8,814266	1922	2000	Medium	-78

-70,585271	8,813589	1926	2000	Medium	-74
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-70,584814	8,812689	1958	2000	Medium	-42
-70,58465	8,812239	1958	2000	Medium	-42
-70,584516	8,811177	1935	2000	Medium	-65
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-70,584541	8,809407	1944	2000	Medium	-56
-70,585153	8,808664	1912	2000	Medium	-88
-70,586059	8,80866	1926	2000	Medium	-74
-70,586835	8,808496	1945	2000	Medium	-55
-70,587221	8,808011	1979	2000	Medium	-21
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-70,588091	8,807139	1979	2000	Medium	-21
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-70,588482	8,807781	1979	2000	Medium	-21
-70,588647	8,808424	2018	2000	Medium	18
-70,588905	8,808262	1998	2000	Medium	-2
-70,589424	8,808485	1998	2000	Medium	-2
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-70,603794	8,816311	2195	2200	Medium	-5
-70,603245	8,816635	2142	2200	Medium	-58
-70,60302	8,817022	2142	2200	Medium	-58
-70,602991	8,817795	2194	2200	Medium	-6
-70,60293	8,818568	2234	2200	Medium	34
-70,602868	8,819115	2242	2200	Medium	42
-70,602611	8,819664	2179	2200	Medium	-21
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-70,602259	8,820599	2217	2200	Medium	17
-70,602228	8,820888	2217	2200	Medium	17
-70,602101	8,821404	2248	2200	Medium	48
-70,601908	8,821823	2273	2200	Medium	73
-70,601423	8,821858	2273	2200	Medium	73
-70,601002	8,821698	2309	2200	Medium	109
-70,600417	8,821186	2290	2200	Medium	90
-70,600156	8,820704	2335	2200	Medium	135
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-70,599503	8,819451	2279	2200	Medium	79
-70,599145	8,818809	2279	2200	Medium	79
-70,598753	8,81807	2256	2200	Medium	56

-70,598264	8,817203	2198	2200	Medium	-2
-70,597649	8,817174	2157	2200	Medium	-43
-70,597229	8,817433	2157	2200	Medium	-43
-70,596745	8,817821	2140	2200	Medium	-60
-70,596293	8,817952	2194	2200	Medium	-6
-70,595807	8,817922	2205	2200	Medium	5
-70,595257	8,817796	2141	2200	Medium	-59
-70,594674	8,81783	2141	2200	Medium	-59
-70,594156	8,817832	2165	2200	Medium	-35
-70,593443	8,81761	2212	2200	Medium	12
-70,592827	8,81713	2265	2200	Medium	65
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-70,592302	8,815651	2224	2200	Medium	24
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-70,592488	8,813655	2265	2200	Medium	65
-70,592776	8,812945	2265	2200	Medium	65
-70,593291	8,812299	2247	2200	Medium	47
-70,593936	8,811814	2218	2200	Medium	18
-70,594581	8,811296	2218	2200	Medium	18
-70,594709	8,810748	2185	2200	Medium	-15
-70,594319	8,810396	2140	2200	Medium	-60
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-70,593154	8,810433	2167	2200	Medium	-33
-70,592347	8,810919	2138	2200	Medium	-62
-70,591799	8,811372	2187	2200	Medium	-13
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-70,588021	8,813448	2173	2200	Medium	-27
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-70,625464	8,802182	2217	2200	Medium	17
-70,625239	8,802489	2166	2200	Medium	-34
-70,624739	8,803006	2205	2200	Medium	5
-70,624579	8,803409	2164	2200	Medium	-36
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-70,62353	8,803945	2184	2200	Medium	-16

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-70,622352	8,804771	2183	2200	Medium	-17
-70,622193	8,805255	2183	2200	Medium	-17
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-70,622603	8,806508	2135	2200	Medium	-65
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-70,625454	8,811083	2174	2200	Medium	-26
-70,624794	8,81181	2156	2200	Medium	-44
-70,624101	8,812409	2149	2200	Medium	-51
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-70,623007	8,813926	2170	2200	Medium	-30
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-70,624957	8,815817	2133	2200	Medium	-67
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-70,626015	8,817326	2124	2200	Medium	-76
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-70,62736	8,817754	2196	2200	Medium	-4
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-70,623717	8,820941	2120	2200	Medium	-80
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-70,622671	8,822088	2202	2200	Medium	2
-70,621862	8,82214	2189	2200	Medium	-11
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-70,620844	8,82245	2229	2200	Medium	29
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-70,620237	8,820682	2194	2200	Medium	-6
-70,61967	8,82046	2194	2200	Medium	-6
-70,619072	8,820623	2195	2200	Medium	-5
-70,618474	8,820754	2215	2200	Medium	15
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-70,61724	8,819858	2200	2200	Medium	0
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-70,615926	8,819108	2225	2200	Medium	25
-70,615535	8,818401	2181	2200	Medium	-19
-70,615258	8,818145	2157	2200	Medium	-43
-70,614677	8,818453	2157	2200	Medium	-43
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-70,613277	8,820117	2208	2200	Medium	8
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-70,612484	8,820072	2260	2200	Medium	60
-70,61235	8,819107	2224	2200	Medium	24
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-70,611271	8,816472	2207	2200	Medium	7
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-70,608429	8,814118	2144	2200	Medium	-56
-70,607993	8,814506	2144	2200	Medium	-56
-70,590215	8,777037	2157	2200	Medium	-43
-70,589749	8,777256	2212	2200	Medium	12
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-70,588389	8,779523	2176	2200	Medium	-24
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-70,590015	8,781281	2144	2200	Medium	-56
-70,590329	8,781899	2144	2200	Medium	-56
-70,59055	8,782579	2197	2200	Medium	-3
-70,590678	8,783446	2153	2200	Medium	-47
-70,590931	8,784312	2167	2200	Medium	-33
-70,591494	8,784867	2201	2200	Medium	1
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-70,593149	8,78613	2209	2200	Medium	9
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-70,594902	8,788383	2176	2200	Medium	-24
-70,595685	8,789433	2204	2200	Medium	4
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-70,599606	8,789014	2263	2200	Medium	63
-70,599568	8,787527	2363	2200	Medium	163
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-70,605054	8,781899	2221	2200	Medium	21
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-70,61302	8,788306	2183	2200	Medium	-17
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-70,613153	8,790226	2142	2200	Medium	-58
-70,613715	8,790657	2151	2200	Medium	-49
-70,613782	8,791555	2168	2200	Medium	-32
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-70,614016	8,795394	2150	2200	Medium	-50
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-70,62291	8,800248	2185	2200	Medium	-15
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-70,603246	8,766917	2242	2200	Medium	42
-70,60321	8,765586	2230	2200	Medium	30
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-70,595065	8,761037	2239	2200	Medium	39

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-70,592216	8,771888	2169	2200	Medium	-31
-70,592249	8,772291	2180	2200	Medium	-20
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-70,591539	8,773687	2152	2200	Medium	-48
-70,591634	8,774089	2117	2200	Medium	-83
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-70,62214	8,766465	2216	2200	Medium	16
-70,621828	8,766126	2221	2200	Medium	21
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-70,656239	8,762074	2237	2200	Medium	37
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-70,650984	8,784611	2249	2200	Medium	49
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-70,644421	8,732737	2222	2200	Medium	22
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-70,643135	8,741166	2248	2200	Medium	48
-70,643416	8,741273	2233	2200	Medium	33
-70,643759	8,74155	2216	2200	Medium	16
-70,644118	8,74175	2216	2200	Medium	16
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-70,624106	8,710109	2107	2200	Medium	-93
-70,624326	8,710542	2137	2200	Medium	-63
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-70,706482	8,717986	2216	2200	Medium	16

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-70,692361	8,713311	2291	2200	Medium	91
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-70,694292	8,713457	2318	2200	Medium	118
-70,695258	8,713855	2232	2200	Medium	32
-70,696256	8,71416	2242	2200	Medium	42
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-70,700645	8,714296	2247	2200	Medium	47
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-70,701374	8,717172	2240	2200	Medium	40
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-70,701236	8,721106	2168	2200	Medium	-32
-70,700741	8,721758	2193	2200	Medium	-7
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-70,700683	8,722688	2216	2200	Medium	16
-70,700405	8,723153	2183	2200	Medium	-17
-70,699816	8,723806	2233	2200	Medium	33
-70,699197	8,724521	2178	2200	Medium	-22
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-70,699116	8,727216	2263	2200	Medium	63
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-70,697385	8,736762	2247	2200	Medium	47
-70,697077	8,737413	2198	2200	Medium	-2
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-70,696276	8,739244	2233	2200	Medium	33
-70,695962	8,738719	2203	2200	Medium	3
-70,695523	8,738009	2203	2200	Medium	3
-70,695114	8,737082	2185	2200	Medium	-15

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-70,691184	8,735272	2160	2200	Medium	-40
-70,6905	8,735306	2160	2200	Medium	-40
-70,690156	8,735091	2176	2200	Medium	-24
-70,690277	8,734347	2206	2200	Medium	6
-70,690586	8,733664	2172	2200	Medium	-28
-70,690952	8,732021	2237	2200	Medium	37
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-70,690475	8,729856	2278	2200	Medium	78
-70,690252	8,728804	2348	2200	Medium	148
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-70,690517	8,725396	2231	2200	Medium	31
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-70,690293	8,723973	2230	2200	Medium	30
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-70,688209	8,724323	2266	2200	Medium	66
-70,687276	8,724575	2213	2200	Medium	13
-70,686375	8,724795	2355	2200	Medium	155
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-70,681079	8,723797	2220	2200	Medium	20
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-70,680244	8,725039	2197	2200	Medium	-3
-70,679903	8,725382	2197	2200	Medium	-3
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-70,678572	8,726967	2185	2200	Medium	-15
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-70,673611	8,7312	2183	2200	Medium	-17
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-70,672427	8,73102	2193	2200	Medium	-7
-70,672024	8,731269	2218	2200	Medium	18
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-70,671109	8,731335	2230	2200	Medium	30
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-70,670298	8,728273	2191	2200	Medium	-9
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-70,671534	8,7261	2289	2200	Medium	89
-70,672183	8,725199	2265	2200	Medium	65
-70,672399	8,724609	2265	2200	Medium	65
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-70,672831	8,723802	2240	2200	Medium	40
-70,672829	8,7234	2220	2200	Medium	20
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-70,67214	8,722381	2150	2200	Medium	-50
-70,671733	8,721949	2150	2200	Medium	-50
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-70,670513	8,720592	2183	2200	Medium	-17
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-70,671195	8,719877	2219	2200	Medium	19
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-70,681985	8,661672	1820	2200	Medium	-380
-70,681518	8,661705	1820	2200	Medium	-380
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-70,681797	8,668516	2239	2200	Medium	39
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-70,680791	8,673197	2271	2200	Medium	71
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-70,682591	8,672167	2282	2200	Medium	82
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-70,683679	8,671791	2304	2200	Medium	104
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-70,685448	8,67073	2271	2200	Medium	71
-70,686068	8,670232	2390	2200	Medium	190
-70,68666	8,670291	2388	2200	Medium	188
-70,687346	8,670536	2286	2200	Medium	86
-70,687718	8,670379	2344	2200	Medium	144
-70,688215	8,670067	2319	2200	Medium	119
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-70,68927	8,683193	2241	2200	Medium	41
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-70,689246	8,684958	2290	2200	Medium	90
-70,689188	8,685795	2290	2200	Medium	90
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-70,691643	8,69207	2314	2200	Medium	114
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-70,692837	8,694449	2252	2200	Medium	52
-70,693335	8,69454	2270	2200	Medium	70
-70,693832	8,694352	2293	2200	Medium	93
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-70,70152	8,694442	2257	2200	Medium	57
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-70,711354	8,701241	2260	2200	Medium	60
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-70,717671	8,707747	2262	2200	Medium	62
-70,71786	8,708241	2191	2200	Medium	-9
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-70,718425	8,709199	2213	2200	Medium	13
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-70,71856	8,718396	2252	2200	Medium	52
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-70,720804	8,71916	2250	2200	Medium	50
-70,721427	8,719219	2267	2200	Medium	67
-70,722361	8,719214	2271	2200	Medium	71
-70,722703	8,719244	2271	2200	Medium	71
-70,722736	8,719646	2259	2200	Medium	59
-70,722426	8,719864	2259	2200	Medium	59
-70,722178	8,720113	2259	2200	Medium	59
-70,721681	8,720301	2241	2200	Medium	41
-70,720966	8,720398	2229	2200	Medium	29
-70,719845	8,720403	2211	2200	Medium	11
-70,719254	8,720436	2262	2200	Medium	62
-70,718538	8,720378	2188	2200	Medium	-12
-70,717823	8,720505	2217	2200	Medium	17
-70,717669	8,720846	2217	2200	Medium	17
-70,71714	8,721003	2217	2200	Medium	17
-70,716455	8,720944	2209	2200	Medium	9
-70,715771	8,721164	2198	2200	Medium	-2
-70,711307	8,680602	2360	2400	High	-40
-70,711496	8,681096	2360	2400	High	-40
-70,711811	8,681776	2394	2400	High	-6
-70,71256	8,68233	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,713309	8,682822	2376	2400	High	-24
-70,713562	8,683564	2413	2400	High	13
-70,713751	8,684245	2388	2400	High	-12
-70,71419	8,684862	2411	2400	High	11
-70,714752	8,685293	2368	2400	High	-32

-70,715191	8,686035	2398	2400	High	-2
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-70,716004	8,686836	2404	2400	High	4
-70,695598	8,671676	2584	2600	High	-16
-70,695379	8,671522	2605	2600	High	5
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-70,694881	8,6714	2605	2600	High	5
-70,69454	8,671742	2628	2600	High	28
-70,694326	8,672549	2664	2600	High	64
-70,694327	8,672889	2664	2600	High	64
-70,694549	8,673693	2701	2600	High	101
-70,694801	8,674466	2750	2600	High	150
-70,695273	8,675703	2679	2600	High	79
-70,695493	8,676167	2752	2600	High	152
-70,695903	8,677187	2705	2600	High	105
-70,695782	8,677961	2674	2600	High	74
-70,695815	8,678488	2674	2600	High	74
-70,695881	8,679416	2650	2600	High	50
-70,695682	8,676661	2720	2600	High	120
-70,694991	8,675178	2751	2600	High	151
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-70,695236	8,681184	2611	2600	High	11
-70,695188	8,682341	2659	2600	High	59
-70,695215	8,681861	2652	2600	High	52
-70,695337	8,68298	2639	2600	High	39
-70,695216	8,6836	2639	2600	High	39
-70,69503	8,683942	2671	2600	High	71
-70,694722	8,6845	2671	2600	High	71
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-70,693086	8,687573	2687	2600	High	87
-70,693088	8,687914	2687	2600	High	87
-70,693151	8,688192	2669	2600	High	69
-70,693586	8,688098	2669	2600	High	69
-70,694354	8,688059	2684	2600	High	84
-70,693968	8,688031	2684	2600	High	84
-70,694822	8,688337	2656	2600	High	56
-70,695331	8,688554	2656	2600	High	56
-70,695857	8,687871	2700	2600	High	100
-70,696199	8,687683	2700	2600	High	100
-70,696605	8,688022	2631	2600	High	31
-70,697351	8,687926	2623	2600	High	23
-70,698408	8,687519	2643	2600	High	43

-70,697909	8,687637	2682	2600	High	82
-70,698593	8,687208	2643	2600	High	43
-70,698716	8,686774	2661	2600	High	61
-70,699056	8,686277	2622	2600	High	22
-70,699365	8,685842	2671	2600	High	71
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-70,700351	8,683639	2672	2600	High	72
-70,700627	8,682864	2651	2600	High	51
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-70,701492	8,68125	2604	2600	High	4
-70,702078	8,680194	2650	2600	High	50
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-70,70419	8,679132	2671	2600	High	71
-70,704873	8,678912	2645	2600	High	45
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-70,699004	8,680702	2770	2800	High	-30
-70,699239	8,680199	2774	2800	High	-26
-70,699415	8,679756	2774	2800	High	-26
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-70,698038	8,676813	2814	2800	High	14
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-70,697953	8,677787	2846	2800	High	46
-70,698133	8,678169	2868	2800	High	68
-70,698164	8,678552	2868	2800	High	68
-70,698167	8,679054	2847	2800	High	47
-70,698139	8,679585	2819	2800	High	19
-70,697964	8,680146	2819	2800	High	19
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-70,697495	8,68121	2806	2800	High	6
-70,697526	8,681564	2814	2800	High	14
-70,697498	8,682006	2814	2800	High	14
-70,69744	8,682272	2814	2800	High	14
-70,697353	8,682656	2814	2800	High	14
-70,697384	8,683098	2819	2800	High	19
-70,697711	8,683244	2819	2800	High	19
-70,698007	8,683213	2784	2800	High	-16
-70,698332	8,682946	2784	2800	High	-16
-70,698598	8,682768	2791	2800	High	-9

-70,698626	8,682414	2791	2800	High	-9
-70,698714	8,682178	2791	2800	High	-9
-70,698771	8,681676	2766	2800	High	-34
-70,691548	8,683596	2429	2400	High	29
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-70,692345	8,682884	2470	2400	High	70
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-70,692161	8,681469	2475	2400	High	75
-70,692631	8,68073	2446	2400	High	46
-70,692985	8,680286	2463	2400	High	63
-70,69313	8,679607	2463	2400	High	63
-70,693306	8,679075	2450	2400	High	50
-70,693599	8,678484	2428	2400	High	28
-70,693834	8,677893	2544	2400	High	144
-70,694009	8,677214	2544	2400	High	144
-70,693976	8,676566	2561	2400	High	161
-70,693766	8,675977	2631	2400	High	231
-70,693289	8,675389	2537	2400	High	137
-70,693049	8,674712	2537	2400	High	137
-70,693047	8,674181	2575	2400	High	175
-70,693043	8,673325	2591	2400	High	191
-70,693068	8,672352	2575	2400	High	175
-70,693036	8,671792	2643	2400	High	243
-70,692884	8,670937	2469	2400	High	69
-70,693029	8,670199	2605	2400	High	205
-70,693086	8,669786	2605	2400	High	205
-70,692817	8,669109	2540	2400	High	140
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-70,691505	8,667375	2557	2400	High	157
-70,690703	8,667054	2529	2400	High	129
-70,689991	8,66688	2533	2400	High	133
-70,688835	8,666885	2544	2400	High	144
-70,687858	8,667096	2551	2400	High	151
-70,687059	8,667306	2549	2400	High	149
-70,686378	8,667633	2549	2400	High	149
-70,685874	8,667606	2520	2400	High	120
-70,685547	8,667254	2520	2400	High	120
-70,685277	8,666635	2418	2400	High	18
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-70,685243	8,665574	2356	2400	High	-44
-70,684944	8,665103	2284	2400	High	-116
-70,684646	8,664751	2284	2400	High	-116
-70,6842	8,664281	2120	2400	High	-280
-70,683902	8,663958	2120	2400	High	-280
-70,683871	8,663574	2049	2400	High	-351

-70,684284	8,663278	2049	2400	High	-351
-70,710691	8,682655	2447	2400	High	47
-70,710438	8,682538	2447	2400	High	47
-70,709962	8,682186	2450	2400	High	50
-70,7091	8,681659	2502	2400	High	102
-70,708432	8,681397	2496	2400	High	96
-70,707928	8,681384	2496	2400	High	96
-70,707335	8,681343	2476	2400	High	76
-70,706831	8,681227	2540	2400	High	140
-70,706357	8,681303	2453	2400	High	53
-70,705795	8,6816	2436	2400	High	36
-70,705398	8,682148	2413	2400	High	13
-70,705401	8,682797	2413	2400	High	13
-70,705392	8,684109	2418	2400	High	18
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-70,703599	8,687479	2485	2400	High	85
-70,703468	8,68804	2464	2400	High	64
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-70,702731	8,689002	2456	2400	High	56
-70,702288	8,689343	2456	2400	High	56
-70,701861	8,689847	2494	2400	High	94
-70,701479	8,69063	2467	2400	High	67
-70,701083	8,691472	2467	2400	High	67
-70,700595	8,691872	2467	2400	High	67
-70,700151	8,691919	2468	2400	High	68
-70,699868	8,691684	2468	2400	High	68
-70,699512	8,691464	2434	2400	High	34
-70,699111	8,691363	2434	2400	High	34
-70,698635	8,691041	2454	2400	High	54
-70,698263	8,690674	2454	2400	High	54
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-70,697357	8,690265	2492	2400	High	92
-70,696869	8,690414	2504	2400	High	104
-70,696425	8,690652	2444	2400	High	44
-70,695881	8,691436	2417	2400	High	17
-70,695483	8,692057	2417	2400	High	17
-70,695158	8,692206	2421	2400	High	21
-70,69498	8,692163	2421	2400	High	21
-70,69486	8,69181	2437	2400	High	37
-70,694621	8,691545	2437	2400	High	37
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-70,693877	8,690767	2478	2400	High	78

-70,693608	8,690355	2507	2400	High	107
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-70,691681	8,690216	2477	2400	High	77
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-70,690999	8,690101	2424	2400	High	24
-70,690909	8,689925	2424	2400	High	24
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-70,690858	8,68845	2426	2400	High	26
-70,690884	8,687551	2447	2400	High	47
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-70,691044	8,686916	2467	2400	High	67
-70,690909	8,686577	2467	2400	High	67
-70,690861	8,685796	2460	2400	High	60
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-70,691272	8,68488	2490	2400	High	90
-70,691372	8,684186	2461	2400	High	61
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-70,713059	8,714629	2413	2400	High	13
-70,712702	8,714336	2372	2400	High	-28
-70,712934	8,713273	2427	2400	High	27
-70,713554	8,712651	2381	2400	High	-19
-70,714619	8,712263	2441	2400	High	41
-70,715418	8,711994	2394	2400	High	-6
-70,716514	8,711664	2427	2400	High	27
-70,717313	8,711543	2437	2400	High	37
-70,717906	8,711599	2437	2400	High	37
-70,718589	8,711802	2417	2400	High	17
-70,718885	8,711713	2414	2400	High	14
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-70,719951	8,711442	2449	2400	High	49
-70,720513	8,711263	2493	2400	High	93
-70,721164	8,710906	2408	2400	High	8
-70,721756	8,710756	2455	2400	High	55
-70,722259	8,710547	2497	2400	High	97
-70,722642	8,710014	2420	2400	High	20
-70,722699	8,709601	2420	2400	High	20
-70,722431	8,709308	2473	2400	High	73
-70,721985	8,708985	2438	2400	High	38
-70,721213	8,708664	2462	2400	High	62
-70,720589	8,708431	2462	2400	High	62
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-70,719635	8,707079	2498	2400	High	98
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-70,718684	8,706552	2385	2400	High	-15

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-70,717812	8,70399	2452	2400	High	52
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-70,716657	8,704114	2450	2400	High	50
-70,715826	8,70394	2423	2400	High	23
-70,714906	8,70362	2439	2400	High	39
-70,71452	8,703445	2427	2400	High	27
-70,714046	8,703506	2427	2400	High	27
-70,713691	8,703626	2389	2400	High	-11
-70,713393	8,70345	2389	2400	High	-11
-70,713451	8,703096	2389	2400	High	-11
-70,713804	8,702534	2441	2400	High	41
-70,71398	8,702061	2443	2400	High	43
-70,713741	8,701679	2381	2400	High	-19
-70,713796	8,700794	2457	2400	High	57
-70,713733	8,699939	2392	2400	High	-8
-70,713878	8,69926	2452	2400	High	52
-70,713875	8,698522	2444	2400	High	44
-70,713695	8,69814	2397	2400	High	-3
-70,713634	8,697639	2395	2400	High	-5
-70,713781	8,697402	2433	2400	High	33
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-70,71481	8,695657	2419	2400	High	19
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-70,715603	8,694091	2457	2400	High	57
-70,715897	8,693411	2431	2400	High	31
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-70,716365	8,69217	2468	2400	High	68
-70,716243	8,691434	2364	2400	High	-36
-70,716152	8,690933	2408	2400	High	8
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-70,715733	8,689961	2437	2400	High	37
-70,715731	8,689489	2416	2400	High	16
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-70,715544	8,687632	2440	2400	High	40
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-70,714681	8,68684	2414	2400	High	14
-70,714502	8,686605	2381	2400	High	-19
-70,714323	8,686222	2410	2400	High	10
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-70,712653	8,683988	2406	2400	High	6
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-70,724071	8,717794	2445	2400	High	45
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-70,722854	8,717505	2427	2400	High	27
-70,722321	8,717713	2427	2400	High	27
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-70,721461	8,717452	2420	2400	High	20
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-70,71929	8,716017	2454	2400	High	54
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-70,718669	8,716344	2398	2400	High	-2
-70,718047	8,716376	2398	2400	High	-2
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-70,71695	8,716263	2391	2400	High	-9
-70,716594	8,716324	2391	2400	High	-9
-70,716089	8,71612	2437	2400	High	37
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-70,714515	8,715507	2383	2400	High	-17
-70,711056	8,723899	2470	2400	High	70
-70,711501	8,724044	2454	2400	High	54
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-70,712093	8,723747	2391	2400	High	-9
-70,712892	8,723448	2391	2400	High	-9
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-70,717549	8,724105	2423	2400	High	23

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-70,718558	8,724455	2431	2400	High	31
-70,718854	8,724277	2423	2400	High	23
-70,719089	8,723804	2423	2400	High	23
-70,719383	8,72333	2381	2400	High	-19
-70,719855	8,722886	2391	2400	High	-9
-70,720416	8,722441	2391	2400	High	-9
-70,720948	8,722114	2440	2400	High	40
-70,72163	8,72214	2454	2400	High	54
-70,722165	8,722433	2424	2400	High	24
-70,722611	8,722667	2424	2400	High	24
-70,723086	8,722812	2406	2400	High	6
-70,72344	8,722398	2406	2400	High	6
-70,723912	8,721894	2414	2400	High	14
-70,724563	8,721773	2414	2400	High	14
-70,725037	8,721742	2424	2400	High	24
-70,725362	8,721475	2424	2400	High	24
-70,725953	8,721148	2415	2400	High	15
-70,726545	8,720762	2450	2400	High	50
-70,727107	8,720582	2458	2400	High	58
-70,72767	8,720461	2458	2400	High	58
-70,728233	8,720459	2445	2400	High	45
-70,728826	8,720604	2446	2400	High	46
-70,72933	8,72066	2446	2400	High	46
-70,729806	8,720835	2451	2400	High	51
-70,730309	8,720833	2451	2400	High	51
-70,730575	8,720625	2473	2400	High	73
-70,730722	8,7203	2439	2400	High	39
-70,731017	8,720092	2439	2400	High	39
-70,731431	8,719854	2478	2400	High	78
-70,731786	8,719558	2468	2400	High	68
-70,731637	8,71947	2468	2400	High	68
-70,731222	8,719472	2471	2400	High	71
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-70,730066	8,719477	2466	2400	High	66
-70,729177	8,719481	2443	2400	High	43
-70,72882	8,719336	2443	2400	High	43
-70,728493	8,719101	2370	2400	High	-30
-70,727988	8,718808	2370	2400	High	-30
-70,727453	8,718516	2466	2400	High	66
-70,727038	8,7184	2425	2400	High	25
-70,726592	8,718254	2425	2400	High	25
-70,726207	8,718168	2405	2400	High	5
-70,725701	8,717875	2465	2400	High	65
-70,725225	8,717494	2445	2400	High	45

-70,7249	8,717584	2445	2400	High	45
-70,724575	8,71788	2445	2400	High	45
-70,699413	8,735276	2393	2400	High	-7
-70,69947	8,734775	2393	2400	High	-7
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-70,699936	8,732915	2388	2400	High	-12
-70,700589	8,732971	2458	2400	High	58
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-70,701834	8,733054	2459	2400	High	59
-70,702692	8,732578	2416	2400	High	16
-70,703254	8,73231	2461	2400	High	61
-70,703786	8,732131	2452	2400	High	52
-70,703756	8,731924	2461	2400	High	61
-70,703576	8,731512	2413	2400	High	13
-70,703218	8,731101	2470	2400	High	70
-70,702388	8,730928	2444	2400	High	44
-70,701557	8,730872	2432	2400	High	32
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-70,700727	8,730729	2405	2400	High	5
-70,700574	8,729668	2421	2400	High	21
-70,70063	8,72896	2405	2400	High	5
-70,700806	8,728605	2405	2400	High	5
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-70,701807	8,727185	2424	2400	High	24
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-70,702097	8,725768	2442	2400	High	42
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-70,702034	8,724942	2395	2400	High	-5
-70,702417	8,72441	2395	2400	High	-5
-70,702802	8,724349	2395	2400	High	-5
-70,703069	8,7242	2439	2400	High	39
-70,703036	8,723552	2433	2400	High	33
-70,703181	8,722814	2410	2400	High	10
-70,703623	8,722251	2410	2400	High	10
-70,70368	8,721868	2395	2400	High	-5
-70,703677	8,72113	2400	2400	High	0
-70,703498	8,720777	2400	2400	High	0
-70,703377	8,720306	2396	2400	High	-4
-70,703314	8,719539	2387	2400	High	-13
-70,70343	8,719008	2387	2400	High	-13
-70,703845	8,718829	2390	2400	High	-10

-70,704291	8,719328	2390	2400	High	-10
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-70,705127	8,720622	2419	2400	High	19
-70,705337	8,721152	2419	2400	High	19
-70,705548	8,721918	2399	2400	High	-1
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-70,706445	8,723566	2416	2400	High	16
-70,706982	8,724389	2428	2400	High	28
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-70,708173	8,725563	2442	2400	High	42
-70,708528	8,725414	2385	2400	High	-15
-70,709029	8,724763	2450	2400	High	50
-70,70956	8,724171	2408	2400	High	8
-70,710329	8,723784	2453	2400	High	53
-70,687734	8,725863	2435	2400	High	35
-70,688233	8,726077	2383	2400	High	-17
-70,688455	8,726882	2437	2400	High	37
-70,688551	8,727593	2450	2400	High	50
-70,688274	8,728245	2455	2400	High	55
-70,688246	8,728988	2448	2400	High	48
-70,68828	8,729515	2448	2400	High	48
-70,688502	8,730381	2434	2400	High	34
-70,688693	8,731371	2440	2400	High	40
-70,688669	8,73295	2376	2400	High	-24
-70,688393	8,733881	2331	2400	High	-69
-70,688115	8,734346	2331	2400	High	-69
-70,687776	8,73506	2357	2400	High	-43
-70,687498	8,735526	2325	2400	High	-75
-70,687251	8,736053	2325	2400	High	-75
-70,687191	8,736673	2295	2400	High	-105
-70,687256	8,73723	2320	2400	High	-80
-70,687415	8,737818	2320	2400	High	-80
-70,687853	8,738342	2374	2400	High	-26
-70,688445	8,738587	2344	2400	High	-56
-70,68885	8,73874	2370	2400	High	-30
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-70,690001	8,738457	2410	2400	High	10
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-70,690718	8,738639	2397	2400	High	-3
-70,691	8,739072	2459	2400	High	59
-70,691404	8,73907	2452	2400	High	52
-70,691527	8,738605	2408	2400	High	8
-70,691867	8,738046	2408	2400	High	8
-70,6923	8,737579	2404	2400	High	4
-70,692519	8,737671	2404	2400	High	4

-70,692989	8,738412	2432	2400	High	32
-70,693365	8,738937	2434	2400	High	34
-70,69368	8,739772	2476	2400	High	76
-70,694026	8,740575	2465	2400	High	65
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-70,694347	8,742835	2466	2400	High	66
-70,694879	8,743328	2454	2400	High	54
-70,695377	8,74348	2454	2400	High	54
-70,695752	8,743757	2478	2400	High	78
-70,69622	8,744065	2478	2400	High	78
-70,696656	8,744063	2449	2400	High	49
-70,697433	8,743874	2482	2400	High	82
-70,697993	8,743747	2402	2400	High	2
-70,69843	8,743869	2489	2400	High	89
-70,699022	8,744114	2447	2400	High	47
-70,699521	8,74436	2447	2400	High	47
-70,700052	8,744729	2459	2400	High	59
-70,700458	8,745037	2415	2400	High	15
-70,700832	8,745221	2415	2400	High	15
-70,701205	8,745033	2415	2400	High	15
-70,701204	8,744724	2415	2400	High	15
-70,701139	8,744198	2386	2400	High	-14
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-70,70045	8,743303	2444	2400	High	44
-70,700012	8,742809	2432	2400	High	32
-70,699729	8,742222	2432	2400	High	32
-70,699291	8,741698	2394	2400	High	-6
-70,698853	8,741266	2394	2400	High	-6
-70,6986	8,740214	2383	2400	High	-17
-70,698751	8,739285	2433	2400	High	33
-70,699182	8,738199	2406	2400	High	6
-70,699583	8,737454	2480	2400	High	80
-70,699518	8,736773	2375	2400	High	-25
-70,69942	8,735844	2401	2400	High	1
-70,664732	8,718625	2367	2400	High	-33
-70,665387	8,719025	2443	2400	High	43
-70,665823	8,719023	2420	2400	High	20
-70,666165	8,718898	2420	2400	High	20
-70,6666	8,718865	2424	2400	High	24
-70,667037	8,71908	2424	2400	High	24
-70,667225	8,719388	2406	2400	High	6
-70,667168	8,720472	2405	2400	High	5
-70,667203	8,721494	2376	2400	High	-24
-70,667393	8,722175	2420	2400	High	20
-70,667769	8,722792	2420	2400	High	20
-70,668331	8,723224	2397	2400	High	-3

-70,66905	8,72384	2440	2400	High	40
-70,669768	8,724394	2406	2400	High	6
-70,669988	8,724858	2428	2400	High	28
-70,669865	8,725168	2428	2400	High	28
-70,669308	8,725759	2408	2400	High	8
-70,668656	8,726195	2434	2400	High	34
-70,668129	8,726631	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,667136	8,727317	2331	2400	High	-69
-70,666579	8,728217	2332	2400	High	-68
-70,666645	8,728867	2294	2400	High	-106
-70,666895	8,729207	2294	2400	High	-106
-70,667364	8,729607	2317	2400	High	-83
-70,667926	8,730007	2315	2400	High	-85
-70,668301	8,73047	2375	2400	High	-25
-70,66846	8,73112	2375	2400	High	-25
-70,668432	8,73177	2429	2400	High	29
-70,668309	8,732204	2465	2400	High	65
-70,667969	8,732763	2465	2400	High	65
-70,667629	8,733353	2527	2400	High	127
-70,667632	8,734034	2518	2400	High	118
-70,667945	8,734436	2442	2400	High	42
-70,668414	8,734836	2434	2400	High	34
-70,668851	8,735144	2360	2400	High	-40
-70,669352	8,735668	2403	2400	High	3
-70,669663	8,735729	2421	2400	High	21
-70,670191	8,735417	2421	2400	High	21
-70,670718	8,734919	2398	2400	High	-2
-70,671714	8,734853	2431	2400	High	31
-70,67218	8,73482	2437	2400	High	37
-70,67274	8,734631	2437	2400	High	37
-70,673144	8,734568	2399	2400	High	-1
-70,67386	8,734471	2419	2400	High	19
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-70,674696	8,733632	2425	2400	High	25
-70,67544	8,732854	2446	2400	High	46
-70,676277	8,732138	2501	2400	High	101
-70,677053	8,731732	2419	2400	High	19
-70,678017	8,731511	2473	2400	High	73
-70,678607	8,731168	2393	2400	High	-7
-70,67904	8,730547	2458	2400	High	58
-70,679534	8,729677	2393	2400	High	-7
-70,680122	8,728962	2415	2400	High	15
-70,680307	8,728528	2382	2400	High	-18
-70,680366	8,727785	2360	2400	High	-40
-70,68114	8,726852	2392	2400	High	-8
-70,681915	8,726136	2392	2400	High	-8

-70,682692	8,725916	2423	2400	High	23
-70,683594	8,725757	2435	2400	High	35
-70,684652	8,725722	2477	2400	High	77
-70,685492	8,725656	2445	2400	High	45
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-70,686707	8,725929	2435	2400	High	35
-70,687206	8,725958	2435	2400	High	35
-70,64598	8,729515	2349	2400	High	-51
-70,646381	8,728801	2402	2400	High	2
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-70,64734	8,727496	2340	2400	High	-60
-70,647555	8,726845	2365	2400	High	-35
-70,647895	8,726255	2365	2400	High	-35
-70,648265	8,72551	2407	2400	High	7
-70,648947	8,724733	2410	2400	High	10
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-70,649814	8,723769	2445	2400	High	45
-70,650464	8,72293	2474	2400	High	74
-70,650929	8,722556	2439	2400	High	39
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-70,651518	8,722027	2425	2400	High	25
-70,651734	8,7215	2425	2400	High	25
-70,652042	8,720786	2370	2400	High	-30
-70,651914	8,720106	2360	2400	High	-40
-70,651819	8,719549	2372	2400	High	-28
-70,652034	8,718959	2372	2400	High	-28
-70,65203	8,718061	2357	2400	High	-43
-70,652027	8,717287	2356	2400	High	-44
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-70,653018	8,716261	2318	2400	High	-82
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-70,654012	8,715761	2315	2400	High	-85
-70,654478	8,715635	2315	2400	High	-85
-70,655101	8,715787	2376	2400	High	-24
-70,655382	8,715941	2376	2400	High	-24
-70,655912	8,716155	2436	2400	High	36
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-70,656814	8,716058	2438	2400	High	38
-70,657282	8,716304	2465	2400	High	65
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-70,658281	8,71695	2411	2400	High	11
-70,658749	8,717041	2411	2400	High	11
-70,65959	8,717254	2409	2400	High	9
-70,660244	8,717468	2409	2400	High	9
-70,660648	8,717342	2424	2400	High	24

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-70,661921	8,716624	2388	2400	High	-12
-70,662293	8,716282	2431	2400	High	31
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-70,662855	8,716589	2431	2400	High	31
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-70,657877	8,745319	2399	2400	High	-1
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-70,657562	8,744422	2454	2400	High	54
-70,657313	8,744299	2454	2400	High	54
-70,657127	8,744455	2454	2400	High	54
-70,656878	8,744487	2427	2400	High	27
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-70,65616	8,74418	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,655817	8,743841	2380	2400	High	-20
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-70,655749	8,742634	2413	2400	High	13
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-70,651656	8,739245	2486	2400	High	86
-70,651471	8,739587	2432	2400	High	32
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-70,651475	8,740423	2365	2400	High	-35
-70,651102	8,740641	2415	2400	High	15
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-70,649323	8,739627	2366	2400	High	-34
-70,648978	8,738947	2409	2400	High	9
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-70,648414	8,738144	2475	2400	High	75
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-70,647234	8,738707	2529	2400	High	129
-70,646924	8,739018	2495	2400	High	95
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-70,645779	8,74054	2374	2400	High	-26
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-70,643963	8,738133	2417	2400	High	17
-70,643683	8,738134	2412	2400	High	12
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-70,642374	8,737737	2365	2400	High	-35
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-70,642898	8,73662	2337	2400	High	-63
-70,643021	8,736186	2370	2400	High	-30
-70,643299	8,735658	2370	2400	High	-30
-70,643701	8,735099	2325	2400	High	-75
-70,644199	8,735128	2381	2400	High	-19
-70,644822	8,735249	2384	2400	High	-16
-70,64529	8,735588	2440	2400	High	40
-70,64554	8,735741	2418	2400	High	18
-70,645945	8,735832	2418	2400	High	18
-70,64635	8,7358	2425	2400	High	25
-70,64641	8,735459	2425	2400	High	25
-70,646471	8,735025	2399	2400	High	-1
-70,646656	8,734591	2399	2400	High	-1
-70,64684	8,734063	2361	2400	High	-39
-70,647522	8,733317	2386	2400	High	-14
-70,6478	8,732975	2386	2400	High	-14
-70,647798	8,732573	2379	2400	High	-21
-70,647641	8,732109	2379	2400	High	-21

-70,647484	8,731893	2426	2400	High	26
-70,646985	8,731616	2375	2400	High	-25
-70,646859	8,731307	2375	2400	High	-25
-70,646733	8,730905	2400	2400	High	0
-70,646327	8,730566	2400	2400	High	0
-70,646076	8,730196	2351	2400	High	-49
-70,664131	8,755185	2392	2400	High	-8
-70,664692	8,75526	2395	2400	High	-5
-70,665394	8,755598	2456	2400	High	56
-70,66594	8,755905	2429	2400	High	29
-70,666282	8,755811	2415	2400	High	15
-70,666374	8,755563	2415	2400	High	15
-70,666247	8,755083	2369	2400	High	-31
-70,665965	8,75462	2369	2400	High	-31
-70,665822	8,754017	2377	2400	High	-23
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-70,666489	8,75341	2396	2400	High	-4
-70,667391	8,753158	2422	2400	High	22
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-70,667885	8,752366	2403	2400	High	3
-70,667355	8,752214	2403	2400	High	3
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-70,665892	8,752236	2383	2400	High	-17
-70,665395	8,7523	2411	2400	High	11
-70,66493	8,752859	2411	2400	High	11
-70,664541	8,752892	2347	2400	High	-53
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-70,664057	8,752554	2347	2400	High	-53
-70,6639	8,752136	2347	2400	High	-53
-70,663804	8,751533	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,663753	8,750557	2422	2400	High	22
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-70,663058	8,748331	2429	2400	High	29
-70,662558	8,747853	2389	2400	High	-11
-70,662354	8,74756	2389	2400	High	-11
-70,661979	8,747097	2367	2400	High	-33
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-70,66269	8,746041	2460	2400	High	60
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-70,661817	8,745828	2488	2400	High	88
-70,661275	8,746419	2411	2400	High	11
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-70,660439	8,747444	2399	2400	High	-1

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-70,659506	8,765054	2334	2400	High	-66
-70,65944	8,764156	2338	2400	High	-62
-70,659344	8,763568	2340	2400	High	-60
-70,659496	8,762824	2364	2400	High	-36
-70,659462	8,762205	2364	2400	High	-36
-70,659397	8,761493	2384	2400	High	-16
-70,659115	8,761153	2394	2400	High	-6
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-70,65858	8,759948	2357	2400	High	-43
-70,658579	8,759576	2378	2400	High	-22
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-70,65767	8,75828	2388	2400	High	-12
-70,657078	8,758035	2382	2400	High	-18
-70,65605	8,757977	2406	2400	High	6
-70,655646	8,758165	2406	2400	High	6
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-70,65391	8,759597	2360	2400	High	-40
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-70,653066	8,758826	2369	2400	High	-31
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-70,653999	8,758636	2361	2400	High	-39
-70,654278	8,758356	2361	2400	High	-39
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-70,655239	8,757516	2344	2400	High	-56
-70,655767	8,757297	2376	2400	High	-24
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-70,656885	8,75658	2390	2400	High	-10
-70,657505	8,756144	2355	2400	High	-45
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-70,661142	8,754951	2356	2400	High	-44
-70,661795	8,754917	2391	2400	High	-9
-70,662605	8,754944	2387	2400	High	-13
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-70,648032	8,789073	2441	2400	High	41

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-70,648493	8,78774	2382	2400	High	-18
-70,648024	8,78737	2382	2400	High	-18
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-70,648954	8,78653	2417	2400	High	17
-70,649268	8,787086	2421	2400	High	21
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-70,650115	8,788476	2451	2400	High	51
-70,650428	8,78897	2467	2400	High	67
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-70,651985	8,788932	2463	2400	High	63
-70,65245	8,788527	2394	2400	High	-6
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-70,654344	8,787373	2450	2400	High	50
-70,654968	8,78768	2442	2400	High	42
-70,65531	8,787617	2442	2400	High	42
-70,655807	8,787336	2459	2400	High	59
-70,656273	8,78721	2472	2400	High	72
-70,657021	8,7873	2472	2400	High	72
-70,657832	8,787668	2455	2400	High	55
-70,658239	8,788192	2477	2400	High	77
-70,658612	8,788129	2477	2400	High	77
-70,659234	8,787847	2388	2400	High	-12
-70,659947	8,787256	2430	2400	High	30
-70,660661	8,78685	2420	2400	High	20
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-70,661779	8,786164	2385	2400	High	-15
-70,662307	8,785945	2419	2400	High	19
-70,662805	8,786035	2419	2400	High	19
-70,663491	8,786187	2407	2400	High	7
-70,664147	8,786587	2453	2400	High	53
-70,664709	8,786956	2420	2400	High	20
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-70,665927	8,787849	2465	2400	High	65
-70,666551	8,788125	2517	2400	High	117
-70,666925	8,788247	2517	2400	High	117
-70,66761	8,788399	2483	2400	High	83
-70,667702	8,787934	2483	2400	High	83
-70,667357	8,787471	2390	2400	High	-10
-70,666981	8,787039	2368	2400	High	-32
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-70,666573	8,786236	2389	2400	High	-11

-70,666447	8,785772	2389	2400	High	-11
-70,666133	8,785277	2327	2400	High	-73
-70,665976	8,784907	2327	2400	High	-73
-70,666255	8,78472	2405	2400	High	5
-70,666691	8,784749	2405	2400	High	5
-70,667066	8,784964	2405	2400	High	5
-70,667782	8,785084	2432	2400	High	32
-70,668466	8,784772	2445	2400	High	45
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-70,669708	8,784147	2441	2400	High	41
-70,67008	8,783681	2433	2400	High	33
-70,669984	8,783278	2433	2400	High	33
-70,669766	8,783279	2433	2400	High	33
-70,669393	8,783343	2437	2400	High	37
-70,668771	8,783532	2437	2400	High	37
-70,668304	8,783472	2413	2400	High	13
-70,667837	8,783381	2358	2400	High	-42
-70,667493	8,783166	2358	2400	High	-42
-70,666994	8,782858	2402	2400	High	2
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-70,665025	8,781133	2456	2400	High	56
-70,664558	8,781166	2467	2400	High	67
-70,66431	8,781384	2396	2400	High	-4
-70,663906	8,781602	2396	2400	High	-4
-70,663502	8,781635	2396	2400	High	-4
-70,663283	8,78145	2396	2400	High	-4
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-70,662349	8,781423	2378	2400	High	-22
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-70,661633	8,781333	2326	2400	High	-74
-70,661382	8,780963	2393	2400	High	-7
-70,66085	8,780284	2401	2400	High	1
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-70,659975	8,779514	2388	2400	High	-12
-70,659565	8,778308	2379	2400	High	-21
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-70,659188	8,777597	2420	2400	High	20
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-70,658099	8,777633	2418	2400	High	18
-70,657695	8,777851	2415	2400	High	15
-70,657447	8,7781	2373	2400	High	-27
-70,657136	8,778102	2373	2400	High	-27
-70,656793	8,778041	2352	2400	High	-48

-70,656698	8,777639	2363	2400	High	-37
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-70,656912	8,776802	2358	2400	High	-42
-70,656972	8,776399	2358	2400	High	-42
-70,656815	8,775997	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,65644	8,775751	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,656283	8,775442	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,65625	8,77504	2400	2400	High	0
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-70,656681	8,773892	2383	2400	High	-17
-70,656616	8,773335	2393	2400	High	-7
-70,65621	8,772903	2402	2400	High	2
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-70,655178	8,771979	2387	2400	High	-13
-70,65474	8,771423	2387	2400	High	-13
-70,654458	8,770991	2356	2400	High	-44
-70,654487	8,770619	2356	2400	High	-44
-70,65486	8,77037	2350	2400	High	-50
-70,655575	8,770243	2366	2400	High	-34
-70,655948	8,770055	2366	2400	High	-34
-70,656382	8,769527	2341	2400	High	-59
-70,656972	8,769307	2341	2400	High	-59
-70,657624	8,768964	2364	2400	High	-36
-70,6584	8,768496	2387	2400	High	-13
-70,658928	8,768029	2444	2400	High	44
-70,65877	8,767689	2442	2400	High	42
-70,65852	8,76735	2395	2400	High	-5
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-70,65889	8,766605	2412	2400	High	12
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-70,615994	8,773975	2383	2400	High	-17
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-70,618074	8,772573	2393	2400	High	-7
-70,618787	8,771796	2406	2400	High	6
-70,619466	8,770554	2350	2400	High	-50
-70,619743	8,76981	2377	2400	High	-23
-70,620049	8,768631	2347	2400	High	-53
-70,62061	8,76866	2369	2400	High	-31
-70,621296	8,768967	2388	2400	High	-12
-70,62192	8,769336	2388	2400	High	-12
-70,622234	8,769861	2414	2400	High	14
-70,622455	8,770634	2457	2400	High	57
-70,622553	8,771594	2487	2400	High	87
-70,622773	8,772119	2489	2400	High	89

-70,622995	8,773016	2418	2400	High	18
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-70,623654	8,774345	2439	2400	High	39
-70,623844	8,774964	2374	2400	High	-26
-70,623878	8,7758	2401	2400	High	1
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-70,623948	8,777627	2451	2400	High	51
-70,624325	8,778368	2445	2400	High	45
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-70,626977	8,77975	2381	2400	High	-19
-70,62738	8,779253	2363	2400	High	-37
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-70,628651	8,777978	2348	2400	High	-52
-70,629395	8,777386	2316	2400	High	-84
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-70,63169	8,77524	2350	2400	High	-50
-70,632184	8,774494	2379	2400	High	-21
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-70,633708	8,774085	2418	2400	High	18
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-70,635617	8,776275	2428	2400	High	28
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-70,636184	8,777852	2469	2400	High	69
-70,637401	8,778652	2414	2400	High	14
-70,638121	8,779392	2424	2400	High	24
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-70,639407	8,781617	2468	2400	High	68
-70,639319	8,782887	2492	2400	High	92
-70,639137	8,783909	2462	2400	High	62
-70,638613	8,78515	2487	2400	High	87
-70,63821	8,785679	2462	2400	High	62
-70,637904	8,786764	2521	2400	High	121
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-70,638758	8,789888	2280	2400	High	-120
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-70,640201	8,792421	2351	2400	High	-49
-70,640792	8,792171	2386	2400	High	-14
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-70,644802	8,790914	2404	2400	High	4
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-70,646977	8,789852	2372	2400	High	-28
-70,647847	8,789539	2346	2400	High	-54
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-70,60366	8,77968	2427	2400	High	27
-70,603101	8,779961	2427	2400	High	27
-70,6022	8,78046	2423	2400	High	23
-70,60161	8,78068	2424	2400	High	24
-70,601112	8,780775	2438	2400	High	38
-70,600614	8,78087	2438	2400	High	38
-70,599619	8,781184	2473	2400	High	73
-70,599186	8,781712	2536	2400	High	136
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-70,598507	8,783108	2549	2400	High	149
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-70,59777	8,785589	2495	2400	High	95
-70,597742	8,786332	2451	2400	High	51
-70,597808	8,787044	2451	2400	High	51
-70,597498	8,787355	2402	2400	High	2
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-70,594468	8,784984	2323	2400	High	-77
-70,594154	8,784366	2357	2400	High	-43

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-70,593776	8,783376	2404	2400	High	4
-70,593401	8,783068	2377	2400	High	-23
-70,592964	8,78276	2429	2400	High	29
-70,592526	8,782205	2361	2400	High	-39
-70,592336	8,781586	2396	2400	High	-4
-70,592364	8,780812	2376	2400	High	-24
-70,592611	8,780191	2355	2400	High	-45
-70,592857	8,779633	2355	2400	High	-45
-70,592635	8,778705	2351	2400	High	-49
-70,592975	8,778053	2392	2400	High	-8
-70,59375	8,777213	2348	2400	High	-52
-70,594369	8,776375	2349	2400	High	-51
-70,59443	8,776158	2328	2400	High	-72
-70,594395	8,775229	2334	2400	High	-66
-70,594422	8,774269	2328	2400	High	-72
-70,594511	8,773308	2314	2400	High	-86
-70,59485	8,772347	2376	2400	High	-24
-70,595406	8,771508	2333	2400	High	-67
-70,595778	8,770918	2383	2400	High	-17
-70,595806	8,770237	2359	2400	High	-41
-70,595677	8,769215	2341	2400	High	-59
-70,595549	8,768411	2365	2400	High	-35
-70,595483	8,767668	2372	2400	High	-28
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-70,595776	8,763362	2429	2400	High	29
-70,595899	8,762866	2385	2400	High	-15
-70,596239	8,762276	2385	2400	High	-15
-70,596329	8,761501	2412	2400	High	12
-70,596451	8,761036	2368	2400	High	-32
-70,596605	8,760664	2368	2400	High	-32
-70,597072	8,760538	2368	2400	High	-32
-70,597447	8,760815	2362	2400	High	-38
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-70,598167	8,761896	2366	2400	High	-34
-70,598263	8,762453	2431	2400	High	31
-70,598359	8,763103	2495	2400	High	95
-70,598517	8,763536	2495	2400	High	95
-70,598893	8,764092	2450	2400	High	50
-70,599299	8,764617	2470	2400	High	70
-70,599705	8,764925	2401	2400	High	1
-70,600143	8,765356	2401	2400	High	1
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-70,601244	8,768046	2478	2400	High	78
-70,601682	8,768601	2385	2400	High	-15
-70,60209	8,769312	2363	2400	High	-37
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-70,601723	8,770738	2505	2400	High	105
-70,601478	8,771668	2516	2400	High	116
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-70,602861	8,77479	2448	2400	High	48
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-70,604352	8,774041	2343	2400	High	-57
-70,604943	8,773945	2419	2400	High	19
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-70,606008	8,775489	2483	2400	High	83
-70,606477	8,776045	2399	2400	High	-1
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-70,608006	8,77675	2372	2400	High	-28
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-70,611799	8,77565	2390	2400	High	-10
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-70,613446	8,775024	2437	2400	High	37
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-70,597253	8,766607	2537	2600	High	-63
-70,597378	8,766669	2537	2600	High	-63
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-70,59942	8,770903	2604	2600	High	4
-70,599547	8,771553	2618	2600	High	18
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-70,599306	8,773319	2628	2600	High	28
-70,599308	8,773876	2629	2600	High	29
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-70,600068	8,776815	2644	2600	High	44
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-70,603307	8,777266	2561	2600	High	-39
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-70,604302	8,777014	2531	2600	High	-69
-70,604242	8,777355	2581	2600	High	-19
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-70,603154	8,777855	2561	2600	High	-39
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-70,599328	8,778645	2655	2600	High	55
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-70,597623	8,780232	2670	2600	High	70
-70,597221	8,780946	2665	2600	High	65
-70,597006	8,781535	2629	2600	High	29
-70,596978	8,782403	2616	2600	High	16
-70,597074	8,782898	2616	2600	High	16
-70,597014	8,783486	2595	2600	High	-5
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-70,596337	8,778039	2603	2600	High	3
-70,596552	8,777325	2571	2600	High	-29
-70,596892	8,776643	2542	2600	High	-58
-70,597075	8,775744	2522	2600	High	-78
-70,597381	8,774566	2545	2600	High	-55
-70,59747	8,773605	2538	2600	High	-62
-70,597714	8,772396	2530	2600	High	-70

-70,597834	8,771312	2535	2600	High	-65
-70,597953	8,770166	2568	2600	High	-32
-70,597888	8,769361	2501	2600	High	-99
-70,597698	8,768649	2530	2600	High	-70
-70,597447	8,768155	2530	2600	High	-70
-70,597227	8,767722	2534	2600	High	-66
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-70,597285	8,766793	2537	2600	High	-63
-70,611831	8,78299	2332	2400	High	-68
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-70,61083	8,781941	2372	2400	High	-28
-70,610702	8,781167	2420	2400	High	20
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-70,60995	8,780087	2347	2400	High	-53
-70,609731	8,779747	2347	2400	High	-53
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-70,633149	8,817087	2366	2400	High	-34
-70,632528	8,817368	2351	2400	High	-49
-70,632154	8,81737	2351	2400	High	-49
-70,631996	8,816813	2327	2400	High	-73
-70,631838	8,816164	2356	2400	High	-44
-70,631555	8,815577	2356	2400	High	-44
-70,631211	8,815237	2377	2400	High	-23
-70,630743	8,815085	2377	2400	High	-23
-70,630183	8,815056	2361	2400	High	-39
-70,629746	8,814872	2361	2400	High	-39
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-70,627967	8,813858	2366	2400	High	-34
-70,627439	8,814077	2362	2400	High	-38
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-70,626691	8,813925	2326	2400	High	-74
-70,62672	8,813523	2343	2400	High	-57
-70,627153	8,812932	2379	2400	High	-21
-70,627712	8,812558	2352	2400	High	-48
-70,628519	8,811966	2351	2400	High	-49
-70,628704	8,81147	2351	2400	High	-49
-70,628421	8,810852	2337	2400	High	-63
-70,628637	8,810356	2326	2400	High	-74
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-70,629691	8,809422	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,629845	8,808926	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,629625	8,808617	2397	2400	High	-3
-70,629282	8,808371	2360	2400	High	-40

-70,628596	8,808095	2309	2400	High	-91
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-70,628031	8,807106	2354	2400	High	-46
-70,627625	8,806768	2387	2400	High	-13
-70,626877	8,806554	2375	2400	High	-25
-70,62644	8,806432	2375	2400	High	-25
-70,625816	8,806125	2355	2400	High	-45
-70,625594	8,805166	2350	2400	High	-50
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-70,627362	8,803548	2381	2400	High	-19
-70,627577	8,80299	2381	2400	High	-19
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-70,62782	8,801719	2313	2400	High	-87
-70,628347	8,801159	2349	2400	High	-51
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-70,626193	8,799775	2326	2400	High	-74
-70,625754	8,799034	2364	2400	High	-36
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-70,624162	8,79808	2359	2400	High	-41
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-70,620979	8,796391	2353	2400	High	-47
-70,621257	8,795925	2393	2400	High	-7
-70,621285	8,795027	2392	2400	High	-8
-70,621439	8,794778	2392	2400	High	-8
-70,621593	8,794344	2413	2400	High	13
-70,621312	8,794129	2413	2400	High	13
-70,620782	8,794007	2387	2400	High	-13
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-70,620153	8,792523	2386	2400	High	-14

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-70,619373	8,792031	2422	2400	High	22
-70,618997	8,791692	2422	2400	High	22
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-70,618002	8,791882	2435	2400	High	35
-70,617412	8,792287	2422	2400	High	22
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-70,615858	8,792697	2347	2400	High	-53
-70,615576	8,792388	2347	2400	High	-53
-70,615573	8,791676	2339	2400	High	-61
-70,615725	8,790901	2345	2400	High	-55
-70,615938	8,789816	2372	2400	High	-28
-70,615966	8,789073	2377	2400	High	-23
-70,615777	8,788516	2406	2400	High	6
-70,615371	8,788239	2348	2400	High	-52
-70,615027	8,787931	2348	2400	High	-52
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-70,613932	8,786573	2394	2400	High	-6
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-70,612112	8,783298	2434	2400	High	34
-70,594214	8,820212	2340	2400	High	-60
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-70,595211	8,820455	2438	2400	High	38
-70,595617	8,820547	2415	2400	High	15
-70,595989	8,820359	2347	2400	High	-53
-70,59658	8,82014	2331	2400	High	-69
-70,597235	8,820385	2349	2400	High	-51
-70,597579	8,820724	2408	2400	High	8
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-70,601364	8,824796	2402	2400	High	2
-70,601953	8,824267	2343	2400	High	-57
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-70,609211	8,817825	2374	2400	High	-26
-70,609492	8,818227	2423	2400	High	23
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-70,610496	8,819833	2429	2400	High	29
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-70,612193	8,823449	2441	2400	High	41
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-70,621178	8,827684	2410	2400	High	10
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-70,622417	8,826285	2372	2400	High	-28
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-70,629705	8,826811	2399	2400	High	-1
-70,63033	8,827365	2464	2400	High	64
-70,630797	8,82727	2415	2400	High	15
-70,631075	8,826712	2346	2400	High	-54
-70,631197	8,826309	2346	2400	High	-54
-70,631413	8,825688	2376	2400	High	-24
-70,631783	8,824974	2344	2400	High	-56
-70,632218	8,824849	2394	2400	High	-6
-70,632716	8,824754	2394	2400	High	-6
-70,633338	8,824534	2347	2400	High	-53
-70,633835	8,824253	2377	2400	High	-23
-70,634177	8,824159	2377	2400	High	-23
-70,634614	8,824374	2365	2400	High	-35
-70,634958	8,824806	2438	2400	High	38
-70,635272	8,825517	2497	2400	High	97
-70,635492	8,825918	2435	2400	High	35
-70,63565	8,826351	2441	2400	High	41
-70,635992	8,826319	2441	2400	High	41
-70,636303	8,826132	2399	2400	High	-1
-70,636519	8,825697	2399	2400	High	-1
-70,636268	8,825234	2392	2400	High	-8
-70,636202	8,824429	2339	2400	High	-61
-70,636444	8,822972	2387	2400	High	-13
-70,636193	8,822509	2356	2400	High	-44

-70,635631	8,822062	2440	2400	High	40
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-70,633744	8,821435	2343	2400	High	-57
-70,63309	8,821268	2343	2400	High	-57
-70,632715	8,820883	2342	2400	High	-58
-70,632898	8,820123	2315	2400	High	-85
-70,633595	8,819392	2343	2400	High	-57
-70,634464	8,818661	2361	2400	High	-39
-70,634805	8,818241	2416	2400	High	16
-70,634586	8,818025	2416	2400	High	16
-70,634025	8,817904	2380	2400	High	-20
-70,71782	8,692392	2592	2600	High	-8
-70,717973	8,691988	2658	2600	High	58
-70,717939	8,691245	2660	2600	High	60
-70,717843	8,690688	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,71784	8,690038	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,717869	8,689542	2565	2600	High	-35
-70,726985	8,716195	2619	2600	High	19
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-70,726265	8,7153	2689	2600	High	89
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-70,720094	8,71347	2605	2600	High	5
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-70,722888	8,711847	2588	2600	High	-12
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-70,723616	8,707725	2673	2600	High	73
-70,723304	8,70751	2673	2600	High	73
-70,72265	8,707544	2645	2600	High	45

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-70,720808	8,706128	2624	2600	High	24
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-70,717833	8,702239	2602	2600	High	2
-70,717117	8,702211	2602	2600	High	2
-70,716712	8,701996	2626	2600	High	26
-70,716395	8,700852	2649	2600	High	49
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-70,717182	8,695894	2615	2600	High	15
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-70,709622	8,727313	2633	2600	High	33
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-70,710397	8,726752	2598	2600	High	-2
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-70,714908	8,726082	2623	2600	High	23
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-70,716124	8,726634	2655	2600	High	55
-70,716468	8,726911	2623	2600	High	23
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-70,720919	8,726952	2592	2600	High	-8
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-70,721595	8,725122	2611	2600	High	11
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-70,729802	8,723041	2653	2600	High	53
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-70,730861	8,72316	2652	2600	High	52
-70,731389	8,723003	2672	2600	High	72
-70,731637	8,722599	2633	2600	High	33
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-70,732565	8,721542	2632	2600	High	32
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-70,733855	8,717603	2636	2600	High	36
-70,732984	8,717886	2650	2600	High	50
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-70,731987	8,717643	2654	2600	High	54
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-70,695452	8,746267	2693	2600	High	93
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-70,699191	8,747055	2614	2600	High	14
-70,69941	8,74724	2671	2600	High	71
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-70,701271	8,739056	2666	2600	High	66
-70,701205	8,738221	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,701389	8,7376	2650	2600	High	50
-70,70176	8,736979	2637	2600	High	37
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-70,70157	8,736206	2619	2600	High	19
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-70,651568	8,726208	2595	2600	High	-5
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-70,652187	8,725493	2631	2600	High	31
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-70,652431	8,724284	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,65274	8,72388	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,653205	8,723476	2601	2600	High	1
-70,653296	8,722887	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,653356	8,722391	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,653666	8,722111	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,654163	8,721737	2601	2600	High	1
-70,654409	8,721148	2563	2600	High	-37
-70,654562	8,720466	2563	2600	High	-37
-70,654622	8,720032	2615	2600	High	15
-70,65518	8,719441	2570	2600	High	-30
-70,655521	8,71913	2611	2600	High	11
-70,65583	8,718571	2589	2600	High	-11
-70,656232	8,718136	2589	2600	High	-11
-70,656917	8,718226	2627	2600	High	27
-70,657635	8,718563	2604	2600	High	4
-70,658509	8,719086	2627	2600	High	27
-70,659444	8,719515	2588	2600	High	-12
-70,660255	8,719821	2616	2600	High	16
-70,66069	8,719603	2609	2600	High	9
-70,661093	8,719415	2537	2600	High	-63
-70,661777	8,719226	2559	2600	High	-41
-70,662275	8,719193	2556	2600	High	-44
-70,66262	8,719811	2594	2600	High	-6
-70,662716	8,720399	2594	2600	High	-6
-70,662967	8,720708	2591	2600	High	-9
-70,663373	8,721108	2591	2600	High	-9
-70,663438	8,721728	2632	2600	High	32
-70,663565	8,722253	2640	2600	High	40
-70,663816	8,722655	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,664347	8,72321	2620	2600	High	20
-70,665002	8,723455	2584	2600	High	-16
-70,665409	8,724042	2617	2600	High	17
-70,665257	8,724754	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,664793	8,725376	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,664172	8,725843	2559	2600	High	-41
-70,664019	8,726339	2545	2600	High	-55
-70,663772	8,726805	2545	2600	High	-55
-70,663182	8,72721	2599	2600	High	-1
-70,662656	8,72777	2625	2600	High	25
-70,662036	8,728423	2673	2600	High	73
-70,661604	8,729261	2673	2600	High	73
-70,661887	8,72991	2688	2600	High	88
-70,662482	8,730743	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,663232	8,731421	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,664137	8,732006	2559	2600	High	-41

-70,665104	8,732435	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,665263	8,733085	2653	2600	High	53
-70,665265	8,733642	2653	2600	High	53
-70,665143	8,734231	2691	2600	High	91
-70,665738	8,73491	2665	2600	High	65
-70,666519	8,735619	2614	2600	High	14
-70,667113	8,736204	2495	2600	High	-105
-70,667988	8,737068	2504	2600	High	-96
-70,668676	8,737715	2544	2600	High	-56
-70,66899	8,738271	2603	2600	High	3
-70,669394	8,738238	2603	2600	High	3
-70,669891	8,737957	2653	2600	High	53
-70,670419	8,737676	2626	2600	High	26
-70,670822	8,737396	2626	2600	High	26
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-70,672004	8,737205	2652	2600	High	52
-70,668367	8,755771	2556	2600	High	-44
-70,668412	8,755244	2547	2600	High	-53
-70,66852	8,755027	2547	2600	High	-53
-70,669156	8,754714	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,670151	8,754509	2553	2600	High	-47
-70,670633	8,754243	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,671534	8,753806	2624	2600	High	24
-70,67228	8,753663	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,672481	8,753306	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,672448	8,752919	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,67226	8,752595	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,671915	8,752178	2526	2600	High	-74
-70,671431	8,7517	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,671025	8,751408	2556	2600	High	-44
-70,670526	8,751255	2556	2600	High	-44
-70,670524	8,750806	2601	2600	High	1
-70,670475	8,750265	2637	2600	High	37
-70,670318	8,749925	2613	2600	High	13
-70,669959	8,749849	2613	2600	High	13
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-70,668715	8,749947	2607	2600	High	7
-70,668233	8,749996	2607	2600	High	7
-70,667936	8,749889	2607	2600	High	7
-70,66767	8,749549	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,667497	8,74907	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,667417	8,748637	2654	2600	High	54
-70,667275	8,748219	2654	2600	High	54
-70,667166	8,748142	2654	2600	High	54
-70,666855	8,748128	2659	2600	High	59
-70,6667	8,748439	2659	2600	High	59

-70,666453	8,748827	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,666018	8,748999	2576	2600	High	-24
-70,665628	8,748861	2576	2600	High	-24
-70,665424	8,748336	2612	2600	High	12
-70,665157	8,747965	2539	2600	High	-61
-70,664798	8,747549	2608	2600	High	8
-70,664313	8,747056	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,664202	8,746638	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,66434	8,746188	2554	2600	High	-46
-70,664571	8,745599	2554	2600	High	-46
-70,664613	8,744499	2624	2600	High	24
-70,664549	8,744205	2569	2600	High	-31
-70,664408	8,743896	2569	2600	High	-31
-70,664032	8,743279	2616	2600	High	16
-70,663843	8,742753	2625	2600	High	25
-70,663716	8,742351	2648	2600	High	48
-70,663296	8,742337	2648	2600	High	48
-70,662939	8,742633	2648	2600	High	48
-70,662366	8,743147	2633	2600	High	33
-70,661916	8,743598	2679	2600	High	79
-70,661421	8,744266	2622	2600	High	22
-70,661033	8,744531	2623	2600	High	23
-70,660535	8,744564	2623	2600	High	23
-70,660099	8,744395	2580	2600	High	-20
-70,659755	8,744103	2580	2600	High	-20
-70,659442	8,743701	2565	2600	High	-35
-70,659285	8,743361	2565	2600	High	-35
-70,659158	8,742727	2604	2600	High	4
-70,65914	8,742232	2604	2600	High	4
-70,658812	8,741955	2666	2600	High	66
-70,658501	8,742095	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,658098	8,742438	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,657554	8,742517	2552	2600	High	-48
-70,657256	8,741977	2600	2600	High	0
-70,657126	8,740832	2617	2600	High	17
-70,656876	8,740538	2546	2600	High	-54
-70,656719	8,740214	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,656593	8,739998	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,65611	8,739845	2555	2600	High	-45
-70,65583	8,739784	2555	2600	High	-45
-70,655781	8,739351	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,655012	8,737821	2690	2600	High	90
-70,655684	8,738515	2612	2600	High	12
-70,65537	8,73799	2612	2600	High	12
-70,655059	8,737899	2690	2600	High	90
-70,654717	8,738101	2612	2600	High	12

-70,654283	8,73849	2618	2600	High	18
-70,653863	8,738554	2618	2600	High	18
-70,653302	8,738402	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,652631	8,738002	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,652194	8,73757	2613	2600	High	13
-70,652036	8,737215	2589	2600	High	-11
-70,651693	8,736938	2648	2600	High	48
-70,651428	8,73697	2648	2600	High	48
-70,651132	8,736894	2620	2600	High	20
-70,650744	8,736957	2620	2600	High	20
-70,650386	8,737067	2590	2600	High	-10
-70,650244	8,736665	2590	2600	High	-10
-70,650056	8,736372	2590	2600	High	-10
-70,649604	8,736064	2629	2600	High	29
-70,649043	8,735943	2618	2600	High	18
-70,648624	8,736332	2593	2600	High	-7
-70,648392	8,73655	2593	2600	High	-7
-70,648127	8,736535	2593	2600	High	-7
-70,648079	8,736164	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,648233	8,735854	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,648666	8,735263	2538	2600	High	-62
-70,649084	8,734797	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,649564	8,734067	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,649903	8,733431	2600	2600	High	0
-70,649746	8,732982	2600	2600	High	0
-70,649479	8,73255	2528	2600	High	-72
-70,649461	8,732086	2528	2600	High	-72
-70,649553	8,731698	2529	2600	High	-71
-70,649629	8,731233	2618	2600	High	18
-70,668814	8,754762	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,669622	8,754511	2553	2600	High	-47
-70,671021	8,75404	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,670957	8,788399	2568	2600	High	-32
-70,67044	8,787767	2610	2600	High	10
-70,670034	8,787382	2543	2600	High	-57
-70,669782	8,786732	2586	2600	High	-14
-70,669889	8,786329	2586	2600	High	-14
-70,670463	8,785816	2602	2600	High	2
-70,671238	8,785131	2546	2600	High	-54
-70,67192	8,784586	2618	2600	High	18
-70,672182	8,784043	2622	2600	High	22
-70,672446	8,783701	2561	2600	High	-39
-70,673034	8,783033	2633	2600	High	33
-70,673468	8,782659	2608	2600	High	8
-70,673342	8,782304	2608	2600	High	8
-70,67289	8,782089	2574	2600	High	-26

-70,672251	8,781999	2658	2600	High	58
-70,672755	8,783359	2561	2600	High	-39
-70,671753	8,781908	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,671346	8,781585	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,67083	8,780906	2609	2600	High	9
-70,67061	8,780411	2671	2600	High	71
-70,670282	8,780227	2675	2600	High	75
-70,669956	8,780399	2675	2600	High	75
-70,669429	8,78085	2641	2600	High	41
-70,669088	8,78127	2576	2600	High	-24
-70,668592	8,781597	2588	2600	High	-12
-70,667954	8,781739	2588	2600	High	-12
-70,667595	8,781524	2522	2600	High	-78
-70,667264	8,780596	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,667076	8,780257	2570	2600	High	-30
-70,666684	8,779763	2570	2600	High	-30
-70,66606	8,779363	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,665654	8,779009	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,665573	8,77839	2624	2600	High	24
-70,665369	8,77788	2691	2600	High	91
-70,664995	8,777804	2691	2600	High	91
-70,664653	8,778007	2633	2600	High	33
-70,664219	8,778442	2638	2600	High	38
-70,663879	8,778939	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,663508	8,779421	2592	2600	High	-8
-70,663228	8,779546	2592	2600	High	-8
-70,663071	8,779345	2592	2600	High	-8
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-70,662554	8,778511	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,658138	8,772461	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,662194	8,778157	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,661913	8,777786	2569	2600	High	-31
-70,66189	8,776223	2595	2600	High	-5
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-70,659085	8,775368	2590	2600	High	-10
-70,65888	8,774811	2590	2600	High	-10
-70,65889	8,773557	2629	2600	High	29
-70,658826	8,773186	2629	2600	High	29
-70,658606	8,77266	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,658355	8,772259	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,658478	8,771856	2576	2600	High	-24
-70,658772	8,771514	2617	2600	High	17

-70,659377	8,771031	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,659826	8,770611	2611	2600	High	11
-70,660416	8,770283	2559	2600	High	-41
-70,66082	8,77008	2591	2600	High	-9
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-70,661331	8,769397	2606	2600	High	6
-70,661701	8,768807	2606	2600	High	6
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-70,661244	8,767539	2559	2600	High	-41
-70,661367	8,767074	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,66149	8,766686	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,661472	8,766253	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,661298	8,765495	2590	2600	High	-10
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-70,661586	8,763837	2607	2600	High	7
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-70,661953	8,76238	2545	2600	High	-55
-70,661842	8,761931	2541	2600	High	-59
-70,661685	8,761498	2541	2600	High	-59
-70,661558	8,761065	2583	2600	High	-17
-70,661275	8,760354	2611	2600	High	11
-70,661039	8,759937	2545	2600	High	-55
-70,660958	8,759086	2550	2600	High	-50
-70,661127	8,758698	2560	2600	High	-40
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-70,662744	8,758134	2602	2600	High	2
-70,663367	8,75844	2600	2600	High	0
-70,663833	8,758175	2609	2600	High	9
-70,664391	8,757631	2552	2600	High	-48
-70,665341	8,757689	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,665933	8,757887	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,667118	8,758362	2618	2600	High	18
-70,668006	8,758621	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,668474	8,758759	2656	2600	High	56
-70,669068	8,759251	2631	2600	High	31
-70,669365	8,75973	2684	2600	High	84
-70,66988	8,75996	2611	2600	High	11
-70,670331	8,759927	2611	2600	High	11
-70,670424	8,759679	2626	2600	High	26
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-70,669966	8,758303	2589	2600	High	-11
-70,669465	8,757624	2557	2600	High	-43
-70,668949	8,757007	2603	2600	High	3

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-70,63649	8,819271	2563	2600	High	-37
-70,637017	8,818712	2543	2600	High	-57
-70,637388	8,818029	2600	2600	High	0
-70,637384	8,817285	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,637756	8,816788	2570	2600	High	-30
-70,637661	8,816386	2570	2600	High	-30
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-70,636444	8,815772	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,636163	8,815587	2537	2600	High	-63
-70,63613	8,815185	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,63619	8,81472	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,636156	8,814163	2586	2600	High	-14
-70,63569	8,814258	2586	2600	High	-14
-70,635286	8,814538	2607	2600	High	7
-70,634727	8,81485	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,634323	8,814852	2547	2600	High	-53
-70,633855	8,814699	2547	2600	High	-53
-70,633417	8,814268	2537	2600	High	-63
-70,633197	8,81368	2560	2600	High	-40
-70,63313	8,812783	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,632816	8,81201	2563	2600	High	-37
-70,632253	8,811486	2563	2600	High	-37
-70,632281	8,810866	2550	2600	High	-50
-70,632622	8,810338	2532	2600	High	-68
-70,632744	8,809811	2532	2600	High	-68
-70,633114	8,809128	2580	2600	High	-20
-70,632987	8,808509	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,632299	8,807831	2589	2600	High	-11
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-70,63114	8,806226	2534	2600	High	-66
-70,631323	8,805296	2613	2600	High	13
-70,631197	8,805049	2578	2600	High	-22
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-70,630513	8,805083	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,630172	8,805425	2506	2600	High	-94
-70,629921	8,805023	2553	2600	High	-47
-70,630044	8,80462	2553	2600	High	-47
-70,630478	8,804247	2565	2600	High	-35
-70,631223	8,803779	2565	2600	High	-35
-70,632247	8,803062	2600	2600	High	0
-70,632899	8,802502	2553	2600	High	-47
-70,633425	8,801973	2567	2600	High	-33
-70,633579	8,801415	2567	2600	High	-33
-70,633577	8,801013	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,633077	8,800612	2577	2600	High	-23

-70,632672	8,800614	2583	2600	High	-17
-70,632394	8,800956	2583	2600	High	-17
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-70,631181	8,801364	2548	2600	High	-52
-70,630993	8,801117	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,630929	8,800683	2549	2600	High	-51
-70,631051	8,800002	2534	2600	High	-66
-70,631421	8,79935	2581	2600	High	-19
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-70,63098	8,798082	2537	2600	High	-63
-70,630387	8,797837	2599	2600	High	-1
-70,629763	8,797344	2599	2600	High	-1
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-70,628737	8,79772	2611	2600	High	11
-70,628052	8,797723	2611	2600	High	11
-70,627336	8,797726	2584	2600	High	-16
-70,627023	8,797418	2530	2600	High	-70
-70,626804	8,79714	2530	2600	High	-70
-70,626616	8,796738	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,62652	8,796119	2617	2600	High	17
-70,626332	8,795903	2617	2600	High	17
-70,625896	8,795843	2599	2600	High	-1
-70,625273	8,795908	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,624588	8,795911	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,624215	8,795819	2571	2600	High	-29
-70,62387	8,795387	2614	2600	High	14
-70,623618	8,794769	2551	2600	High	-49
-70,623428	8,793903	2560	2600	High	-40
-70,623299	8,793005	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,62308	8,792604	2601	2600	High	1
-70,622643	8,792358	2557	2600	High	-43
-70,622206	8,792143	2557	2600	High	-43
-70,621862	8,791742	2533	2600	High	-67
-70,621766	8,791185	2593	2600	High	-7
-70,621516	8,790907	2593	2600	High	-7
-70,620923	8,790507	2516	2600	High	-84
-70,62064	8,790044	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,619859	8,789335	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,619327	8,788687	2645	2600	High	45
-70,618798	8,78872	2645	2600	High	45
-70,618114	8,789064	2574	2600	High	-26
-70,61774	8,788817	2522	2600	High	-78
-70,617114	8,788201	2567	2600	High	-33
-70,616988	8,787768	2525	2600	High	-75
-70,61689	8,786622	2540	2600	High	-60

-70,616855	8,785786	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,616323	8,785107	2625	2600	High	25
-70,616011	8,784954	2589	2600	High	-11
-70,615201	8,784895	2533	2600	High	-67
-70,614669	8,784309	2588	2600	High	-12
-70,614199	8,783506	2585	2600	High	-15
-70,613698	8,78292	2511	2600	High	-89
-70,613261	8,782519	2587	2600	High	-13
-70,612573	8,781841	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,612072	8,781162	2547	2600	High	-53
-70,611975	8,780388	2539	2600	High	-61
-70,611879	8,779831	2539	2600	High	-61
-70,611784	8,779336	2579	2600	High	-21
-70,611687	8,778562	2558	2600	High	-42
-70,612617	8,777722	2551	2600	High	-49
-70,613362	8,77713	2613	2600	High	13
-70,614328	8,777281	2614	2600	High	14
-70,615043	8,777216	2596	2600	High	-4
-70,615758	8,776903	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,616283	8,775941	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,616748	8,775412	2526	2600	High	-74
-70,617588	8,775285	2552	2600	High	-48
-70,618179	8,775158	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,618955	8,774752	2607	2600	High	7
-70,619357	8,7741	2552	2600	High	-48
-70,619852	8,773355	2562	2600	High	-38
-70,620224	8,773137	2562	2600	High	-38
-70,620599	8,773259	2580	2600	High	-20
-70,621038	8,774062	2620	2600	High	20
-70,621415	8,774773	2613	2600	High	13
-70,621824	8,775979	2660	2600	High	60
-70,621953	8,776845	2697	2600	High	97
-70,621924	8,777434	2729	2600	High	129
-70,621742	8,778519	2741	2600	High	141
-70,6219	8,779106	2709	2600	High	109
-70,622526	8,779847	2615	2600	High	15
-70,622809	8,780558	2613	2600	High	13
-70,622875	8,78127	2641	2600	High	41
-70,62322	8,781826	2574	2600	High	-26
-70,624	8,782256	2621	2600	High	21
-70,624529	8,782285	2621	2600	High	21
-70,625028	8,782561	2585	2600	High	-15
-70,625623	8,783302	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,626028	8,783424	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,626835	8,782739	2542	2600	High	-58
-70,627143	8,781964	2552	2600	High	-48

-70,628106	8,781464	2607	2600	High	7
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-70,629193	8,780871	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,629781	8,780187	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,630648	8,7791	2594	2600	High	-6
-70,631329	8,778137	2614	2600	High	14
-70,632197	8,777266	2621	2600	High	21
-70,632816	8,776613	2552	2600	High	-48
-70,633285	8,777075	2596	2600	High	-4
-70,63332	8,77788	2613	2600	High	13
-70,633789	8,778467	2589	2600	High	-11
-70,634602	8,779083	2603	2600	High	3
-70,635195	8,779606	2656	2600	High	56
-70,63582	8,780006	2615	2600	High	15
-70,63635	8,78019	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,636663	8,780684	2640	2600	High	40
-70,63673	8,781799	2679	2600	High	79
-70,63658	8,783131	2630	2600	High	30
-70,636555	8,784524	2596	2600	High	-4
-70,636558	8,785175	2554	2600	High	-46
-70,636281	8,785764	2531	2600	High	-69
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-70,635011	8,78738	2637	2600	High	37
-70,634955	8,788805	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,635114	8,789517	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,635245	8,790972	2639	2600	High	39
-70,635372	8,791498	2686	2600	High	86
-70,635623	8,79193	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,636562	8,793103	2620	2600	High	20
-70,637375	8,793966	2611	2600	High	11
-70,637969	8,794552	2562	2600	High	-38
-70,638374	8,794581	2562	2600	High	-38
-70,639775	8,794482	2603	2600	High	3
-70,640147	8,794233	2603	2600	High	3
-70,641296	8,793547	2554	2600	High	-46
-70,642508	8,792984	2630	2600	High	30
-70,643192	8,792764	2582	2600	High	-18
-70,644063	8,792605	2589	2600	High	-11
-70,645276	8,792538	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,646022	8,792163	2631	2600	High	31
-70,646829	8,791726	2570	2600	High	-30
-70,647419	8,791259	2639	2600	High	39
-70,648226	8,790667	2629	2600	High	29
-70,648942	8,790819	2626	2600	High	26
-70,650157	8,79103	2611	2600	High	11
-70,651341	8,791118	2617	2600	High	17

-70,651995	8,79127	2702	2600	High	102
-70,652523	8,790989	2608	2600	High	8
-70,653019	8,790522	2632	2600	High	32
-70,653857	8,78993	2637	2600	High	37
-70,65454	8,789556	2580	2600	High	-20
-70,655505	8,78949	2604	2600	High	4
-70,656096	8,789332	2604	2600	High	4
-70,656719	8,78936	2629	2600	High	29
-70,657063	8,789699	2694	2600	High	94
-70,657346	8,790318	2658	2600	High	58
-70,657628	8,790905	2688	2600	High	88
-70,657908	8,790903	2688	2600	High	88
-70,658498	8,790498	2654	2600	High	54
-70,659244	8,790123	2632	2600	High	32
-70,660019	8,789532	2596	2600	High	-4
-70,660794	8,78863	2572	2600	High	-28
-70,661291	8,788504	2616	2600	High	16
-70,66185	8,788254	2616	2600	High	16
-70,662348	8,788097	2642	2600	High	42
-70,662754	8,788343	2642	2600	High	42
-70,662912	8,78893	2694	2600	High	94
-70,663255	8,789115	2659	2600	High	59
-70,663784	8,789019	2661	2600	High	61
-70,664593	8,789016	2676	2600	High	76
-70,665309	8,788889	2676	2600	High	76
-70,665932	8,789072	2676	2600	High	76
-70,666524	8,789224	2626	2600	High	26
-70,667022	8,789222	2626	2600	High	26
-70,667458	8,78922	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,66774	8,789497	2581	2600	High	-19
-70,667807	8,790581	2608	2600	High	8
-70,667654	8,791232	2608	2600	High	8
-70,667657	8,791944	2609	2600	High	9
-70,667629	8,792626	2641	2600	High	41
-70,667414	8,793339	2664	2600	High	64
-70,667168	8,794021	2648	2600	High	48
-70,666984	8,794642	2684	2600	High	84
-70,666986	8,795075	2684	2600	High	84
-70,667423	8,79529	2644	2600	High	44
-70,667795	8,794824	2644	2600	High	44
-70,668167	8,794636	2654	2600	High	54
-70,668789	8,79451	2620	2600	High	20
-70,668851	8,794262	2620	2600	High	20
-70,668848	8,793797	2620	2600	High	20
-70,669064	8,793332	2585	2600	High	-15
-70,669591	8,79271	2629	2600	High	29

-70,670272	8,791964	2580	2600	High	-20
-70,670955	8,791465	2637	2600	High	37
-70,67192	8,79143	2680	2600	High	80
-70,672168	8,791243	2616	2600	High	16
-70,67198	8,790872	2605	2600	High	5
-70,671604	8,790471	2605	2600	High	5
-70,671291	8,790039	2580	2600	High	-20
-70,671195	8,78942	2524	2600	High	-76
-70,596008	8,823001	2610	2600	High	10
-70,59643	8,823041	2618	2600	High	18
-70,597063	8,823206	2618	2600	High	18
-70,597528	8,823707	2603	2600	High	3
-70,59791	8,824334	2676	2600	High	76
-70,598337	8,825423	2678	2600	High	78
-70,599014	8,826049	2650	2600	High	50
-70,600112	8,826631	2644	2600	High	44
-70,601083	8,826962	2552	2600	High	-48
-70,601757	8,827043	2540	2600	High	-60
-70,602262	8,826789	2574	2600	High	-26
-70,602765	8,826116	2522	2600	High	-78
-70,636218	8,823624	2311	2400	High	-89
-70,603436	8,825275	2534	2600	High	-66
-70,604275	8,824475	2517	2600	High	-83
-70,605579	8,823924	2593	2600	High	-7
-70,605999	8,823462	2508	2600	High	-92
-70,606756	8,823039	2574	2600	High	-26
-70,606668	8,822327	2551	2600	High	-49
-70,607087	8,821738	2568	2600	High	-32
-70,607886	8,821315	2568	2600	High	-32
-70,608561	8,821396	2594	2600	High	-6
-70,608688	8,821689	2594	2600	High	-6
-70,608693	8,822821	2626	2600	High	26
-70,608781	8,823533	2634	2600	High	34
-70,609289	8,824202	2599	2600	High	-1
-70,609882	8,824703	2602	2600	High	2
-70,610347	8,82512	2602	2600	High	2
-70,610814	8,825789	2605	2600	High	5
-70,611321	8,826247	2554	2600	High	-46
-70,611995	8,826161	2554	2600	High	-46
-70,612752	8,825696	2565	2600	High	-35
-70,61355	8,82519	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,614267	8,825103	2624	2600	High	24
-70,615196	8,825602	2619	2600	High	19
-70,615576	8,825726	2574	2600	High	-26
-70,615452	8,826314	2591	2600	High	-9
-70,615118	8,827153	2654	2600	High	54

-70,615332	8,827823	2654	2600	High	54
-70,615924	8,82824	2624	2600	High	24
-70,616053	8,828742	2624	2600	High	24
-70,616351	8,829412	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,616983	8,829493	2598	2600	High	-2
-70,617741	8,82928	2591	2600	High	-9
-70,61829	8,829613	2652	2600	High	52
-70,618587	8,830073	2652	2600	High	52
-70,618886	8,83091	2612	2600	High	12
-70,619603	8,831033	2562	2600	High	-38
-70,620361	8,830862	2562	2600	High	-38
-70,620991	8,830482	2597	2600	High	-3
-70,62196	8,830394	2542	2600	High	-58
-70,622169	8,829806	2568	2600	High	-32
-70,622546	8,829469	2520	2600	High	-80
-70,623178	8,829257	2562	2600	High	-38
-70,62364	8,828961	2562	2600	High	-38
-70,624228	8,828497	2545	2600	High	-55
-70,624819	8,828621	2561	2600	High	-39
-70,625495	8,828995	2574	2600	High	-26
-70,626086	8,829286	2574	2600	High	-26
-70,627183	8,829617	2599	2600	High	-1
-70,627648	8,829824	2599	2600	High	-1
-70,628282	8,830241	2579	2600	High	-21
-70,628535	8,83024	2579	2600	High	-21
-70,628912	8,829819	2584	2600	High	-16
-70,629415	8,829271	2551	2600	High	-49
-70,626697	8,829346	2557	2600	High	-43
-70,629921	8,829311	2578	2600	High	-22
-70,630597	8,829644	2632	2600	High	32
-70,631399	8,829892	2601	2600	High	1
-70,631777	8,82968	2601	2600	High	1
-70,632029	8,829344	2531	2600	High	-69
-70,632278	8,828588	2581	2600	High	-19
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-70,632735	8,826993	2501	2600	High	-99
-70,633197	8,826698	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,633621	8,827157	2611	2600	High	11
-70,633792	8,827743	2618	2600	High	18
-70,63388	8,828539	2627	2600	High	27
-70,634051	8,829209	2653	2600	High	53
-70,634265	8,829963	2659	2600	High	59
-70,634899	8,830379	2622	2600	High	22
-70,635196	8,830755	2653	2600	High	53
-70,635409	8,831258	2643	2600	High	43
-70,635703	8,831131	2598	2600	High	-2

-70,636587	8,830749	2591	2600	High	-9
-70,636923	8,830413	2543	2600	High	-57
-70,637215	8,829741	2588	2600	High	-12
-70,637085	8,829028	2577	2600	High	-23
-70,636997	8,828274	2526	2600	High	-74
-70,637754	8,827768	2558	2600	High	-42
-70,638343	8,827682	2573	2600	High	-27
-70,639061	8,827846	2586	2600	High	-14
-70,639606	8,827299	2620	2600	High	20
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-70,641038	8,826999	2585	2600	High	-15
-70,64171	8,826619	2613	2600	High	13
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-70,643223	8,825606	2612	2600	High	12
-70,643853	8,825142	2616	2600	High	16
-70,6444	8,824804	2616	2600	High	16
-70,644398	8,824469	2596	2600	High	-4
-70,644102	8,824177	2596	2600	High	-4
-70,643471	8,824347	2613	2600	High	13
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-70,642502	8,824603	2552	2600	High	-48
-70,641912	8,824606	2554	2600	High	-46
-70,641618	8,824691	2554	2600	High	-46
-70,641155	8,824861	2550	2600	High	-50
-70,64069	8,824611	2550	2600	High	-50
-70,640226	8,824529	2585	2600	High	-15
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-70,639001	8,823948	2558	2600	High	-42
-70,638113	8,823113	2571	2600	High	-29
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-70,638315	8,821268	2572	2600	High	-28
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-70,637258	8,820392	2595	2600	High	-5
-70,636624	8,819976	2561	2600	High	-39
-70,71402	8,727602	2802	2800	High	2
-70,714559	8,728036	2867	2800	High	67
-70,715073	8,728568	2813	2800	High	13
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-70,716099	8,728927	2839	2800	High	39
-70,716492	8,72941	2808	2800	High	8
-70,716834	8,729676	2863	2800	High	63
-70,717248	8,729455	2809	2800	High	9
-70,717685	8,729138	2809	2800	High	9
-70,718196	8,728869	2845	2800	High	45
-70,718658	8,728576	2785	2800	High	-15

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-70,720173	8,729175	2841	2800	High	41
-70,720345	8,729514	2841	2800	High	41
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-70,722318	8,728971	2826	2800	High	26
-70,722853	8,728605	2777	2800	High	-23
-70,723243	8,728603	2801	2800	High	1
-70,723488	8,728821	2841	2800	High	41
-70,72371	8,729378	2841	2800	High	41
-70,723957	8,729959	2783	2800	High	-17
-70,724276	8,730418	2819	2800	High	19
-70,724862	8,730731	2828	2800	High	28
-70,725178	8,730366	2791	2800	High	-9
-70,72537	8,729783	2791	2800	High	-9
-70,725905	8,72944	2810	2800	High	10
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-70,726293	8,728929	2864	2800	High	64
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-70,725803	8,728398	2819	2800	High	19
-70,726116	8,727523	2798	2800	High	-2
-70,726332	8,726818	2822	2800	High	22
-70,726671	8,726307	2822	2800	High	22
-70,727012	8,726087	2764	2800	High	-36
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-70,729106	8,725519	2834	2800	High	34
-70,729764	8,725347	2788	2800	High	-12
-70,730837	8,725293	2785	2800	High	-15
-70,731447	8,725484	2844	2800	High	44
-70,73174	8,725556	2844	2800	High	44
-70,732131	8,725651	2865	2800	High	65
-70,732446	8,725334	2822	2800	High	22
-70,732735	8,724532	2782	2800	High	-18
-70,733293	8,723802	2834	2800	High	34
-70,730398	8,725295	2788	2800	High	-12
-70,733998	8,723338	2834	2800	High	34
-70,734679	8,722922	2864	2800	High	64
-70,735458	8,722603	2823	2800	High	23
-70,73609	8,722309	2823	2800	High	23
-70,73648	8,722065	2784	2800	High	-16
-70,73721	8,721746	2821	2800	High	21
-70,737574	8,721332	2821	2800	High	21
-70,737912	8,720699	2786	2800	High	-14

-70,737811	8,719875	2780	2800	High	-20
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-70,738927	8,718632	2832	2800	High	32
-70,739315	8,718267	2832	2800	High	32
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-70,741157	8,715735	2796	2800	High	-4
-70,741445	8,714836	2833	2800	High	33
-70,74137	8,714399	2796	2800	High	-4
-70,741271	8,713963	2796	2800	High	-4
-70,740686	8,714063	2772	2800	High	-28
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-70,737569	8,715072	2816	2800	High	16
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-70,735889	8,715565	2778	2800	High	-22
-70,734767	8,715667	2789	2800	High	-11
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-70,73228	8,715775	2813	2800	High	13
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-70,731353	8,715658	2799	2800	High	-1
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-70,728082	8,714945	2794	2800	High	-6
-70,727715	8,714559	2791	2800	High	-9
-70,727127	8,713955	2791	2800	High	-9
-70,726636	8,713326	2789	2800	High	-11
-70,726293	8,712988	2789	2800	High	-11
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-70,725536	8,712749	2836	2800	High	36
-70,725363	8,712313	2801	2800	High	1
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-70,726039	8,710684	2821	2800	High	21
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-70,725465	8,707824	2873	2800	High	73

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-70,725114	8,705908	2868	2800	High	68
-70,724676	8,70608	2868	2800	High	68
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-70,72302	8,706452	2753	2800	High	-47
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-70,721953	8,702502	2775	2800	High	-25
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-70,719137	8,699918	2799	2800	High	-1
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-70,720052	8,692053	2797	2800	High	-3
-70,720465	8,691638	2832	2800	High	32
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-70,665058	8,740437	2758	2800	High	-42
-70,664569	8,740197	2832	2800	High	32
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-70,662254	8,740668	2818	2800	High	18
-70,661745	8,741228	2833	2800	High	33
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-70,660791	8,740747	2782	2800	High	-18
-70,660471	8,739948	2825	2800	High	25
-70,660056	8,739853	2789	2800	High	-11
-70,659226	8,739808	2793	2800	High	-7

-70,658665	8,73964	2713	2800	High	-87
-70,658174	8,738939	2773	2800	High	-27
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-70,655913	8,735188	2855	2800	High	55
-70,655352	8,735069	2870	2800	High	70
-70,654866	8,735459	2814	2800	High	14
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-70,652062	8,730182	2769	2800	High	-31
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-70,656176	8,722739	2774	2800	High	-26
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-70,659756	8,721777	2773	2800	High	-27
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-70,659743	8,724228	2833	2800	High	33
-70,659673	8,724932	2837	2800	High	37
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-70,659489	8,72748	2863	2800	High	63
-70,659175	8,728258	2847	2800	High	47
-70,658764	8,729061	2835	2800	High	35
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-70,65826	8,730955	2879	2800	High	79
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-70,659731	8,73272	2803	2800	High	3
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-70,680325	8,740321	2945	2800	High	145
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-70,682173	8,744584	2815	2800	High	15
-70,682323	8,745311	2815	2800	High	15
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-70,683568	8,745596	2831	2800	High	31
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-70,684814	8,746125	2818	2800	High	18
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-70,673014	8,760723	2806	2800	High	6
-70,672646	8,760288	2779	2800	High	-21
-70,672351	8,759659	2779	2800	High	-21
-70,672275	8,759174	2803	2800	High	3
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-70,671976	8,757671	2763	2800	High	-37
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-70,672655	8,756721	2797	2800	High	-3
-70,673581	8,756669	2808	2800	High	8
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-70,675886	8,754014	2756	2800	High	-44
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-70,675319	8,752536	2781	2800	High	-19
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-70,674161	8,750018	2818	2800	High	18
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-70,671419	8,747676	2869	2800	High	69
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-70,669541	8,74766	2776	2800	High	-24
-70,667999	8,746381	2799	2800	High	-1
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-70,668636	8,746949	2799	2800	High	-1
-70,668881	8,747287	2776	2800	High	-24
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-70,673141	8,78637	2801	2800	High	1
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-70,667717	8,778824	2695	2800	High	-105
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-70,666101	8,777423	2700	2800	High	-100
-70,665855	8,777036	2762	2800	High	-38
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-70,635267	8,796181	2771	2800	High	-29
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-70,631254	8,79336	2797	2800	High	-3
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-70,630156	8,79334	2807	2800	High	7

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-70,628963	8,793807	2763	2800	High	-37
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-70,627329	8,793814	2744	2800	High	-56
-70,627035	8,793548	2777	2800	High	-23
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-70,62635	8,793114	2777	2800	High	-23
-70,625471	8,792972	2763	2800	High	-37
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-70,625294	8,79142	2726	2800	High	-74
-70,625048	8,790912	2781	2800	High	-19
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-70,622601	8,789248	2766	2800	High	-34
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-70,618527	8,777885	2762	2800	High	-38
-70,619502	8,77776	2763	2800	High	-37
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-70,621823	8,784083	2809	2800	High	9
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-70,624757	8,78572	2826	2800	High	26
-70,625147	8,785743	2826	2800	High	26
-70,625829	8,785497	2826	2800	High	26
-70,626851	8,784886	2768	2800	High	-32
-70,628114	8,78374	2761	2800	High	-39
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-70,632099	8,780205	2781	2800	High	-19
-70,631711	8,780643	2795	2800	High	-5
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-70,63263	8,790078	2886	2800	High	86
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-70,640434	8,795322	2757	2800	High	-43
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-70,642411	8,795386	2755	2800	High	-45
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-70,60379	8,82774	2767	2800	High	-33
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-70,624982	8,831628	2778	2800	High	-22
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-70,632707	8,835283	2823	2800	High	23
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-70,633418	8,836105	2777	2800	High	-23
-70,633685	8,835836	2777	2800	High	-23
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-70,635021	8,834593	2814	2800	High	14
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-70,647782	8,823982	2774	2800	High	-26
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-70,648183	8,820948	2765	2800	High	-35
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-70,693355	8,794202	3354	3400	High	-46
-70,695786	8,792468	3340	3400	High	-60
-70,696029	8,792273	3340	3400	High	-60
-70,696149	8,791908	3366	3400	High	-34
-70,695444	8,79247	3340	3400	High	-60
-70,696415	8,791422	3347	3400	High	-53
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-70,697651	8,768123	3587	3600	High	-13
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-70,697252	8,766257	3616	3600	High	16
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-70,69637	8,76546	3605	3600	High	5
-70,695761	8,765414	3613	3600	High	13
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-70,695124	8,764859	3675	3600	High	75
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-70,69441	8,763431	3638	3600	High	38
-70,694067	8,763117	3638	3600	High	38
-70,693822	8,762754	3647	3600	High	47
-70,69372	8,761808	3620	3600	High	20
-70,693645	8,761444	3620	3600	High	20
-70,693497	8,761081	3605	3600	High	5
-70,693105	8,760792	3605	3600	High	5
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-70,689236	8,757388	3588	3600	High	-12
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-70,688555	8,757609	3546	3600	High	-54
-70,688824	8,757802	3588	3600	High	-12
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-70,689732	8,758987	3593	3600	High	-7
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-70,692664	8,765743	3561	3600	High	-39
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-70,694395	8,770952	3585	3600	High	-15
-70,694784	8,770611	3564	3600	High	-36
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-70,696242	8,769318	3637	3600	High	37
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-70,685308	8,80028	3598	3600	High	-2
-70,662641	8,809819	3567	3600	High	-33
-70,662518	8,809456	3595	3600	High	-5
-70,662468	8,809165	3595	3600	High	-5
-70,662296	8,808826	3595	3600	High	-5
-70,662173	8,808657	3575	3600	High	-25
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-70,661004	8,809196	3515	3600	High	-85
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-70,662254	8,810403	3567	3600	High	-33
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-70,668536	8,813336	3542	3600	High	-58
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-70,668023	8,813168	3542	3600	High	-58
-70,66734	8,81322	3527	3600	High	-73
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-70,666535	8,813053	3544	3600	High	-56
-70,666119	8,812813	3613	3600	High	13
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-70,665488	8,813665	3584	3600	High	-16
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-70,664085	8,810808	3586	3600	High	-14
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-70,666567	8,809365	3594	3600	High	-6

-70,666809	8,809049	3594	3600	High	-6
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-70,67051	8,807382	3617	3600	High	17
-70,671119	8,80721	3617	3600	High	17
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-70,668724	8,811782	3626	3600	High	26
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-70,628433	8,785607	3020	3000	High	20
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-70,626755	8,786682	2995	3000	High	-5
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-70,626171	8,786879	2921	3000	High	-79
-70,625805	8,787002	2921	3000	High	-79
-70,625538	8,787221	2996	3000	High	-4
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-70,731673	8,709749	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,731511	8,708803	3204	3200	High	4
-70,731315	8,708743	3263	3200	High	63
-70,730998	8,708781	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,730413	8,708723	3187	3200	High	-13
-70,730119	8,708518	3187	3200	High	-13
-70,730008	8,708118	3187	3200	High	-13
-70,730237	8,707632	3164	3200	High	-36
-70,730466	8,707073	3223	3200	High	23
-70,730683	8,706538	3223	3200	High	23
-70,730901	8,706076	3184	3200	High	-16
-70,731251	8,705395	3222	3200	High	22
-70,731395	8,704909	3222	3200	High	22
-70,731223	8,704485	3200	3200	High	0
-70,730965	8,704208	3200	3200	High	0
-70,73061	8,703857	3200	3200	High	0
-70,730096	8,703496	3242	3200	High	42
-70,72962	8,703364	3242	3200	High	42
-70,729194	8,703476	3232	3200	High	32
-70,728695	8,703623	3192	3200	High	-8
-70,728328	8,703504	3192	3200	High	-8
-70,728069	8,702862	3212	3200	High	12
-70,727774	8,70233	3161	3200	High	-39

-70,72748	8,70187	3211	3200	High	11
-70,727196	8,701301	3211	3200	High	11
-70,726865	8,700866	3225	3200	High	25
-70,726499	8,700673	3225	3200	High	25
-70,726	8,700858	3217	3200	High	17
-70,72544	8,701103	3217	3200	High	17
-70,725061	8,700825	3169	3200	High	-31
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-70,724982	8,6996	3191	3200	High	-9
-70,725114	8,699163	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,725026	8,698666	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,725061	8,698217	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,724949	8,697684	3174	3200	High	-26
-70,725008	8,697404	3174	3200	High	-26
-70,725337	8,697197	3174	3200	High	-26
-70,725692	8,697523	3196	3200	High	-4
-70,725974	8,697995	3226	3200	High	26
-70,726244	8,698357	3226	3200	High	26
-70,726659	8,69844	3207	3200	High	7
-70,727073	8,69822	3207	3200	High	7
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-70,728363	8,697862	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,728985	8,697847	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,729461	8,69793	3250	3200	High	50
-70,729804	8,698341	3215	3200	High	15
-70,730063	8,698898	3265	3200	High	65
-70,730322	8,699503	3265	3200	High	65
-70,730554	8,699709	3249	3200	High	49
-70,73109	8,699633	3249	3200	High	49
-70,728753	8,734959	3235	3200	High	35
-70,728824	8,734425	3229	3200	High	29
-70,72887	8,733746	3201	3200	High	1
-70,72916	8,733186	3201	3200	High	1
-70,729572	8,732748	3163	3200	High	-37
-70,730057	8,732163	3210	3200	High	10
-70,730397	8,731676	3183	3200	High	-17
-70,730907	8,731237	3192	3200	High	-8
-70,731297	8,73126	3243	3200	High	43
-70,731761	8,731476	3243	3200	High	43
-70,732079	8,731644	3243	3200	High	43
-70,732593	8,731933	3243	3200	High	43
-70,733082	8,732271	3231	3200	High	31
-70,733425	8,73256	3231	3200	High	31
-70,734036	8,732873	3212	3200	High	12
-70,734645	8,732797	3217	3200	High	17
-70,735058	8,732407	3217	3200	High	17

-70,735422	8,732042	3207	3200	High	7
-70,735737	8,731603	3207	3200	High	7
-70,735906	8,731239	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,736148	8,730728	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,736364	8,729975	3272	3200	High	72
-70,736605	8,729343	3256	3200	High	56
-70,736796	8,728541	3218	3200	High	18
-70,737377	8,727617	3224	3200	High	24
-70,737865	8,727639	3224	3200	High	24
-70,738597	8,727757	3230	3200	High	30
-70,739256	8,727875	3217	3200	High	17
-70,739939	8,727969	3254	3200	High	54
-70,740499	8,727627	3242	3200	High	42
-70,740692	8,727165	3242	3200	High	42
-70,740859	8,726388	3210	3200	High	10
-70,741149	8,72578	3192	3200	High	-8
-70,741585	8,725317	3207	3200	High	7
-70,742316	8,725144	3205	3200	High	5
-70,743146	8,725358	3196	3200	High	-4
-70,743707	8,725331	3196	3200	High	-4
-70,744218	8,724989	3208	3200	High	8
-70,744143	8,72465	3208	3200	High	8
-70,74414	8,724068	3184	3200	High	-16
-70,744285	8,723679	3171	3200	High	-29
-70,744697	8,723143	3220	3200	High	20
-70,74511	8,722801	3171	3200	High	-29
-70,745596	8,722484	3211	3200	High	11
-70,74613	8,72202	3164	3200	High	-36
-70,746494	8,721533	3217	3200	High	17
-70,746663	8,72112	3209	3200	High	9
-70,746369	8,720855	3209	3200	High	9
-70,745977	8,720589	3164	3200	High	-36
-70,745538	8,720397	3218	3200	High	18
-70,744927	8,720206	3205	3200	High	5
-70,744487	8,720063	3185	3200	High	-15
-70,74417	8,719918	3185	3200	High	-15
-70,743949	8,719555	3221	3200	High	21
-70,743897	8,718998	3221	3200	High	21
-70,744016	8,718439	3201	3200	High	1
-70,744453	8,717952	3201	3200	High	1
-70,744866	8,717683	3224	3200	High	24
-70,703688	8,760332	3232	3200	High	32
-70,703523	8,759735	3232	3200	High	32
-70,703416	8,759338	3202	3200	High	2
-70,703463	8,759071	3202	3200	High	2
-70,703893	8,75865	3205	3200	High	5

-70,70446	8,758436	3205	3200	High	5
-70,705069	8,758287	3224	3200	High	24
-70,705532	8,758042	3234	3200	High	34
-70,705576	8,757145	3207	3200	High	7
-70,705987	8,756245	3174	3200	High	-26
-70,706714	8,75532	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,707004	8,754736	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,7071	8,754323	3248	3200	High	48
-70,706926	8,753693	3218	3200	High	18
-70,706799	8,752529	3202	3200	High	2
-70,707382	8,752017	3203	3200	High	3
-70,707747	8,751724	3203	3200	High	3
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-70,708207	8,751067	3221	3200	High	21
-70,708301	8,750363	3223	3200	High	23
-70,708176	8,749611	3223	3200	High	23
-70,708247	8,749222	3208	3200	High	8
-70,708391	8,74864	3185	3200	High	-15
-70,708535	8,748129	3185	3200	High	-15
-70,708629	8,747401	3167	3200	High	-33
-70,708846	8,746721	3204	3200	High	4
-70,709307	8,746185	3169	3200	High	-31
-70,709816	8,745649	3223	3200	High	23
-70,709789	8,745091	3192	3200	High	-8
-70,709764	8,744848	3192	3200	High	-8
-70,709762	8,744411	3183	3200	High	-17
-70,710103	8,744264	3183	3200	High	-17
-70,710445	8,744554	3176	3200	High	-24
-70,710885	8,744746	3218	3200	High	18
-70,711472	8,744986	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,711863	8,745178	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,7124	8,745224	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,712887	8,745077	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,71313	8,74493	3220	3200	High	20
-70,713274	8,744541	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,713272	8,74391	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,713366	8,74323	3185	3200	High	-15
-70,713361	8,742066	3183	3200	High	-17
-70,713553	8,741531	3183	3200	High	-17
-70,713649	8,741143	3168	3200	High	-32
-70,713598	8,74056	3168	3200	High	-32
-70,713596	8,740172	3166	3200	High	-34
-70,713838	8,739734	3226	3200	High	26
-70,714372	8,739198	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,714516	8,738664	3168	3200	High	-32
-70,714416	8,738179	3168	3200	High	-32

-70,714512	8,737742	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,714704	8,737111	3232	3200	High	32
-70,715092	8,736672	3201	3200	High	1
-70,715334	8,736185	3172	3200	High	-28
-70,715821	8,736183	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,716408	8,73652	3222	3200	High	22
-70,716897	8,736809	3222	3200	High	22
-70,717534	8,73734	3256	3200	High	56
-70,717923	8,737192	3264	3200	High	64
-70,718409	8,736802	3211	3200	High	11
-70,719078	8,736374	3237	3200	High	37
-70,719467	8,736166	3174	3200	High	-26
-70,719967	8,736116	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,72026	8,736175	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,720493	8,736526	3228	3200	High	28
-70,720788	8,737022	3228	3200	High	28
-70,721153	8,736899	3228	3200	High	28
-70,721615	8,736569	3226	3200	High	26
-70,722211	8,736118	3204	3200	High	4
-70,722661	8,735836	3204	3200	High	4
-70,723075	8,735798	3238	3200	High	38
-70,723368	8,735942	3238	3200	High	38
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-70,724042	8,736643	3230	3200	High	30
-70,724521	8,73726	3263	3200	High	63
-70,724963	8,73801	3223	3200	High	23
-70,725259	8,738773	3245	3200	High	45
-70,725566	8,739269	3216	3200	High	16
-70,725909	8,739437	3216	3200	High	16
-70,726322	8,739192	3215	3200	High	15
-70,726613	8,738864	3215	3200	High	15
-70,726928	8,73845	3191	3200	High	-9
-70,72728	8,738036	3219	3200	High	19
-70,727789	8,737427	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,728067	8,736928	3205	3200	High	5
-70,728394	8,736405	3205	3200	High	5
-70,728831	8,735978	3245	3200	High	45
-70,728891	8,73565	3245	3200	High	45
-70,72873	8,735251	3140	3200	High	-60
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-70,693116	8,751707	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,679478	8,786303	3172	3200	High	-28
-70,680336	8,785818	3201	3200	High	1
-70,681034	8,785574	3231	3200	High	31
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-70,682484	8,785113	3184	3200	High	-16

-70,682321	8,784659	3184	3200	High	-16
-70,682076	8,784072	3123	3200	High	-77
-70,681292	8,783085	3161	3200	High	-39
-70,681021	8,782685	3163	3200	High	-37
-70,680752	8,78266	3163	3200	High	-37
-70,680349	8,782742	3104	3200	High	-96
-70,679999	8,782502	3104	3200	High	-96
-70,679674	8,782156	3104	3200	High	-96
-70,679511	8,781756	3110	3200	High	-90
-70,679426	8,780739	3148	3200	High	-52
-70,679155	8,78042	3148	3200	High	-52
-70,678832	8,780261	3231	3200	High	31
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-70,678133	8,780264	3204	3200	High	4
-70,677836	8,779971	3125	3200	High	-75
-70,679455	8,781194	3148	3200	High	-52
-70,677268	8,779331	3149	3200	High	-51
-70,677266	8,77885	3149	3200	High	-51
-70,677345	8,778555	3156	3200	High	-44
-70,677667	8,778233	3156	3200	High	-44
-70,6778	8,777884	3182	3200	High	-18
-70,677556	8,777564	3182	3200	High	-18
-70,677206	8,777405	3182	3200	High	-18
-70,677178	8,777138	3182	3200	High	-18
-70,676961	8,776818	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,676638	8,776659	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,676263	8,776955	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,675995	8,77717	3135	3200	High	-65
-70,675618	8,777038	3173	3200	High	-27
-70,675455	8,776691	3173	3200	High	-27
-70,675425	8,775996	3208	3200	High	8
-70,675313	8,77506	3134	3200	High	-66
-70,67531	8,774391	3138	3200	High	-62
-70,675118	8,773616	3199	3200	High	-1
-70,674795	8,77343	3199	3200	High	-1
-70,674229	8,773165	3192	3200	High	-8
-70,673179	8,772849	3229	3200	High	29
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-70,671212	8,772002	3161	3200	High	-39
-70,67094	8,771388	3161	3200	High	-39
-70,670936	8,770451	3170	3200	High	-30
-70,671227	8,769487	3155	3200	High	-45
-70,671711	8,769351	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,672167	8,769215	3200	3200	High	0
-70,673107	8,768944	3233	3200	High	33
-70,673698	8,768727	3171	3200	High	-29

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-70,675951	8,767486	3182	3200	High	-18
-70,676515	8,76735	3225	3200	High	25
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-70,6781	8,766862	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,6788	8,767046	3182	3200	High	-18
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-70,680849	8,76824	3235	3200	High	35
-70,681091	8,768239	3235	3200	High	35
-70,681738	8,768745	3209	3200	High	9
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-70,682522	8,769597	3234	3200	High	34
-70,682847	8,770051	3234	3200	High	34
-70,683142	8,770049	3211	3200	High	11
-70,683223	8,769915	3211	3200	High	11
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-70,682593	8,767564	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,682348	8,766762	3186	3200	High	-14
-70,682129	8,765881	3189	3200	High	-11
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-70,681741	8,763314	3169	3200	High	-31
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-70,681387	8,762326	3195	3200	High	-5
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-70,68098	8,761552	3174	3200	High	-26
-70,680548	8,761099	3209	3200	High	9
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-70,680301	8,760057	3154	3200	High	-46
-70,680865	8,760001	3188	3200	High	-12
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-70,683015	8,759697	3195	3200	High	-5
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-70,683091	8,758654	3182	3200	High	-18
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-70,681024	8,753446	3155	3200	High	-45
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-70,680775	8,751789	3189	3200	High	-11
-70,680531	8,751442	3189	3200	High	-11
-70,680152	8,750936	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,679936	8,750722	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,679827	8,750429	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,679772	8,750054	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,679797	8,74968	3181	3200	High	-19
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-70,682732	8,750576	3228	3200	High	28
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-70,683538	8,750466	3226	3200	High	26
-70,684075	8,750249	3181	3200	High	-19
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-70,685985	8,750508	3243	3200	High	43
-70,686415	8,750373	3166	3200	High	-34
-70,686954	8,750611	3236	3200	High	36
-70,687117	8,750905	3220	3200	High	20
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-70,688167	8,751408	3246	3200	High	46
-70,688544	8,751353	3246	3200	High	46
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-70,692225	8,750882	3194	3200	High	-6
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-70,694635	8,754509	3239	3200	High	39
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-70,694854	8,755391	3272	3200	High	72

-70,69534	8,755924	3278	3200	High	78
-70,695907	8,756322	3229	3200	High	29
-70,696582	8,756961	3168	3200	High	-32
-70,697096	8,757574	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,697475	8,758268	3202	3200	High	2
-70,697801	8,759016	3227	3200	High	27
-70,6981	8,759656	3202	3200	High	2
-70,698534	8,760457	3243	3200	High	43
-70,698805	8,760991	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,698915	8,761365	3223	3200	High	23
-70,698945	8,76206	3223	3200	High	23
-70,699001	8,762595	3265	3200	High	65
-70,699218	8,762969	3305	3200	High	105
-70,699677	8,763555	3251	3200	High	51
-70,699947	8,763607	3251	3200	High	51
-70,700403	8,763391	3251	3200	High	51
-70,700992	8,762961	3223	3200	High	23
-70,701179	8,762558	3169	3200	High	-31
-70,701499	8,761995	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,701792	8,761512	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,702301	8,761109	3201	3200	High	1
-70,702704	8,760973	3201	3200	High	1
-70,703241	8,760864	3241	3200	High	41
-70,703564	8,760755	3241	3200	High	41
-70,640987	8,802685	3131	3200	High	-69
-70,64104	8,80247	3131	3200	High	-69
-70,641011	8,801962	3123	3200	High	-77
-70,641305	8,80156	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,641491	8,801211	3162	3200	High	-38
-70,641569	8,800542	3162	3200	High	-38
-70,64181	8,8003	3129	3200	High	-71
-70,642453	8,799655	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,642775	8,79952	3103	3200	High	-97
-70,643312	8,799411	3163	3200	High	-37
-70,643877	8,799381	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,643901	8,79882	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,644277	8,798577	3118	3200	High	-82
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-70,645001	8,798092	3168	3200	High	-32
-70,645431	8,798117	3200	3200	High	0
-70,646078	8,798516	3200	3200	High	0
-70,646752	8,798834	3237	3200	High	37
-70,647318	8,799045	3204	3200	High	4
-70,647831	8,799605	3257	3200	High	57
-70,648101	8,799764	3230	3200	High	30
-70,648397	8,79987	3230	3200	High	30

-70,648775	8,800243	3187	3200	High	-13
-70,649287	8,800374	3187	3200	High	-13
-70,649582	8,800186	3187	3200	High	-13
-70,65001	8,799676	3196	3200	High	-4
-70,650814	8,799003	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,65143	8,798519	3175	3200	High	-25
-70,651858	8,798089	3175	3200	High	-25
-70,652474	8,797525	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,653171	8,79696	3163	3200	High	-37
-70,653788	8,796502	3204	3200	High	4
-70,65454	8,796312	3204	3200	High	4
-70,654915	8,796043	3189	3200	High	-11
-70,655479	8,795906	3219	3200	High	19
-70,656207	8,796197	3219	3200	High	19
-70,656612	8,796597	3228	3200	High	28
-70,65688	8,796516	3228	3200	High	28
-70,657281	8,796032	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,657791	8,795736	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,658222	8,795761	3214	3200	High	14
-70,658761	8,796159	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,658952	8,796694	3218	3200	High	18
-70,659305	8,797414	3236	3200	High	36
-70,659791	8,797894	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,65993	8,798936	3212	3200	High	12
-70,660041	8,799819	3206	3200	High	6
-70,660745	8,800698	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,660827	8,801099	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,660858	8,801955	3219	3200	High	19
-70,660995	8,80257	3258	3200	High	58
-70,661078	8,803078	3266	3200	High	66
-70,661405	8,804093	3206	3200	High	6
-70,661649	8,804466	3206	3200	High	6
-70,662026	8,804598	3248	3200	High	48
-70,662563	8,804489	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,663209	8,804433	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,663827	8,80443	3168	3200	High	-32
-70,664231	8,804589	3250	3200	High	50
-70,664663	8,804935	3212	3200	High	12
-70,664854	8,805469	3270	3200	High	70
-70,665069	8,805441	3270	3200	High	70
-70,665552	8,805171	3199	3200	High	-1
-70,66598	8,804661	3199	3200	High	-1
-70,666355	8,804526	3185	3200	High	-15
-70,667161	8,804174	3232	3200	High	32
-70,667669	8,803584	3163	3200	High	-37
-70,668366	8,803046	3203	3200	High	3

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-70,670248	8,803064	3235	3200	High	35
-70,670732	8,803062	3249	3200	High	49
-70,671217	8,803274	3249	3200	High	49
-70,671781	8,803084	3253	3200	High	53
-70,671805	8,802388	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,671802	8,801586	3141	3200	High	-59
-70,672551	8,800833	3156	3200	High	-44
-70,672847	8,800779	3156	3200	High	-44
-70,673841	8,800507	3217	3200	High	17
-70,674888	8,800208	3177	3200	High	-23
-70,675639	8,799696	3204	3200	High	4
-70,676363	8,799238	3203	3200	High	3
-70,676657	8,798809	3203	3200	High	3
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-70,676411	8,798114	3199	3200	High	-1
-70,676516	8,797338	3201	3200	High	1
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-70,677911	8,79677	3185	3200	High	-15
-70,678179	8,796448	3218	3200	High	18
-70,678794	8,795589	3223	3200	High	23
-70,679249	8,795293	3175	3200	High	-25
-70,679409	8,794944	3175	3200	High	-25
-70,679568	8,794489	3135	3200	High	-65
-70,679996	8,793979	3195	3200	High	-5
-70,680723	8,794002	3216	3200	High	16
-70,681206	8,793893	3216	3200	High	16
-70,681501	8,793651	3194	3200	High	-6
-70,681471	8,792929	3194	3200	High	-6
-70,681494	8,792019	3175	3200	High	-25
-70,681599	8,791617	3175	3200	High	-25
-70,68192	8,791081	3156	3200	High	-44
-70,681972	8,790733	3156	3200	High	-44
-70,681486	8,790387	3196	3200	High	-4
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-70,681023	8,789132	3164	3200	High	-36
-70,68086	8,788785	3164	3200	High	-36
-70,680509	8,788412	3194	3200	High	-6
-70,679861	8,787773	3191	3200	High	-9
-70,679293	8,78716	3158	3200	High	-42
-70,679211	8,786733	3172	3200	High	-28
-70,681698	8,783592	3161	3200	High	-39
-70,657157	8,816337	3178	3200	High	-22
-70,657396	8,815801	3153	3200	High	-47
-70,657825	8,815425	3153	3200	High	-47
-70,65828	8,814861	3179	3200	High	-21

-70,658279	8,814593	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,657657	8,813981	3163	3200	High	-37
-70,657226	8,813742	3209	3200	High	9
-70,656823	8,813958	3159	3200	High	-41
-70,656339	8,813933	3159	3200	High	-41
-70,655665	8,813615	3151	3200	High	-49
-70,655179	8,813189	3123	3200	High	-77
-70,654935	8,812628	3134	3200	High	-66
-70,655066	8,811772	3122	3200	High	-78
-70,655117	8,811156	3137	3200	High	-63
-70,655033	8,810408	3148	3200	High	-52
-70,654841	8,809686	3148	3200	High	-52
-70,654461	8,808805	3145	3200	High	-55
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-70,65408	8,807763	3204	3200	High	4
-70,653732	8,808166	3222	3200	High	22
-70,65341	8,808489	3222	3200	High	22
-70,653144	8,808998	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,652957	8,809373	3188	3200	High	-12
-70,65277	8,809669	3205	3200	High	5
-70,652422	8,810045	3205	3200	High	5
-70,651968	8,810582	3199	3200	High	-1
-70,651753	8,810823	3199	3200	High	-1
-70,651352	8,81128	3140	3200	High	-60
-70,650896	8,811523	3147	3200	High	-53
-70,650493	8,811578	3147	3200	High	-53
-70,650087	8,811125	3158	3200	High	-42
-70,6496	8,810405	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,649385	8,810325	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,648927	8,810301	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,648578	8,810463	3175	3200	High	-25
-70,648042	8,810733	3175	3200	High	-25
-70,647425	8,811056	3185	3200	High	-15
-70,646994	8,811085	3176	3200	High	-24
-70,646375	8,810927	3176	3200	High	-24
-70,645783	8,81085	3202	3200	High	2
-70,645273	8,811146	3223	3200	High	23
-70,644792	8,811683	3172	3200	High	-28
-70,644416	8,811872	3159	3200	High	-41
-70,643824	8,811821	3159	3200	High	-41
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-70,64379	8,81027	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,64403	8,809787	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,644323	8,809144	3154	3200	High	-46
-70,644829	8,807884	3180	3200	High	-20

-70,644719	8,80751	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,644261	8,807298	3142	3200	High	-58
-70,643668	8,806953	3145	3200	High	-55
-70,643398	8,806687	3145	3200	High	-55
-70,643127	8,806287	3145	3200	High	-55
-70,643152	8,805671	3139	3200	High	-61
-70,643365	8,805242	3125	3200	High	-75
-70,643523	8,804626	3125	3200	High	-75
-70,643575	8,804171	3119	3200	High	-81
-70,643573	8,80361	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,64341	8,803262	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,642952	8,803211	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,642388	8,803401	3173	3200	High	-27
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-70,641742	8,80327	3136	3200	High	-64
-70,641392	8,803004	3136	3200	High	-64
-70,626582	8,841858	3214	3200	High	14
-70,626474	8,841618	3214	3200	High	14
-70,626041	8,841138	3201	3200	High	1
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-70,625177	8,840393	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,624799	8,840073	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,624636	8,839593	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,624418	8,839085	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,623905	8,838606	3216	3200	High	16
-70,623527	8,838153	3163	3200	High	-37
-70,623122	8,837887	3191	3200	High	-9
-70,622851	8,837514	3146	3200	High	-54
-70,623092	8,837272	3191	3200	High	-9
-70,623738	8,837216	3191	3200	High	-9
-70,624302	8,837106	3212	3200	High	12
-70,62508	8,836728	3176	3200	High	-24
-70,625807	8,836805	3160	3200	High	-40
-70,6264	8,837204	3194	3200	High	-6
-70,626806	8,837657	3194	3200	High	-6
-70,626998	8,838512	3219	3200	High	19
-70,627242	8,839046	3205	3200	High	5
-70,628133	8,839738	3203	3200	High	3
-70,628754	8,84027	3166	3200	High	-34
-70,629483	8,840856	3229	3200	High	29
-70,629887	8,841068	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,630264	8,841093	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,631555	8,841194	3161	3200	High	-39
-70,632366	8,8421	3236	3200	High	36
-70,632904	8,842098	3236	3200	High	36
-70,633522	8,841962	3159	3200	High	-41

-70,634004	8,841558	3197	3200	High	-3
-70,634593	8,840994	3183	3200	High	-17
-70,635586	8,840428	3221	3200	High	21
-70,636095	8,839971	3159	3200	High	-41
-70,636927	8,839486	3141	3200	High	-59
-70,637733	8,839402	3180	3200	High	-20
-70,638297	8,839212	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,638674	8,839291	3181	3200	High	-19
-70,639322	8,839823	3231	3200	High	31
-70,639353	8,840786	3264	3200	High	64
-70,640106	8,840809	3228	3200	High	28
-70,640539	8,841262	3225	3200	High	25
-70,641024	8,841554	3225	3200	High	25
-70,641454	8,841445	3209	3200	High	9
-70,642151	8,840881	3216	3200	High	16
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-70,643867	8,839749	3235	3200	High	35
-70,644349	8,839159	3204	3200	High	4
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-70,645258	8,838112	3208	3200	High	8
-70,645796	8,838002	3229	3200	High	29
-70,646386	8,837598	3198	3200	High	-2
-70,646706	8,837062	3159	3200	High	-41
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-70,64756	8,83556	3194	3200	High	-6
-70,647933	8,834702	3217	3200	High	17
-70,647931	8,834381	3203	3200	High	3
-70,647715	8,834168	3164	3200	High	-36
-70,647553	8,833848	3164	3200	High	-36
-70,647524	8,833367	3191	3200	High	-9
-70,647601	8,832671	3179	3200	High	-21
-70,647893	8,831813	3161	3200	High	-39
-70,64824	8,83109	3186	3200	High	-14
-70,648505	8,830393	3148	3200	High	-52
-70,649175	8,829855	3179	3200	High	-21
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-70,649953	8,829397	3145	3200	High	-55
-70,650384	8,829395	3145	3200	High	-55
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-70,651682	8,831101	3193	3200	High	-7
-70,651953	8,831555	3234	3200	High	34
-70,652223	8,831794	3182	3200	High	-18

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-70,652841	8,831551	3182	3200	High	-18
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-70,65348	8,83021	3142	3200	High	-58
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-70,654389	8,829029	3161	3200	High	-39
-70,654522	8,828494	3134	3200	High	-66
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-70,655301	8,828383	3188	3200	High	-12
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-70,656833	8,828056	3218	3200	High	18
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-70,658711	8,827057	3155	3200	High	-45
-70,658602	8,826764	3155	3200	High	-45
-70,658305	8,826524	3155	3200	High	-45
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-70,65771	8,825724	3151	3200	High	-49
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-70,657088	8,824951	3176	3200	High	-24
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-70,65756	8,822247	3181	3200	High	-19
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-70,656376	8,822172	3165	3200	High	-35
-70,65608	8,822174	3139	3200	High	-61
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-70,655433	8,821722	3178	3200	High	-22
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-70,655935	8,819686	3176	3200	High	-24
-70,656094	8,819177	3147	3200	High	-53
-70,656199	8,818669	3119	3200	High	-81
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-70,620167	8,838809	2958	3000	High	-42
-70,620248	8,838756	2958	3000	High	-42
-70,620381	8,838354	3027	3000	High	27
-70,620676	8,838138	3013	3000	High	13
-70,620972	8,838217	3013	3000	High	13
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-70,637012	8,835967	2958	3000	High	-42
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-70,636194	8,836519	2949	3000	High	-51
-70,635658	8,836963	2949	3000	High	-51
-70,635283	8,837339	2945	3000	High	-55
-70,634962	8,837648	2945	3000	High	-55
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-70,743634	8,711305	2976	3000	High	-24
-70,743823	8,711518	3037	3000	High	37
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-70,742505	8,717196	3019	3000	High	19
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-70,739737	8,72312	3048	3000	High	48
-70,722365	8,693105	3014	3000	High	14
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-70,721778	8,694017	2991	3000	High	-9
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-70,724377	8,703983	2986	3000	High	-14
-70,724966	8,703446	3053	3000	High	53
-70,725314	8,702989	3053	3000	High	53
-70,725582	8,702828	3089	3000	High	89
-70,726013	8,703013	3028	3000	High	28
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-70,726746	8,704615	3010	3000	High	10
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-70,757476	8,721995	3770	3800	High	-30
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-70,75707	8,721328	3717	3800	High	-83
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-70,757552	8,720871	3772	3800	High	-28
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-70,704845	8,783708	3392	3400	High	-8

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-70,709867	8,776436	3413	3400	High	13
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-70,566148	8,786731	1793	1800	Medium	993
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-70,56523	8,785906	1801	1800	Medium	1001
-70,564691	8,785587	1801	1800	Medium	1001
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-70,561572	8,785653	1772	1800	Medium	972
-70,56114	8,785281	1732	1800	Medium	932
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-70,563169	8,788081	1837	1800	Medium	1037
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-70,565316	8,787029	1817	1800	Medium	1017
-70,564268	8,787381	1842	1800	Medium	1042

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-70,53119	8,801348	1230	1200	Medium	30
-70,530946	8,800921	1202	1200	Medium	2
-70,530675	8,800575	1202	1200	Medium	2
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-70,530027	8,799855	1206	1200	Medium	6
-70,529944	8,79932	1206	1200	Medium	6
-70,530399	8,798864	1206	1200	Medium	6
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-70,52991	8,797688	1196	1200	Medium	-4
-70,529346	8,797878	1193	1200	Medium	-7
-70,528999	8,798388	1204	1200	Medium	4
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-70,528171	8,799889	1207	1200	Medium	7
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-70,527313	8,800508	1220	1200	Medium	20
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-70,527022	8,801499	1199	1200	Medium	-1
-70,527855	8,801469	1209	1200	Medium	9
-70,528391	8,801039	1226	1200	Medium	26
-70,528903	8,80117	1229	1200	Medium	29
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-70,508181	8,677547	587	600	Low	-13
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-70,508096	8,676531	563	600	Low	-37
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-70,508717	8,67717	587	600	Low	-13
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-70,522667	8,676285	568	600	Low	-32
-70,522398	8,67634	568	600	Low	-32
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-70,523716	8,68313	557	600	Low	-43
-70,523341	8,683506	557	600	Low	-43
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-70,52191	8,688541	574	600	Low	-26
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-70,52354	8,692762	605	600	Low	5
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-70,525943	8,688686	644	600	Low	44
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-70,504758	8,739387	780	800	Medium	-20
-70,505189	8,739653	787	800	Medium	-13
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-70,513867	8,744274	753	800	Medium	-47
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-70,512197	8,743799	780	800	Medium	-20
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-70,548671	8,739638	952	1000	Medium	-48
-70,548668	8,739077	952	1000	Medium	-48
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-70,560314	8,746145	978	1000	Medium	-22
-70,560504	8,746519	947	1000	Medium	-53
-70,56064	8,746946	947	1000	Medium	-53
-70,560453	8,747215	946	1000	Medium	-54
-70,551567	8,705303	736	800	Medium	-64
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-70,550352	8,70397	783	800	Medium	-17
-70,549948	8,703678	730	800	Medium	-70
-70,549222	8,703787	785	800	Medium	-15

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-70,547796	8,703499	762	800	Medium	-38
-70,547393	8,703501	762	800	Medium	-38
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-70,546371	8,703665	751	800	Medium	-49
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-70,542105	8,705743	862	800	Medium	62
-70,542188	8,706438	857	800	Medium	57
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-70,542008	8,708285	794	800	Medium	-6
-70,542306	8,708792	827	800	Medium	27
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-70,543168	8,70935	855	800	Medium	55
-70,543762	8,709963	852	800	Medium	52
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-70,541031	8,712783	799	800	Medium	-1
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-70,540741	8,714095	792	800	Medium	-8
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-70,542838	8,71406	797	800	Medium	-3
-70,543083	8,714888	797	800	Medium	-3
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-70,544234	8,720127	811	800	Medium	11
-70,544103	8,72093	815	800	Medium	15
-70,544185	8,721278	826	800	Medium	26
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-70,54637	8,722901	847	800	Medium	47
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-70,546858	8,723915	791	800	Medium	-9
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-70,547239	8,725064	807	800	Medium	7
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-70,549095	8,725244	777	800	Medium	-23
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-70,550843	8,725156	753	800	Medium	-47
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-70,550975	8,724594	753	800	Medium	-47
-70,550436	8,724329	724	800	Medium	-76
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-70,548599	8,722223	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,548703	8,721473	779	800	Medium	-21
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-70,548355	8,715134	779	800	Medium	-21
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-70,547544	8,714201	778	800	Medium	-22
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-70,547351	8,712918	771	800	Medium	-29
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-70,547453	8,71174	806	800	Medium	6
-70,547909	8,711417	806	800	Medium	6
-70,548983	8,711119	800	800	Medium	0
-70,550031	8,710793	806	800	Medium	6
-70,551294	8,710601	794	800	Medium	-6

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-70,552255	8,709099	757	800	Medium	-43
-70,55185	8,708512	779	800	Medium	-21
-70,551792	8,707629	795	800	Medium	-5
-70,552031	8,706853	817	800	Medium	17
-70,551839	8,70589	790	800	Medium	-10
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-70,568581	8,697368	527	600	Low	-73
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-70,567396	8,696998	533	600	Low	-67
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-70,566914	8,697375	534	600	Low	-66
-70,567346	8,697694	534	600	Low	-66
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-70,568102	8,698547	554	600	Low	-46
-70,568533	8,698759	557	600	Low	-43
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-70,564853	8,680074	727	800	Medium	-73
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-70,565558	8,681489	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,565935	8,681782	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,566232	8,682075	784	800	Medium	-16
-70,566744	8,682207	782	800	Medium	-18
-70,567254	8,682204	762	800	Medium	-38
-70,567387	8,681803	734	800	Medium	-66
-70,567198	8,681536	734	800	Medium	-66
-70,566712	8,681163	743	800	Medium	-57
-70,5662	8,680818	759	800	Medium	-41
-70,566118	8,680524	759	800	Medium	-41
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-70,562069	8,676634	700	800	Medium	-100

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-70,562314	8,677302	755	800	Medium	-45
-70,561857	8,677251	767	800	Medium	-33
-70,561562	8,677439	767	800	Medium	-33
-70,560783	8,677656	757	800	Medium	-43
-70,573394	8,665218	706	800	Medium	-94
-70,573098	8,665139	706	800	Medium	-94
-70,572962	8,664658	706	800	Medium	-94
-70,57331	8,664255	676	800	Medium	-124
-70,573581	8,664816	706	800	Medium	-94
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-70,604479	8,590316	548	600	Low	-52
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-70,532339	8,654644	554	600	Low	-46
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-70,537773	8,662059	575	600	Low	-25
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-70,535547	8,66354	599	600	Low	-1
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-70,520501	8,634442	359	400	Low	-41
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-70,520319	8,638151	381	400	Low	-19
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-70,51987	8,638827	383	400	Low	-17
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-70,472109	8,741975	756	800	Medium	-44
-70,472461	8,742615	769	800	Medium	-31
-70,472517	8,743204	786	800	Medium	-14
-70,472789	8,743925	798	800	Medium	-2
-70,473032	8,744272	781	800	Medium	-19
-70,473437	8,744698	795	800	Medium	-5
-70,473816	8,745259	772	800	Medium	-28
-70,473791	8,745794	782	800	Medium	-18
-70,473228	8,74609	798	800	Medium	-2
-70,472367	8,746014	812	800	Medium	12

-70,471882	8,745882	815	800	Medium	15
-70,471129	8,745831	823	800	Medium	23
-70,469169	8,760259	965	1000	Medium	-35
-70,469034	8,760152	965	1000	Medium	-35
-70,468712	8,760421	987	1000	Medium	-13
-70,468741	8,760876	987	1000	Medium	-13
-70,469011	8,761196	986	1000	Medium	-14
-70,469336	8,761623	1000	1000	Medium	0
-70,469606	8,761916	999	1000	Medium	-1
-70,470037	8,762182	984	1000	Medium	-16
-70,470413	8,76202	999	1000	Medium	-1
-70,470842	8,761617	974	1000	Medium	-26
-70,470652	8,761216	962	1000	Medium	-38
-70,470059	8,761005	963	1000	Medium	-37
-70,470835	8,746207	823	1000	Medium	-177
-70,469708	8,760685	963	1000	Medium	-37
-70,549912	8,73107	728	800	Medium	-72
-70,549696	8,730911	728	800	Medium	-72
-70,548998	8,731127	739	800	Medium	-61
-70,548919	8,731476	762	800	Medium	-38
-70,549378	8,731982	762	800	Medium	-38
-70,55008	8,732541	772	800	Medium	-28
-70,551022	8,732912	769	800	Medium	-31
-70,551237	8,73275	769	800	Medium	-31
-70,550938	8,732136	769	800	Medium	-31
-70,550182	8,73139	755	800	Medium	-45
-70,549374	8,730965	739	800	Medium	-61
-70,550642	8,73187	740	800	Medium	-60
-70,54981	8,732274	772	800	Medium	-28
-70,550538	8,732726	769	800	Medium	-31
-70,538885	8,69441	555	600	Low	-45
-70,538656	8,694237	561	600	Low	-39
-70,538481	8,694024	561	600	Low	-39
-70,538802	8,693835	555	600	Low	-45
-70,539153	8,693981	555	600	Low	-45
-70,539114	8,694342	555	600	Low	-45
-70,539963	8,695034	572	600	Low	-28
-70,539708	8,694928	572	600	Low	-28
-70,539787	8,694527	533	600	Low	-67
-70,540204	8,694579	533	600	Low	-67
-70,540353	8,694859	572	600	Low	-28